

Agro2Circular

D8.7 – Toolkit of guidelines and training materials (final)

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Table of contents

1.1.	List of figures.....	7
1.2.	List of tables	8
2.	List of abbreviations.....	9
3.	Glossary.....	10
1	Executive summary <abstract>	12
2	Introduction	13
3	Methodology	15
3.1.	Identification of Training Needs and Stakeholders	15
3.2.	Participant profile and demographic overview	16
3.3.	Data analysis and results	17
4.	Final list of guidelines and training materials	27
4.1.	Primary Education.....	27
4.2.	Secondary Education.....	28
4.3.	Higher Education.....	29
4.4.	Industry/Businesses	30
4.5.	Public Sector.....	31
5.	ANNEX I - Training Plan for local actors: Primary education	39
5.1.	PE1: "The Sustainable Farm" or "The School Garden"	40
5.2.	PE2: The Park Clean-Up Team	44
5.3.	PE3: The Repair Shop	49
5.4.	PE4: Waste sorting game	53
5.5.	PE5: Online Crossword puzzles.....	57
6.	ANNEX II - Training Plan for local actors: secondary education/bachelor	60

6.1. SE1: Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM) – Practical Case Study Analysis	61
6.2. SE2: Brainstorming new circular business models	66
6.3. SE3: Educational presentations.....	70
6.4. SE4: Debate: circular economy vs lineal economy	75
6.5. SE5: Create a prototype business using circular economy principles	78
6.6. SE6: Circular business challenge: sustainable packaging and food products from waste	82
6.7. SE7: Designing a circular economy strategy for a region	86
6.8. SE8: Exploring circular economy: practical approaches to recycling, repair, and bioremediation	90
6.9. SE9: Career and professions related to the circular economy.....	95
7. ANNEX III - Training Plan for local actors: Higher education ..	100
7.1. HE1: Study Modules for Higher Education. Circular Economy Business Models: Analysis and implementation	101
7.2. HE2: Financial mechanism assessment for the circular economy: study modules	116
7.3. HE3: Implementing Circular Economy in the agrifood sector: a case study approach	132
7.4. HE4: Introductory coursework on governance in the circular economy....	146
7.5. HE5: Evaluating circular economy solutions: Lifecycle based approaches	160
7.6. HE6: A2C Data Integration System (DIS) Training Outline for Computer Science Students	174
8. ANNEX IV – Training Plan for local actors: Industry/business	177
8.1. IB1: Circular Business Models: guidelines & regional success stories.....	178
8.2. IB2: Guidelines for value chain analysis session on circular business models in the agrifood sector.....	183
8.3. IB3: Industrial symbiosis: guidelines with case studies in the agrifood industry	193

8.4.	IB4: Creating value from waste in the agro-industry: cases.....	198
8.5.	IB5: Funding opportunities for the circular economy: infosheet	201
8.6.	IB6: Circular Economy regulation in the agrifood sector: infosheet	206
8.7.	IB7: Regulation of the circular economy in Spanish industry: a guide for companies.	212
8.8.	IB8: Data Integration System (DIS) tool.....	219
8.9.	IB9: Standardisation: guidelines for the agrifood industry	223
8.10.	IB10: Promoting awareness of circular economy at managerial level	237
8.11.	IB11: Good practice Directory for circular economy in the agrifood sector 240	
8.12.	IB12: Industry Mentoring Programme	248
9.	ANNEX V - Training Plan for local actors: Public Sector	257
9.1.	PS1: Circular Public Procurement: guidelines and best practices	258
9.2.	PS2: Guidelines for fostering public engagement in circular economy	273
10.	Annex VI. References	302

1.1. List of figures

Figure 1 - D.8.6 & D.8.7 relationship.....	14
Figure 2 - Breakdown of responses per questionnaire section	18
Figure 3 - Heatmap illustrating topic relevance for section 2	19
Figure 4 - Relevance of topics in primary education	21
Figure 5 - Relevance of topics in secondary education	23
Figure 6 - Relevance of topics in university education.....	25
Figure 7 - Business Model Canvas example template.....	65
Figure 8 - Business Model Canvas example template (2).....	191
Figure 9 - Final 30 selected good practices	245
Figure 10 - Quintuple Helix of Stakeholders representation. From van Bueren (2023)....	277

1.2. List of tables

Table 1 - Final list of Guidelines and training materials	38
Table 2 - 75 selected good practices for analysis	243

2. List of abbreviations

A2C – Agro2Circular

CE – Circular Economy

CIFEA – Integrated Agricultural Training Centres (Centros Integrados de Formación y Experiencias Agrarias)

DIS – Digital Integration System

EU – European Union

GPP – Green Public Procurement

LCA – Life Cycle Assessment

M – Month (referring to project timeline)

NGO – Non-Governmental Organisation

SME – Small and Medium-sized Enterprise

WP – Work Package

3. Glossary

Agro2Circular (A2C)

A European project under the Horizon 2020 programme that focuses on promoting circular economy solutions within the agrifood value chain, particularly through waste valorisation, technological innovation, and knowledge transfer.

Circular economy (CE) in the agrifood sector

The application of circular economy principles to the agrifood industry, aiming to minimise waste, optimise resource use, and create value through upcycling organic and plastic waste streams.

Circular public procurement

A procurement strategy that prioritises products and services with high circularity potential, such as food items with sustainable certifications, recycled-content packaging, and waste-efficient supply chains.

Digital integration system (DIS)

A data management system designed for tracking and optimising waste and resource flows in the agrifood sector, ensuring transparency and efficiency in circular economy processes.

Food waste valorisation

The process of repurposing food waste and by-products into valuable products, such as bio-based materials, animal feed, bioplastics, or energy sources, reducing disposal and improving resource efficiency.

Green public procurement (GPP) in agrifood

The integration of environmental and circularity criteria in the procurement of food products, favouring organic, local, and sustainably produced goods while reducing food waste and packaging impact.

Industrial symbiosis in agrifood

A model where agrifood businesses collaborate to utilise each other's waste streams as raw materials, promoting efficiency and reducing environmental impact.

Knowledge transfer in circular economy

The structured process of disseminating circular economy knowledge, practices, and innovations from research and industry experts to stakeholders, including businesses, educators, and policymakers.

Life cycle thinking in agrifood procurement

A methodology that assesses the environmental, social, and economic impacts of food products throughout their lifecycle, from production and processing to distribution, consumption, and disposal.

Sustainable food systems

Food production and consumption models that prioritise environmental sustainability, social responsibility, and economic viability, ensuring minimal waste and efficient resource use.

Training toolkit for circular economy

A set of educational materials developed within A2C to support self-learning and capacity building for different stakeholders, including public administrations, industry, and educational institutions, to facilitate the adoption of circular economy practices in the agrifood sector.

1 Executive summary <abstract>

This deliverable presents the finalised toolkit of guidelines and training materials developed under Task 8.6 – Training, knowledge transfer, and guidelines to promote the A2C circular model. The objective has been to create autonomous training resources for different stakeholders, supporting the adoption and dissemination of circular economy principles, with a particular focus on the agrifood value chain. The materials have been developed based on various activities and consultations with stakeholders from both within and outside the project consortium. This process has ensured that they address real needs and provide a practical foundation for promoting and developing circular economy practices.

D8.7 is the final version of the toolkit, building on the initial draft presented in D8.6. It includes a set of training resources designed for a wide range of users, from schools and vocational training centres to universities, public administrations, industry, and civil society organisations. The materials are intended to support self-learning and capacity building, making circular economy knowledge more accessible and applicable across different sectors.

2 Introduction

This deliverable is framed within the overall objective of **WP8 - A2C outreach: Communication, dissemination, exploitation, training & policy recommendations**. Thus, it is part of the activities aimed at widespreading the project results and engaging stakeholders, while raising awareness and knowledge about circular economy and innovations produced by Agro2Circular (A2C).

More specifically, this is the last outcome of the **Task 8.6 Training, knowledge transfer and guidelines/recommendations to promote A2C circular model. (M9- M36)**, aiming at delivering specific resources and open learning materials to contribute to the promotion of the model, taking into account the facilitators and barriers identified in WP7. The task includes the elaboration of an autonomous training plan for local actors and education services for local communities and training modules/guidelines for EU stakeholders to better implement/transfer the knowledge acquired during the project and all lessons learnt.

Two deliverables were developed from this task: D8.6 Toolkit of guidelines and training materials (Draft), which includes a first outline of some of the materials/guidelines to be developed in the framework of Task 8.6; and **D8.7 Toolkit of guidelines and training materials (Final)**, which is presented in this document as a developed and final version of the contents foreseen in Task 8.6, as shown in the following figure:

Figure 1 - D.8.6 & D.8.7 relationship

Therefore, D.8.7 contains a set of didactic materials intended to be shared with various actors and institutions for education/training/dissemination of circular economy knowledge and competences. This includes different target groups, ranging from non-higher education institutions (schools, secondary schools, vocational schools) to higher education institutions (graduates, master and doctoral students) including the general population, the industry, Civil Society Organisations and Public Administrations.

3 Methodology

The development of the training materials and guidelines presented in this deliverable is based on the activities carried out within the Agro2Circular (A2C) project, specifically those related to the design and validation of the A2C model, as well as the elaboration of policy briefs. The process has been structured to ensure that the identified areas and stakeholders benefit from targeted training materials that facilitate the promotion of circular economy principles at the regional level, with a specific focus on the agri-food sector.

3.1. Identification of Training Needs and Stakeholders

The selection of training materials and guidelines was informed by the results of a structured questionnaire administered to project partners and external stakeholders. This questionnaire aimed to identify relevant training topics and preferred formats for capacity-building materials. Participants were asked to evaluate the importance of different training topics for businesses, industries, and entrepreneurs on a scale from 1 (not relevant) to 7 (extremely relevant). The topics included:

- **Circular economy business models:** Understanding innovative business models that align with circular economy principles.
- **Industrial symbiosis approach:** Examining collaboration between businesses where waste or by-products of one entity serve as resources for another.
- **Value creation through waste in the agri-food sector:** Exploring opportunities for reusing and repurposing waste streams.
- **Public and private financing schemes for circular economy:** Assessing funding opportunities at regional and national levels.
- **Legal frameworks for circular economy at the EU, national, and regional levels:** Understanding the regulatory landscape and its implications.
- **Technological solutions for integrating circular economy in the agri-food industry:** Introducing digital tools such as the DIS system for real-time management and traceability of materials and organic products.
- **Standardisation:** Evaluating the role of standardisation in circular economy processes.

Respondents were also asked to assess the usefulness of different training formats for each topic, rating them on a scale from 1 (not useful) to 7 (extremely useful). The proposed formats included:

- **In-person workshops** with expert presentations and interactive discussions.
- **Online interactive sessions** with case studies and practical exercises.
- **Written guides and self-learning materials** including case studies and exercises.
- **Video-based courses** with tutor support and structured learning pathways.
- **Podcasts and expert interviews** showcasing real-world examples and experiences.

The questionnaire also provided respondents with the opportunity to highlight any specific aspects of the topics that they found particularly relevant or identify additional training needs that were not originally included.

3.2. Participant profile and demographic overview

A total of **44 participants** responded to the questionnaire, representing a diverse range of sectors and professional backgrounds. The demographic distribution is summarised as follows:

- **Gender Distribution:** The sample included **24 men (54.5%)**, **19 women (43.2%)**, and **1 non-binary respondent (2.3%)**, ensuring a balanced representation of perspectives.
- **Geographic Distribution:** The majority of participants are based in **Murcia, Spain (21 respondents, 47.7%)**, followed by **Cartagena (4)**, **Lorca (2)**, **Molina de Segura (2)**, and **Almería (2)**. Additionally, one participant resides in **Leeuwarden, Netherlands**, reflecting some international engagement.
- **Sectoral Representation:** The respondents belong to various professional sectors, with the highest representation from:
 - **Academia and Research (17 participants, 38.6%)**
 - **Industry (11 participants, 25.0%)**
 - **Education (4 participants, 9.1%)**
 - **Public Administration (4 participants, 9.1%)**
 - **Agri-food Sector (2 participants, 4.5%)**
 - The remaining respondents are affiliated with **business associations, civil society, consulting, and technical services**.

- **Institutional Affiliation:** The participants represent a **broad range of organisations**, with:
 - **13 distinct institutions from academia and research**
 - **11 different companies from the industrial sector**
 - **4 institutions from education and public administration each**
 - The rest are spread across agri-food, consulting, and business associations.

This diversity in professional backgrounds and expertise has provided a comprehensive perspective on the training needs and priorities for the development of educational materials within the **Agro2Circular** project.

3.3. Data analysis and results

3.3.1. Sectoral representation of respondents & Institutional affiliation

The responses to the questionnaire were distributed across various professional sectors, with academia/research and industry being the most represented categories. These two sectors combined accounted for 24 responses, indicating a strong engagement from research institutions and industrial stakeholders. The respondents represented a diverse array of institutions. The ten most represented organisations illustrate the variety of perspectives incorporated into the study. Among these, Fundación Cajamar and CTNC (Centro Tecnológico Nacional de la Conserva y Alimentación) had the highest number of responses, each with two participants. The remaining institutions contributed individual responses, covering universities, business associations, agri-food foundations, independent consultants, and companies across different industries.

3.3.2. Sections of the Questionnaire Answered

The majority of respondents completed Section 2, which focused on training materials for the agri-food industry, businesses, entrepreneurs, vocational training institutions, and CIFEAs centres. Notably, all remaining sections received the same number of responses, indicating a relatively balanced interest across different target groups.

Figure 2 - Breakdown of responses per questionnaire section

3.3.3. Training Materials for the Agri-Food Industry, Businesses, and Entrepreneurs (Section 2)

Relevance of Training Topics

A heatmap analysis of the responses illustrates the perceived relevance of various training topics related to the circular economy. Darker tones indicate higher relevance, while lighter tones represent lower perceived importance.

- **Most relevant topics:**

- *Industrial symbiosis approach*: The highest-rated topic, highlighting the strong interest in inter-sectoral collaboration, where waste and by-products from one entity serve as inputs for another.
- *Creating value through waste in the agri-food industry*: Participants emphasised the importance of waste valorisation as a key circular economy strategy for the agri-food sector.
- *Business models based on circular economy principles*: The transformation of business models towards circular economy principles was also perceived as a high-priority area.

- **Moderately relevant topics:**

- *Technological solutions (DIS tool)*: The DIS tool for waste management and material traceability received considerable attention, though not as high as the previously mentioned topics.
- *Financing schemes and opportunities*: While considered important, financing mechanisms ranked lower, potentially indicating that industry actors view access to funding as a challenge but not their most immediate concern.
- **Lower relevance (though still important):**
 - Standardisation
 - Legal regulation at the EU, national, and regional levels

These topics scored slightly lower, suggesting that while regulatory frameworks are important, respondents might already be familiar with these aspects or do not prioritise them in their immediate training needs.

Figure 3 - Heatmap illustrating topic relevance for section 2

Preferred Training Formats

To further analyse respondents' preferences, the industrial symbiosis approach, the most highly rated topic, serves as an example. The preferred formats for training materials in this area are:

- *Written guidelines with practical examples*: This format was the most favoured across all topics, highlighting a preference for self-learning materials.
- *Case studies and success stories*: Respondents showed a strong interest in learning from real-world applications of circular economy strategies.
- *Online courses and video materials*: While face-to-face training sessions were generally less preferred, online interactive sessions and recorded content were considered useful.

Additional Comments

Open-ended responses provided further insights, with several key topics emerging as areas of interest for training materials:

- Green public procurement and circular public procurement
- Energy efficiency and cogeneration with agri-food by-products
- Awareness-raising for management on circular economy benefits
- Regional-level by-product exchange platforms
- End-of-waste status and product design
- Waste mapping and value creation through waste

These insights have informed the refinement of training materials and the integration of new elements into the Agro2Circular model.

3.3.4. Training Materials for Primary Education (Section 3)

Relevance of Training Topics

The most relevant topics for primary education respondents highlight the importance of foundational knowledge rather than technical content:

- *General considerations on the circular economy*: Rated as the most important topic, indicating the need to introduce basic circular economy concepts at an early age.
- *Agri-food, plastics, and circular economy*: Ranked second, reflecting concerns over plastic use and food waste, making this an essential educational area.
- *Agro2Circular project results*: Received moderate ratings, showing that while project-specific content is valuable, respondents prioritise broader educational topics.
- *Green entrepreneurship and careers in sustainability*: Considered important to introduce future career paths related to sustainability and the circular economy.

- **Circular business models:** This topic received the lowest rating, suggesting it may be too complex for younger students.

Figure 4 - Relevance of topics in primary education

The results align closely with recent findings in the literature regarding the role of circular economy (CE) and sustainability education in primary schools. As shown in the heatmap and qualitative feedback, primary-level stakeholders prioritised foundational topics such as general CE principles and the agri-food/plastics nexus, while assigning lower relevance to more technical or complex topics such as business models. This mirrors the findings of Kosta et al. (2025¹), who highlighted that CE remains largely absent from primary curricula and emphasised the need to introduce it more systematically at earlier educational stages. Their study revealed that teachers are generally supportive of embedding CE and

¹ [1] A. D. Kosta, K. M. Keramitsoglou, and K. P. Tsagarakis, "Circular economy and sustainable development in primary education," *Frontiers in Sustainability*, vol. 6, Art. no. 1414055, Feb. 2025. doi: 10.3389/frsus.2025.1414055

sustainability concepts into environmental studies, particularly through experiential and play-based methods—an approach echoed in our respondents' preference for interactive, hands-on formats like role-playing, workshops, and visual materials. Furthermore, Kosta et al. found that educators' awareness and personal engagement with sustainability strongly influence their willingness to promote CE content in schools, reinforcing our strategy to design flexible, engaging, and accessible materials that empower teachers as key facilitators of early-stage CE education.

Preferred Training Formats

Respondents highlighted the importance of interactive and practical learning approaches, including:

- Workshops and hands-on activities
- Role-playing games
- Crossword puzzles and visual materials

These formats align with the need for engaging, age-appropriate education on circular economy concepts.

3.3.5. Training Materials for Secondary and High School Education (Section 4)

Relevance of Training Topics

At the secondary and high school level, training needs become more career-oriented:

- *Green entrepreneurship and career opportunities*: Rated highest, reflecting the importance of preparing students for sustainability-related professions.
- *General considerations on the circular economy*: Maintained a high rating, confirming that foundational knowledge is still critical.
- *Agri-food, plastics, and circular economy*: Highly rated, though slightly lower than in primary education.
- *Circular business models*: Gained relevance at this level, as students begin to engage with economic and business-related concepts.
- *Evaluation of financial mechanisms for the circular economy*: Received the lowest rating, indicating that financial considerations may be more relevant for university-level students.

Figure 5 - Relevance of topics in secondary education

Preferred Training Formats

- Debates and case studies
- Creative assignments (e.g., research papers, investigative projects)
- Simulation activities focused on business and finance

These formats align with secondary students' cognitive development, fostering critical thinking and independent learning. Moreover, such interactive, problem-based, and student-centred methods have been recommended in emerging pedagogies for circular economy education. For instance, Kirchherr and Piscicelli (2019²) propose five core principles for circular economy teaching—interactivity, non-dogmatism, reciprocity, constructive alignment, and problem-based learning—highlighting the value of exercises such as

² [2] J. Kirchherr and L. Piscicelli, "Towards an education for the circular economy (ECE): Five teaching principles and a case study," *Resources, Conservation & Recycling*, vol. 150, p. 104406, 2019. DOI: [10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104406](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104406).

simulations, circular business model design, and critical scenario planning. These approaches are not only well-suited to higher education, but also offer pedagogical benefits when adapted for upper-secondary students preparing for vocational or academic careers in sustainability fields.

3.3.6. Training Materials for University Students (Section 5)

Relevance of Training Topics

For university students, technical and strategic topics gained prominence:

- *Technological solutions for circular economy in the agri-food sector*: The most highly rated topic, indicating a demand for applied knowledge.
- *Circular economy business models*
- *Financial mechanisms and funding opportunities*
- *Governance of the circular economy*
- *Natural capital accounting and life cycle assessment*
- *Legal regulation at different levels*

These rankings demonstrate the importance of providing in-depth, analytical content to university-level learners.

Figure 6 - Relevance of topics in university education

Preferred Training Formats

- Written modules with case studies
- Innovation projects and real-world applications
- Research-based assignments and policy analysis

Respondents also suggested integrating circular economy topics into different academic disciplines, such as engineering and business studies. In the case of environmental sciences, circular economy content is already present to some extent—particularly through courses in waste management, industrial ecology, and sustainability assessment. However,

the degree and depth of integration can vary across institutions and programmes, suggesting room for more consistent and comprehensive incorporation of CE principles.

4. Final list of guidelines and training materials

The findings from the questionnaire have been integrated into the broader framework of Task 8.6, which aims to develop a comprehensive training plan for local actors and education services, as well as specific modules and guidelines for EU stakeholders. The training plan serves a dual purpose:

1. **Training and education for local actors** to facilitate the adoption of circular economy practices at the regional level.
2. **Transferability and lessons learnt** from the A2C project, offering guidelines and recommendations for stakeholders at the EU level.

Below is a brief description of the materials for each of the target groups, as well as how they complement each other:

4.1. Primary Education

The materials developed for primary education provide teachers with interactive resources to introduce circular economy concepts in the classroom through role-playing activities and educational games. Each material is designed to engage students in hands-on learning experiences that encourage critical thinking about sustainability.

The **role-play activities (PE1, PE2, PE3, and PE4)** immerse students in real-world scenarios where they take on different roles to explore key aspects of the circular economy. **"The Sustainable Farm" and "The School Garden" (PE1)** introduce students to organic farming and waste management by encouraging them to transform a farm into a sustainable one. Similarly, **"The Park Clean-up Team" (PE2)** focuses on plastic waste reduction and proper waste separation. **"The Repair Shop" (PE3)** highlights the importance of reuse and repair, while the **Waste Sorting Game (PE4)** teaches students about proper waste disposal and its role in circularity.

To reinforce these concepts, the **Crossword Puzzle (PE5)** familiarises students with essential circular economy terminology, helping them consolidate their understanding in a playful yet educational way. Together, these materials provide a complementary set of tools for educators to make circular economy principles accessible and engaging for young learners.

4.2. Secondary Education

The materials developed for secondary education offer a structured and engaging approach to understanding circular economy principles through case studies, debates, and hands-on activities. They encourage students to think critically about sustainability challenges and explore real-world applications of circular business models.

The **Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM) materials (SE1, SE2, SE5)** form a progressive learning pathway. **SE1 (Case Study Analysis)** introduces students to existing business models, helping them understand their structure and benefits. This knowledge is then applied in **SE2 (Brainstorming New Business Models)**, where students identify local sustainability issues and design potential circular solutions. Finally, **SE5 (Creating a Prototype Business)** builds on these activities by challenging students to develop a full business plan for a circular initiative, linking their ideas to the A2C model.

The **materials on plastics and the agri-food sector (SE3, SE6)** provide insights into key circular economy challenges. **SE3 (From Plastics to Bioplastics)** educates students on the transition from conventional plastics to sustainable alternatives, including a practical exercise where they propose material substitutions. **SE6 (Circular Food and Packaging Design)** deepens this understanding by requiring students to role-play as entrepreneurs developing circular food products and packaging, considering materials, waste management, and cost-benefit analysis.

For a broader perspective, students engage in **debates and scenario-based activities (SE4, SE7, SE8)**. **SE4 (Debate on Circular vs. Linear Economy)** fosters discussion on the pros and cons of circular models. **SE7 (Designing a Circular Strategy)** and **SE8 (Exploring Circular Technologies)** immerse students in applied circular economy thinking, with secondary students focusing on recycling, repair, and reuse, while bachelor-level students delve into advanced recycling methods and biotechnologies.

Lastly, **SE9 (Careers in the Circular Economy)** introduces students to professional opportunities in the sector, highlighting the importance of sustainability-focused careers and entrepreneurship.

4.3. Higher Education

The higher education materials provide advanced, discipline-specific resources to support students in gaining a deeper understanding of circular economy principles and their application across different sectors. These materials combine theoretical coursework with practical case studies, ensuring that students acquire both analytical skills and hands-on experience.

The **Circular Economy Business Models (HE1)** module introduces students to successful circular business models through case study analysis, helping them assess how businesses implement circular principles in practice. This is complemented by **HE2 (Financial Mechanism Assessment)**, which examines public and private funding opportunities that support circular economy initiatives, providing a financial perspective to business model implementation.

For students in technical, engineering and environmental disciplines, **HE3 (Technological Solutions for Circularity in Agri-food)** presents real-world examples of how companies integrate technological innovations to adopt circular practices. It also highlights contributions from related sectors, such as recyclers, biotech firms, and the cosmetics industry, reinforcing the cross-sectoral nature of circular solutions.

The governance aspect is covered in **HE4 (Circular Economy Governance at European, National, and Regional Levels)**, which offers coursework on public policy evaluation and best practices in governance to promote circularity. This material is particularly relevant for students in law, political science, and environmental studies, equipping them with the tools to critically assess policy frameworks.

Students interested in environmental impact assessment (environmental sciences) will benefit from **HE5 (Natural Capital Accounting & Life Cycle Assessment)**, which explores the application of LCA methodologies—including social LCA—and natural capital accounting to evaluate the sustainability of specific industries and processes.

Finally, **HE6 (A2C DIS Tool Training Modules)** provides materials tailored to computer science students and informatics, introducing them to digital tools that support circular economy strategies, along with case studies showcasing their practical application.

The comprehensive list of guidelines and training materials begins on the following page, (See table 1) while the corresponding materials for each item are provided in the annexes of this deliverable.

4.4. Industry/Businesses

The training materials designed for industry and businesses form a complementary set of resources aimed at supporting the transition towards circular economy practices within the agri-food sector. The materials cover various aspects, from business models and regulatory frameworks to funding opportunities and industrial symbiosis, ensuring that businesses have access to both strategic guidance and practical tools.

The guidelines on **Circular Economy Business Models (IB1)** provide an overview of regional success stories, illustrating how businesses can integrate circularity into their operations. This resource is closely linked to the **Industry Mentoring Programme (IB12)**, as it offers a foundation of case studies and practical insights that can be further explored through mentorship. Similarly, the **Directory of Good Circular Economy Practices in the Agri-food Sector (IB11)** serves as a key reference, offering concrete examples that can inform the mentoring activities under IB12.

For businesses looking to assess and improve their circularity, the **Guidelines for Value Chain Analysis (IB2)** support the identification of circularity gaps within existing business models. These guidelines complement the **Industrial Symbiosis resource (IB3)**, which provides case studies demonstrating how businesses can collaborate to optimise resource use. In parallel, the guidelines on **Creating Value from Waste in Agro-industry (IB4)** focus on real-world implementations and barriers encountered, helping businesses understand the practical challenges of adopting circular approaches.

To address regulatory aspects, the Infosheets on **Circular Economy Regulation at EU Level (IB6)** and **National Level (IB7)** offer clear, practical information on compliance requirements and opportunities, including the role of regional by-product pools and the 'end-of-waste' status. These materials ensure that businesses have a solid understanding of the legal framework governing circular economy initiatives.

Access to funding is another key enabler for businesses, and the **Infosheet on Funding Opportunities (IB5)** provides summaries of relevant schemes, tax incentives, and

additional financial resources that can support the implementation of circular economy strategies.

Additionally, the A2C **DIS tool documentation (IB8)** summarises the functionality of the tool and provides basic instructions for use, facilitating its integration into business operations. **Standardisation guidelines (IB9)** coming from the A2C project further complement these resources by offering sector-specific guidance for the agri-food industry, helping businesses align with best practices.

Finally, the document on **Public Awareness (IB10)** is designed to engage management-level decision-makers, emphasising the importance of integrating circular economy principles into business processes. By fostering awareness at the leadership level, this material supports the broader uptake of the practices outlined in the other resources.

4.5. Public Sector

The materials developed for the public sector focus on two key areas: circular public procurement and public engagement. The **Guidelines on Circular Public Procurement (PS1)** provide a consolidated report with best practices, offering public administrations practical insights into integrating circularity into procurement processes. This resource is complemented by the **Guidelines for Fostering Public Engagement in Circular Economy (PS2)**, which support local authorities in engaging citizens and stakeholders in circular initiatives. Together, these materials help public sector actors implement circular economy principles both through procurement strategies and by fostering active participation from society.

ID	TARGET	TOPIC	Material - brief description
PE1	Primary education	Agri-food, plastics, circular economy	Guidelines and materials for Role-play "the sustainable farm" or "the school garden": students take on the role of farmers who want to turn their farm into a sustainable farm and learn about the importance of organic farming and waste management.
PE2	Primary education	Agri-food, plastics, circular economy	Guidelines and materials for Role-play "the park clean-up team": students can take on the role of members of a clean-up team who want to reduce the amount of plastics in a park and learn about the importance of waste management and separation of materials.
PE3	Primary education	Agri-food, plastics, circular economy	Guidelines and materials for Role-play "the repair shop": students can take on the role of workers in a repair shop and learn about the importance of reusing and repairing objects.
PE4	Primary education	General considerations on Circular Economy and its context	Guidelines and materials for Role-play: waste sorting game. In this game, students have to sort different types of waste into the corresponding bins in order to understand the importance of waste separation and how it contributes to the circular economy.

PE5	Primary education	General considerations on Circular Economy and its context	Crossword puzzle with terms related to the circular economy, sustainability and the ecological transition, such as "recycling", "reuse", "renewable energy", "pollution", etc.
SE1	Secondary Education	Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM)	Practical activity: case study of a company. Students analyse how the company's business model works, what its benefits are and how it differs from other business models. Connected with SE2 & SE3.
SE2	Secondary Education	Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM)	Brainstorming new business models: students work in groups to identify sustainability issues in their community and then come up with ideas for new business models that can address these issues using circular economy principles. Connected with S1 and S3.
SE3	Secondary Education	Agri-food, plastics, circular economy	Slide presentation "from plastics to bioplastics". Students learn about the importance of reducing the use of plastics and the transition to more sustainable materials such as bioplastics. Clear differences between biodegradable and bio-based plastics, the benefits of both and case studies where the benefits of biodegradable plastics and other biodegradable materials as substitutes for standard plastics become clear. + Practical exercise: ask students to propose solutions where it is

			beneficial to replace plastics with alternative materials (including bioplastics) evaluating pros and cons.
SE4	Secondary Education	General considerations on Circular Economy and its context	Debate: Students research and discuss the advantages and disadvantages of the circular economy compared to the linear economy. They may be asked to consider different aspects such as resource efficiency, waste reduction and job creation.
SE5	Secondary Education/Bachelor	Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM)	Creating a prototype business: Students work in teams to develop a prototype business using circular economy principles. This activity would involve the creation of a business plan for a food waste collection and recycling company, linking it to the A2C model. Connected with S1 & S2.
SE6	Secondary Education/Bachelor	Agri-food, plastics, circular economy	Students pretend to be a company or entrepreneurs who, in addition to wanting to produce sustainable and circular packaging, seek to produce circular ingredients or food by making use of food waste. They will have to investigate different materials, technologies and methods of collection and recycling. They will also have to analyse costs and benefits related to the production of these foods and ingredients. They will be challenged to make decisions about which materials to use for packaging design, which foods to design from discards, how to optimise the collection and recycling of waste and by-products, and how to implement strategies to minimise waste throughout the production process.

SE7	Secondary Education/Bachelor	General considerations on Circular Economy and its context	Practical activity/work: a hypothetical scenario is presented in which students have to design a circular economy strategy for a company, city or region. Through the scenario, students can understand how the circular economy relates in practice to sustainability and the ecological transition.
SE8	Secondary Education/Bachelor	General considerations on Circular Economy and its context	Practical work/activity: Students will explore various circular practices and technologies. Secondary students will focus on recycling, repair, and reuse. Bachelor students will study mechanical, chemical, and enzymatic recycling, bioremediation biotechnology, and producing high-value products from waste (bioplastics, biodiesel, biofertilisers).
SE9	Secondary Education/Bachelor	Careers and professions related to the circular economy	Slideshow on careers and professions related to the circular economy and the importance of environmentally sensitive entrepreneurship.
HE1	Higher Education	Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM)	Courses or study modules (downloadable written material) including case study analysis of successful companies. Investigation and analysis of an existing circular business model, with emphasis on how the principles of the circular economy are implemented in practice.

HE2	Higher Education	Financial mechanism assessment (public and private funding opportunities) for the circular economy	Courses or study modules (downloadable written material)
HE3	Higher Education	Technological solutions for the introduction of the circular economy in the agri-food business/industry.	Case study on how a company has implemented technological solutions to adopt circular economy principles in the agri-food sector. Inclusion of related sectors that provide solutions to waste in the sector without being specifically companies in the sector (recyclers, biotechnology companies, cosmetics sector, etc.): dedicated to business degrees, industrial and chemical engineering, chemistry, biotechnology.
HE4	Higher Education	Circular economy governance at European, national and regional level.	Practical work/activity: Coursework and written modules on governance (including evaluation of the effectiveness of public policies) and legislation + Practical activity: Research on best practices in governance to promote the circular economy. Dedicated to legal/political science degrees, adapted to Environmental Science.
HE5	Higher Education	Natural Capital Accounting & Life Cycle Assessment	Research on the application of Life Cycle Assessment (including Social) and natural capital accounting in a specific industry/process and how this contributes to the circular economy.

HE6	Higher Education	DIS tool	Training modules for computer science degree
IB1	Industry/Business	Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM)	Guidelines including regional success stories
IB2	Industry/Business	Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM)	Guidelines for session: value chain analysis for the identification of circularity gaps in business models.
IB3	Industry/Business	Industrial symbiosis	Guidelines with case studies in the agri-food industry
IB4	Industry/Business	Creating value from waste in agro-industry	Guidelines with emphasis on case studies implemented and barriers encountered
IB5	Industry/Business	Funding Opportunities	Infosheet with summaries of funding schemes, including tax breaks and exemptions, and access to additional resources
IB6	Industry/Business	Circular Economy regulation at EU level	Infosheets with practical information on how it affects businesses

IB7	Industry/Business	Circular Economy regulation at national level	Infosheets with practical information on how it affects businesses. Including Regional by-product pool. End of waste status.
IB8	Industry/Business	DIS tool	Downloadable written documents summarising the functionality of the DIS and providing basic instructions for use
IB9	Industry/Business	Standardisation	Guidelines for agri-food industry
IB10	Industry/Business	Public awareness	Document to promote public awareness (specifically at management level) of the need for the introduction of the Circular Economy in business processes.
IB11	Industry/Business	Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM)	Directory of good CE practices in the Agri-food sector
IB12	Industry/Business	Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM)	Industry Mentoring Programme
PS1	Public Sector	Circular Public Procurement	Guidelines and consolidated report with best practices

PS2	Public Sector	Public Engagement	Guidelines for fostering public engagement in Circular Economy
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Table 1 - Final list of Guidelines and training materials

5. ANNEX I - Training Plan for local actors: Primary education

5.1. PE1: "The Sustainable Farm" or "The School Garden"

5.1.1. Introduction

Objective of the Material

This educational activity aims to introduce children to the concept of organic farming, sustainable waste management, and circular economy principles through an engaging role-play exercise. By taking on different roles within a farming community, students will learn about the environmental impact of agricultural practices and explore solutions for reducing waste and promoting sustainability.

Target Audience

This material is designed for primary school teachers who wish to implement an interactive learning experience on sustainability. It provides a structured role-play activity that allows students to actively participate in discussions on organic farming, waste reduction, and responsible consumption.

Contribution to the Circular Economy in the Agri-Food Sector

The agri-food sector generates a significant amount of waste, much of which can be repurposed or reduced through sustainable farming techniques. This activity will help students understand that waste is not necessarily rubbish but can be transformed into valuable resources. By composting organic waste, minimising chemical inputs, and promoting biodiversity, students will grasp how circular economy principles contribute to more sustainable food production.

5.1.2. Activity Overview

In this interactive role-play, students will become farmers, environmental advocates, or consumers, working together to turn their farm into a sustainable, circular farm. The activity includes setting up a small garden in the school, where children will observe the benefits of composting and organic farming practices.

Resources and Materials Needed (Before Implementation)

To successfully carry out this activity, the following materials and support are required:

Materials:

- ✓ Pots or raised garden beds (e.g. reused wooden boxes)
- ✓ Soil for planting
- ✓ Fast-growing vegetable seeds (lettuce, radishes, spinach)
- ✓ Organic waste (fruit peels, vegetable scraps, dry leaves, eggshells)
- ✓ Compost bin or a designated composting area
- ✓ Mini gardening tools (small shovels, watering cans)
- ✓ Plant labels or tags
- ✓ Garden journals for students

Time Requirements:

- ⌚ *Initial preparation and planting:* 1–2 school sessions (60–90 minutes each)
- ⌚ *Weekly care and monitoring:* 30–45 minutes per week
- ⌚ *Composting process:* At least 3 months to obtain mature compost

Personnel Required:

- 👤 At least one teacher to moderate the role-play and guide students
- 🌱 Support from staff or volunteers familiar with composting (e.g. maintaining appropriate humidity and temperature in the composting area)
- 🧑 Optional: Involvement of school gardening experts or parent volunteers for support during planting and composting phases

Roles for the Activity

Each student will take on a specific role, helping them understand different perspectives on sustainable farming:

- **Organic Farmers** – Focus on growing crops without chemicals, using natural compost and eco-friendly methods.
- **Nature Friends** – Support the farmers by researching or implementing sustainable practices, such as water conservation, composting, and biodiversity promotion.
- **Neighbours and Buyers** – Represent consumers who prefer environmentally friendly food and discuss how farming methods affect the environment.

- **Traditional Farmers** – Play a contrasting role, advocating for conventional farming methods and questioning the need for change.
- **Moderator (Teacher)** – Facilitates the discussion, ensuring each role contributes effectively and guiding students in reflecting on sustainability challenges.

The role-play will take place in a small school garden, allowing students to put their ideas into practice and share their observations.

Steps for Implementing the Activity

1. Introduction to Organic Farming

Introduce the concept of sustainable agriculture and explain that the students will create an organic garden using natural methods.

Discuss organic waste and its role in agriculture (e.g. fruit peels, vegetable scraps, eggshells, and dry leaves).

Explain how composting organic waste provides essential nutrients to plants instead of sending waste to landfill.

2. Planting and Preparing the Garden

Soil Preparation: Students will fill pots or garden beds with nutrient-rich soil.

Seed Planting: Each child will plant fast-growing vegetable seeds (e.g. lettuce, radishes, spinach) and label them.

Watering: Students will learn about water conservation techniques and the importance of responsible irrigation.

3. Making Compost with Organic Waste

Collecting Waste: Demonstrate the types of organic waste that can be composted.

Composting Process: Use a compost bin or a designated area where students can mix their organic waste and learn how it decomposes.

4. Caring for the Garden and Observing Growth

Weekly Care: Students will check the plants, remove dry leaves, and monitor soil health.

Applying Compost: When ready, compost will be used to enrich the soil, showing its benefits in improving plant health.

5. Reflection and Evaluation

Observing Growth: Students will keep a garden journal to document how plants grow with compost.

Discussion on the Waste Cycle: The teacher will lead a reflection on how organic waste is repurposed into nutrients, reinforcing the circular economy concept.

Group Reflection Questions:

- What did we learn about organic waste?
- Why is compost better for the environment than chemical fertilisers?
- How can we apply these ideas at home?

Key Learning Outcomes

This activity will help students:

- ✓ Understand waste management (reduce, reuse, and recycle in agriculture).
- ✓ Recognise the impact of farming on the environment (water use, pollution, biodiversity).
- ✓ Learn how to create compost and use it as a natural fertiliser.
- ✓ Develop teamwork and problem-solving skills while role-playing different perspectives on farming.

Materials Needed

- ✓ Pots or raised garden beds (reused wooden boxes can be an option).
- ✓ Soil for planting.
- ✓ Fast-growing vegetable seeds (lettuce, radishes, spinach).
- ✓ Organic waste (fruit peels, coffee grounds, dry leaves).
- ✓ Mini gardening tools (small shovels and watering cans).
- ✓ Plant labels or tags.

5.1.3. Further Resources

For more information and additional materials on organic farming, waste management, and circular economy practices, refer to the following [link](#).

5.2. PE2: The Park Clean-Up Team

5.2.1. Introduction

Objective of the Material

This role-play activity introduces children to the importance of waste management, recycling, and environmental conservation. By assuming different roles, students will explore the challenges of plastic waste in public spaces and develop strategies to promote sustainable behaviours.

Target Audience

This material is intended for primary school teachers who want to engage students in an interactive and educational experience about plastic waste, recycling, and responsible public behaviour.

Contribution to the Circular Economy in the Agri-Food Sector

Plastics are widely used in the agri-food industry, from packaging to disposable utensils. However, improper disposal leads to pollution in parks, rivers, and oceans. This activity encourages students to conduct a **litter inventory** by collecting and categorising waste found in a nearby area (e.g., schoolyard or park). Students will count and record the number of tobacco butts, plastic bags, food wrappers, bottles, and other common items, helping them **identify the most abundant types of litter** and reflect on their sources (e.g., school snacks, on-the-go consumption, lack of recycling habits).

Once inventoried, the group will discuss:

- Why certain waste types are more common
- What consumption habits lead to this waste
- Which **9R strategies** (Refuse, Reduce, Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Repurpose, Recycle, Recover) could apply to prevent or manage each litter type

By linking each waste item to possible actions under the **9Rs framework**, students will understand how **small daily choices**—like refusing single-use plastics, reusing containers, or recycling properly—can contribute to a **circular economy** where waste is minimised, and resources are used more responsibly.

5.2.2. Activity Overview

In this role-play scenario, students will take on the role of a clean-up team and park visitors to explore different attitudes towards waste management. They will develop waste reduction strategies, discuss recycling incentives, and debate the impact of plastic pollution.

Materials Needed

- ✓ Simulated Recycling Bins – Boxes or containers labelled for plastic, paper, organic, and glass waste.
- ✓ Simulated Waste – Paper cut-outs or recycled materials representing plastic wrappers, bottles, and food scraps.
- ✓ Informational Posters – Materials for students to design awareness campaigns on waste separation.
- ✓ Role Cards – Cards assigning students their specific roles (Cleaning Team, Park Visitors, Waste Managers).
- ✓ Research Materials – Basic resources on waste management, plastic pollution, and recycling.
- ✓ Gloves and Simulated Trash Bags – For a more realistic clean-up experience, using recycled or reusable materials.

Roles for the Activity

Each student will take on a specific role, allowing them to experience different perspectives on environmental responsibility:

Cleaning Team – Responsible for assessing pollution levels, collecting waste, and promoting recycling practices.

Waste Managers – Ensure that all waste is sorted and recycled correctly, explaining the importance of proper waste separation.

Park Visitors – Some will support recycling, while others will resist change, highlighting real-world environmental challenges.

Moderator (Teacher) – Facilitates discussions, ensures fair participation, and guides students in problem-solving.

The role-play setting should resemble a park environment, such as the school yard itself, with recycling bins, litter, and diverse attitudes towards waste disposal.

Key Themes Explored

The role-play will focus on several environmental issues, encouraging students to think critically and propose solutions:

1. Plastic Waste Management

Understanding the long-term impact of plastic pollution on ecosystems.

Learning about the reduce, reuse, and recycle principles to minimise waste.

2. Waste Separation

The clean-up team will establish a colour-coded waste separation system to sort plastics, organic waste, paper, and glass.

Emphasis on the importance of correct bin usage and recycling efficiency.

3. Environmental Education

Finding effective ways to raise awareness among park visitors.

Designing posters, flyers, or simple information boards to educate the public.

4. Alternatives to Plastic

Identifying sustainable alternatives (e.g. reusable bottles, eco-friendly packaging).

Encouraging better choices in public spaces to reduce single-use plastics.

5. Freedom vs Responsibility in Recycling

Some visitors will argue that recycling requires too much effort and reduces personal freedom.

The cleaning team must present persuasive arguments for collective responsibility and the long-term benefits of a cleaner environment.

6. Economic and Environmental Costs of Recycling

Students will discuss the challenges and benefits of recycling, including:

- The economic costs of setting up recycling systems.
- The environmental benefits of waste reduction.

Steps for Implementing the Activity

1. Introduction to the Problem

- The teacher explains the issue of plastic waste in public spaces and how parks often suffer from pollution.
- Students are divided into their assigned roles.

2. Waste Assessment and Clean-Up Plan

- The cleaning team evaluates the park's litter problem and proposes a waste reduction strategy.
- Park visitors (some supportive, some resistant) react to the new policies.
- The waste managers help ensure proper recycling is implemented.

3. Simulating Different Attitudes

- Some park visitors will be environmentally conscious, encouraging others to recycle.
- Others will question recycling efforts, arguing against the inconvenience or economic costs.
- The cleaning team must educate, convince, and respond to concerns.

4. Developing a Park Clean-Up Strategy

After engaging with the park visitors, the clean-up team will:

- Identify problems encountered in implementing waste separation.
- Suggest improvements (e.g. clearer signage, better bin placement).
- Design an awareness campaign with incentives for recycling.

5. Reflection and Evaluation

Groups will discuss:

- Which arguments were the most convincing?
- What changes could make recycling easier and more effective?
- How can we apply these lessons at home and in the community?

Key Learning Outcomes

By participating in this activity, students will:

- ✓ Understand the importance of waste reduction and recycling.
- ✓ Learn about the impact of plastic pollution on the environment.
- ✓ Develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills when addressing real-world challenges.

- ✓ Explore ways to encourage recycling in public spaces.
- ✓ Experience different perspectives on waste management and responsibility.

5.3. PE3: The Repair Shop

5.3.1. Introduction

Objective of the Material

This activity introduces children to the culture of repair and reuse, helping them understand that not all broken or damaged objects need to be discarded. By assuming different roles in a repair shop, students will learn about practical repair techniques and how small actions can contribute to a circular economy.

Target Audience

This material is designed for primary school teachers who want to engage students in a hands-on learning experience about repair, reuse, and waste reduction.

Contribution to the Circular Economy in the Agri-Food Sector

Plastic crates and containers are widely used in the agri-food industry for transporting and storing fruits, vegetables, and other products. Unfortunately, these items are often discarded after minimal use, contributing to unnecessary waste. This activity encourages repairing and reusing these objects instead of throwing them away, promoting a more sustainable and resource-efficient approach.

5.3.2. Activity Overview

In this role-play scenario, students will work in a repair shop, assessing and fixing damaged plastic crates commonly used in agriculture and food storage. Through inspection, repair, and labelling, they will learn the importance of prolonging the lifespan of objects rather than disposing of them.

Roles for the Activity

Each student will be assigned a specific role in the repair process, promoting teamwork and problem-solving skills:

Inspection Station – Students check plastic crates for damage (cracks, broken corners) and decide what kind of repair is needed.

Repair Station – Students apply patches, tape, or glue to fix the damaged crates.

Cleaning and Marking Station – Once repaired, the crates are cleaned and labelled as “Repaired” with the type of repair completed.

Moderator (Teacher) – Guides the students through the process and resolves any questions.

The setting should resemble a repair workshop, with designated areas for inspection, repair, and labelling.

Key Themes Explored

This activity encourages critical thinking and hands-on learning while introducing students to key environmental topics:

1. Reuse vs Waste

- Understanding the negative impact of the “throwaway culture”.
- Learning that repairing objects saves money, reduces waste, and protects the environment.

2. Technical Skills

- Introduction to basic repair tools and techniques.
- Understanding how small repairs can extend the life of objects.

3. Circular Economy

- Repair and reuse are essential strategies in a circular economy.
- Learning how repairing materials reduces the need for new resources.

4. Responsible Consumption

- Encouraging students to think twice before discarding objects.
- Discussing how small actions at home and school can help reduce waste.

Steps for Implementing the Activity

1. Introduction to the Repair Workshop

The teacher introduces the idea that students will work in a repair shop, fixing plastic crates used in the agri-food sector.

Discussion about why repair is important: "Every crate we repair is one less crate that ends up in the rubbish."; "Repairing saves resources and reduces waste."

2. Repair Process

Inspection Station – Students examine each crate for cracks or broken parts and decide on the best repair method.

Repair Station – Students use repair tape, mesh patches, or glue to fix the damaged crates.

Cleaning and Marking Station – The repaired crates are cleaned and labelled as "Ready to Use."

3. Role Rotation

After a set amount of time, students rotate roles to experience all aspects of the repair process.

4. Reflection and Discussion

At the end of the activity, the teacher leads a group discussion, asking:

- "Why is repairing crates better than throwing them away?"
- "How can we apply this at home or school?"
- "What other objects can we repair instead of discarding?"

Key Learning Outcomes

By participating in this role-play, students will:

- ✓ Understand the importance of repair and reuse.
- ✓ Develop basic technical skills for fixing objects.
- ✓ Learn how small repairs contribute to waste reduction.
- ✓ Gain awareness of the circular economy and sustainable consumption.
- ✓ Improve teamwork, creativity, and problem-solving skills.

Materials Needed

- ✓ Mini plastic crates or used containers – Small fruit containers or recycled plastic items.
- ✓ Strong repair tape – Duct tape or strong adhesive tape for simulating repairs.
- ✓ Eco-friendly glue for plastics – Safe for children and easy to use.
- ✓ Plastic mesh patches – Pieces of mesh or stronger plastic to reinforce broken areas.

- ✓ Markers or labels – To tag repaired crates with their fix description.
- ✓ Small work gloves – Optional, to help students feel like real repair workers.
- ✓ Work area with basic tools – Safety scissors, rags, and cleaning materials.

5.4. PE4: Waste sorting game

5.4.1. Introduction

Objective of the Material

This activity introduces students to waste separation and recycling, helping them understand the role of proper waste management in the circular economy. By engaging in a waste sorting role-play, children will experience first-hand the challenges and benefits of separating waste correctly.

Target Audience

This material is designed for primary school teachers who want to implement an engaging, interactive learning experience that promotes environmental awareness and responsible waste disposal.

Contribution to the Circular Economy in the agrifood sector

Proper waste sorting is essential for recycling and resource recovery. When waste is separated correctly, materials such as paper, plastic, glass, and organic waste can be processed and reused rather than being sent to landfills. Teaching children these principles at an early age reinforces sustainable habits that contribute to a more resource-efficient future.

5.4.2. Activity Overview

In this role-play scenario, students will take on the roles of waste collectors, sorters, environmental supervisors, and transporters, working together to clean up a simulated public park. They will learn to categorise waste, discuss challenges in recycling, and reflect on how waste management contributes to sustainability.

Roles for the Activity

Students are divided into four groups, each with specific responsibilities:

Collectors – Gather waste from different areas of the simulated classroom or playground and bring it to the recycling area.

Sorters – Separate waste into its respective categories and place it in the correct container.

Environmental Supervisors – Monitor whether the waste is sorted correctly and assist sorters in resolving any doubts or issues.

Transporters – Carry the filled containers to the “recycling centre”, a designated area where all collected materials are deposited.

To ensure all students experience different aspects of the recycling process, roles can rotate throughout the activity.

Key Themes Explored

This activity introduces students to essential waste management principles while developing their critical thinking and teamwork skills.

1. Waste Separation and Recycling

Understanding the importance of sorting waste for recycling.

Recognising how different materials (paper, plastic, glass, organic) should be disposed of correctly.

2. Sustainability and the Circular Economy

Learning how recycling conserves resources and reduces landfill waste.

Understanding how waste can be transformed into new materials in a circular economic system.

3. Critical Thinking and Debate

Students will discuss and evaluate arguments for and against waste sorting, learning to justify their opinions.

Developing the ability to weigh up environmental and economic factors in waste management decisions.

4. Teamwork and Problem-Solving

Working together to ensure efficient waste sorting.

Encouraging collaboration between different roles to achieve a common goal.

Steps for Implementing the Activity

1. Introduction to the Circular Economy and Waste Sorting

The teacher introduces the concept of the circular economy, explaining how proper waste separation contributes to sustainability.

Discussion on why recycling is important:

"What happens to rubbish if it is not recycled?"

"How can sorting waste help the environment?"

"What types of materials can be recycled?"

2. Waste Sorting Role-Play

The teacher sets up a public park simulation, scattering various types of waste around the area.

Students assigned to the Collectors group retrieve waste and bring it to the sorting area.

The Sorters group separates the waste into the correct bins.

The Environmental Supervisors assess whether waste is being sorted correctly and help correct mistakes.

The Transporters move the filled containers to the "recycling centre".

3. Discussion and Debate

After the role-play, students engage in a structured discussion reflecting on:

- The challenges faced in sorting waste.
- The consequences of improper waste management.
- The importance of individual responsibility in reducing waste and recycling correctly.
- Critics' Perspectives: Some students will take on the role of waste sorting critics, presenting arguments against recycling, such as effort, cost, or lack of immediate benefits. Other students will counter these arguments, developing their debate and reasoning skills.

4. Reflection and Key Takeaways

The activity concludes with a group reflection on what students learned: "Why is recycling important?"; "What would happen if no one sorted waste?"; "What can we do at home and school to improve recycling?"

Key Learning Outcomes

By participating in this role-play, students will:

- ✓ Understand the importance of waste sorting and recycling.
- ✓ Develop critical thinking and debating skills by discussing waste management.

- ✓ Learn to make informed decisions about sustainable waste disposal.
- ✓ Gain teamwork experience, working together towards a common environmental goal.
- ✓ Improve their awareness of circular economy principles.

Materials Needed

- ✓ Simulated Recycling Bins – Containers in different colours for waste separation:
 - Green – Glass.
 - Yellow – Plastics and packaging.
 - Blue – Paper and cardboard.
 - Brown – Organic waste.
 - Grey – Non-recyclable waste.
- ✓ Special Collection Points – Designated spots for batteries, electronics, and hazardous waste.
- ✓ Simulated or Clean Waste – Objects for sorting, such as:
 - Paper, plastic bottles, glass jars, cardboard.
 - Simulated food scraps (e.g., cut-out images or biodegradable materials).
 - Batteries, old light bulbs, and broken electronic devices for special collection bins.
- ✓ Informational Cards – Visual guides with images and descriptions of different types of waste.
- ✓ Critics' Cards – Argument cards for students taking on the role of waste sorting sceptics.
- ✓ Role Markers – Vests or tags identifying Collectors, Sorters, Environmental Supervisors, and Transporters.

5.5. PE5: Online Crossword puzzles

5.5.1. Introduction

Objective of the Material

This activity introduces students to key circular economy and sustainability concepts through an interactive crossword puzzle. By solving the crossword, children will become familiar with fundamental terms related to waste management, renewable energy, pollution reduction, and sustainable practices.

Target Audience

This material is designed for primary school teachers who wish to engage students in a fun, educational activity that reinforces environmental awareness and sustainability principles.

Contribution to the Circular Economy in the agrifood sector

Understanding circular economy vocabulary is an essential first step in promoting sustainable habits. By recognising key terms such as recycling, reuse, pollution, and renewable energy, students develop an early appreciation of how their actions impact the environment and how resources can be used more efficiently.

5.5.2. Activity Overview

This crossword puzzle will help children learn and consolidate their knowledge of key environmental and sustainability terms. The game serves as an engaging way to introduce students to fundamental circular economy concepts while improving their vocabulary and problem-solving skills.

Key Learning Objectives

- ✓ Introduce essential vocabulary related to circular economy, sustainability, and ecological transition.
- ✓ Enhance critical thinking skills by linking definitions to relevant concepts.
- ✓ Reinforce the importance of sustainability through a playful and interactive format.

✓ Promote engagement and teamwork, as students can work individually or in pairs/groups to complete the crossword.

Crossword Details

The crossword contains terms and concepts related to:

- Waste Management: Recycling, reuse, composting, waste reduction.
- Sustainability Principles: Responsible consumption, renewable energy, biodiversity.
- Environmental Protection: Pollution, carbon footprint, conservation.
- Circular Economy Practices: Upcycling, eco-design, green innovation.

Teachers can integrate the crossword puzzle into their lessons by:

- Introducing each term through a brief class discussion.
- Providing real-life examples of how these concepts apply to everyday situations.
- Encouraging group collaboration to solve the crossword.
- Discussing answers together to reinforce learning.

Crossword Puzzle Links

The crossword is available in both English and Spanish, allowing for bilingual learning opportunities:

Crossword #1:

📌 English Version: <https://crosswordlabs.com/view/training-plan-for-local-actors>

📌 Spanish Version: <https://crosswordlabs.com/view/training-plan-for-local-actors>

Crossword #2:

📌 English version: <https://crosswordlabs.com/view/2024-11-06-206>

📌 Spanish version: <https://crosswordlabs.com/view/2024-11-06-206>

Reflection and Discussion

After completing the crossword, students can participate in a group discussion to reinforce key takeaways: "Which terms were new to you?"; "Why is it important to know these

words?"; "How can we apply these concepts at home and at school?"; "What actions can we take to reduce waste and protect the environment?"

Additional Teaching Suggestions

- Use the crossword as a warm-up activity before introducing a lesson on sustainability.
- Create a competition where students try to complete the crossword in teams.
- Encourage students to illustrate one of the concepts from the crossword as a class poster.

6. ANNEX II - Training Plan for local actors: secondary education/bachelor

6.1. SE1: Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM) – Practical Case Study Analysis

6.1.1. Introduction and Learning Objectives

This training material is designed for **secondary education teachers** to facilitate a **practical learning activity** on **circular economy business models (CEBM)**. The objective is to enable students to analyse and compare business models that incorporate circular economy principles with traditional linear models.

Through this activity, students will:

- Understand the fundamentals of circular economy in business.
- Identify the key components of a circular economy business model.
- Assess the advantages and challenges of circular economy initiatives.
- Develop critical thinking skills by comparing real or fictional case studies.

This activity encourages active learning by engaging students in case study analysis, allowing them to explore how businesses integrate sustainable practices while remaining economically viable.

6.1.2. Background: Circular Economy and Business Models

In traditional linear business models, companies operate on a take-make-dispose basis, extracting raw materials, producing goods, and discarding waste at the end of the product's life. However, circular economy business models aim to reduce waste, maximise resource efficiency, and extend product lifecycles through reuse, refurbishment, and recycling.

By studying examples of circular economy business models, students will explore how businesses can be both profitable and environmentally responsible, fostering a more sustainable economic system.

6.1.3. Structure of the Activity

Step 1: Selection of a Company (Real or Fictional)

Students will work individually or in groups to:

- Select a real company implementing circular economy principles. (*See examples in Section 4.2*)

- OR create a fictional company with a circular economy approach. (*See the provided case study template in Section 4. Case Study Template: EcoCycle Solutions.*)

Step 2: Business Model Breakdown

Students should analyse and break down the business model using a structured approach, focusing on the following elements:

- Value Proposition: What problem does the business solve? How does it incorporate circular economy principles?
- Customer Segments: Who are the main customers? Why would they choose this business?
- Distribution Channels: How does the business deliver its products or services to its customers?
- Customer Relationships: How does the business engage with customers and encourage long-term participation?

Students should document their findings in a structured format, either as a written report, a presentation, or a visual representation such as a Business Model Canvas.

Step 3: Comparing Circular and Linear Business Models

Once students have analysed their chosen company, they will:

- Compare it with a traditional linear business model (e.g., fast fashion vs. sustainable fashion).
- Identify key differences, such as:
 - How resources are used (circular vs. extractive).
 - How waste is managed (minimised vs. disposed of).
 - Economic benefits (cost savings, new revenue streams).

Step 4: Presentation & Class Discussion

Each student/group presents their findings, followed by a class discussion guided by the educator. Encourage students to:

- Explain the key benefits of circular business models.
- Discuss the challenges businesses face when shifting to circular practices.
- Debate whether circular economy business models can be implemented in all industries.

Step 5: Reflection and Real-World Application

Educators should facilitate a final reflection where students:

- Discuss what they learned about circular economy business models.
- Consider how they, as consumers, can support circular businesses.
- Brainstorm industries where circular economy principles could be applied further.

6.1.4. Case Study Template: EcoCycle Solutions (Example)

4.1 Introduction

EcoCycle Solutions is a fictitious company specialising in the collection and refurbishment of electronic devices to reduce e-waste. The company applies circular economy principles by extending the lifecycle of electronic components, reducing dependency on raw materials, and minimising environmental impact.

4.2 Business Model Analysis

Value Proposition: EcoCycle Solutions provides a sustainable alternative for electronic device disposal by refurbishing and reselling components. The company helps consumers, businesses, and institutions responsibly manage electronic waste.

Customer Segments:

- Technology companies needing sustainable e-waste solutions.
- Consumers seeking refurbished electronics at lower prices.
- Government agencies and NGOs promoting waste reduction.

Distribution Channels:

- Digital platform for e-waste collection requests.
- Physical and online stores selling refurbished devices.
- Retail partnerships for collection points.

Customer Relationships:

- Loyalty programmes for customers who trade in old electronics.
- Personalised services for businesses with bulk disposal needs.
- Transparency through online tracking of refurbishment and recycling processes.

6.1.5. Activity Instructions for Students

1. **Choose a company** (real or fictional) implementing circular economy principles.
2. **Identify the key components** of its business model:
 - Value proposition
 - Target customers

- Distribution channels
 - Customer relationships
3. **Analyse the advantages** of its circular model in comparison to traditional linear models:
- Economic benefits (cost savings, new revenue streams).
 - Environmental impact (waste reduction, resource efficiency).
 - Competitive advantages (differentiation, compliance with regulations).
4. **Present findings** through a **visual report or group presentation**.

6.1.6. Key Discussion Questions

After completing the activity, students should reflect on the following:

- How does the circular economy model differ from traditional business models?
- What are the main benefits and challenges of adopting a circular economy approach?
- Can circular economy business models be applied to all industries? Why or why not?
- What role do consumers, businesses, and governments play in supporting the transition to a circular economy?

6.1.7. Conclusion

This activity helps students understand the real-world application of circular economy concepts by analysing business models that prioritise sustainability and efficiency. By comparing these models to traditional approaches, students develop a critical perspective on how businesses can contribute to a more sustainable future.

6.1.8. Further Reading & References

[3] A. T. Braun, O. Schöllhammer, and B. Rosenkranz, "Adaptation of the Business Model Canvas Template to Develop Business Models for the Circular Economy," *Procedia CIRP*, 2021.

[4] Ellen MacArthur Foundation, Resources on Circular Economy Business Models. [Online]. Available: <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/resources>

Figure 7 - Business Model Canvas example template

6.2. SE2: Brainstorming new circular business models

6.2.1. Introduction and Learning Objectives

This educational material is designed for **secondary school teachers** to facilitate a hands-on learning activity that encourages students to **develop innovative business models** based on circular economy principles. The activity promotes entrepreneurial thinking, problem-solving, and sustainability awareness, while encouraging students to address real-world sustainability challenges in their communities.

Through this activity, students will:

- Identify sustainability issues in their local environment.
- Apply circular economy principles to create innovative business solutions.
- Develop an entrepreneurial mindset by designing business models that are both sustainable and profitable.
- Collaborate in teams, strengthening communication and critical thinking skills.

This activity is directly connected to **SE1 (Case Study Analysis of Circular Economy Business Models)** and **SE3 (Plastics and Bioplastics in the Circular Economy)**, helping students build a holistic understanding of how business and sustainability intersect.

6.2.2. Background: Circular Economy and Business Innovation

Traditional business models follow a linear structure: **extract resources** → **produce goods** → **consume** → **discard waste**. This approach wastes valuable materials, contributes to pollution, and puts pressure on natural resources.

Circular economy business models aim to close the loop by designing processes that:

- Reduce waste by using fewer raw materials.
- Reuse existing materials through refurbishing or repurposing.
- Recycle waste into valuable products.
- Regenerate ecosystems by integrating sustainable and nature-based solutions.

Through this brainstorming activity, students will develop their own circular business ideas by identifying local sustainability issues and proposing innovative solutions.

6.2.3. Structure of the Activity

Step 1: Identifying a Local Sustainability Issue

Students work in small groups to investigate and choose a real sustainability issue in their local area. The problem could relate to:

- Food waste in school cafeterias or local restaurants.
- Excessive plastic packaging in supermarkets.
- Fast fashion waste from discarded clothes.
- E-waste from old smartphones and laptops.
- Water pollution due to improper waste disposal.

Teachers should guide students in researching their chosen issue by asking:

- What are the most common waste materials in our community?
- How are these materials currently managed or disposed of?
- Could these materials be repurposed, recycled, or used in a different way?

Step 2: Applying Circular Economy Principles

Once the sustainability issue is defined, students brainstorm business solutions using circular economy strategies.

Key questions for idea generation:

- How can we convert waste into a valuable resource?
- Can we redesign an existing product or service to be more sustainable?
- Can we draw inspiration from successful circular economy businesses?

Guiding Circular Economy Principles:

- Reduce: Minimise resource use and waste production.
- Reuse: Find ways to extend product life cycles.
- Recycle: Transform waste into new materials.
- Regenerate: Use sustainable processes to restore ecosystems.

Step 3: Developing a Circular Economy Business Idea

Each group develops a business model for their idea, covering:

- **Problem Statement:** What issue is the business solving?
- **Business Concept:** What product/service does the company offer?
- **Circular Strategies Used:** How does the business apply **reduce, reuse, recycle, or regenerate** principles?
- **Target Customers:** Who will benefit from this business?

- **Revenue Model:** How will the business be financially sustainable?

Example Business Concepts:

1. Agri-Food Sector

- Food Waste Composting: A business that collects food waste from restaurants and turns it into compost for urban gardens.
- Upcycled Food Products: Making snacks from imperfect fruits and vegetables that would otherwise be discarded.

2. Fashion and Textiles

- Clothing Rental Platforms: A subscription service where people rent clothes instead of buying new ones.
- Textile Recycling Hubs: A collection and sorting service that converts used textiles into new fabrics.

3. Technology and E-Waste

- Refurbished Electronics Marketplace: A business that repairs and resells used smartphones and laptops.
- Modular Gadgets: A company that produces phones and computers with interchangeable parts to reduce electronic waste.

4. Sustainable Cities

- Shared Mobility Services: Bicycle or electric scooter sharing with a focus on using recyclable materials.
- Recycled Building Materials: A company that produces construction materials from plastic waste.

Step 4: Presenting the Business Ideas

Each group presents their business model to the class, answering key questions:

- What sustainability issue does this business address?
- How does the business function?
- What impact would this business have on the community?
- How is this business different from a traditional (linear) business model?

Encourage students to use visuals such as slides, posters, or business model canvases to communicate their ideas clearly.

Step 5: Group Discussion and Reflection

After the presentations, the class discusses the proposed ideas:

- Which business models are the most feasible?
- What challenges might arise when implementing them?
- How can these models inspire real-world change?

Encourage students to evaluate the potential impact of their ideas on society and the environment.

6.2.4. Key Takeaways

By the end of the activity, students should be able to:

- Understand how circular business models work.
- Identify real-world sustainability issues.
- Apply circular economy principles to develop solutions.
- Reflect on the challenges and opportunities of transitioning to a circular economy.

This activity fosters creativity, entrepreneurship, and sustainability awareness, equipping students with practical skills to think critically about environmental and business challenges.

6.2.5. Additional Resources for Educators

- **Ellen MacArthur Foundation:** Circular economy education resources – <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org>
- **Circular Economy Club:** Best practices and case studies – <https://www.circulareconomyclub.com>
- **ScienceDirect:** Research articles on circular business models – <https://www.sciencedirect.com>

6.3. SE3: Educational presentations

The following document provides an overview of four educational presentations developed within the Agro2Circular (A2C) project. These materials aim to introduce students to key concepts in circular economy, bioplastics, plastic recycling, and the valorisation of agri-food waste. Although the presentations are designed for the Spanish educational context and are in Spanish, they can serve as inspiration for educators in other regions to create similar materials.

To avoid unnecessary length, the slides accompanying these educational materials have not been included in this document. They are available for consultation on the CORDIS platform at the following link: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036838/results>.

6.3.1. Circular Economy Concept

Overview

This presentation, developed for secondary education students, introduces the concept of circular economy as an alternative to the traditional linear economy. It provides a broad perspective on the environmental challenges posed by resource depletion, landfill saturation, and greenhouse gas emissions.

Key Contents

- **Linear vs Circular Economy:** Explanation of how the traditional 'take-make-dispose' system differs from a circular approach focused on reducing waste, reusing materials, and regenerating natural systems.
- **Principles of Circular Economy:**
 - Waste and pollution elimination
 - Maximising resource use through recycling, reuse, and repair
 - Regenerating natural systems, including sustainable agriculture
- **European Circular Economy Strategy:** A focus on key policy areas such as electronics, textiles, plastics, and food packaging.
- **Agro2Circular Project:** Insights into how circular economy principles apply to the agri-food sector, focusing on fruit, vegetable, and multilayer plastic waste.

Application for Educators

- **Discussion Activity:** Students can compare real-world examples of circular and linear economy models.
- **Practical Exercise:** Students propose circular solutions for common waste problems in their daily lives.

6.3.2. Biotechnology and Bioplastics

Overview

This presentation explores the role of biotechnology in sustainable material production, focusing on the development of bioplastics as an alternative to traditional petroleum-based plastics.

Key Contents

- **Introduction to Biotechnology:** Definition and applications in various sectors, including agriculture and waste management.
- **Understanding Bioplastics:** Classification of bioplastics into:
 - **Bio-based and biodegradable** (e.g., PLA, PHA)
 - **Bio-based but non-biodegradable** (e.g., bio-based PET)
 - **Petroleum-based but biodegradable** (e.g., certain synthetic polymers)
- **The Biodegradability Myth:** Explanation that biodegradable plastics do not always degrade easily in nature and require specific industrial composting conditions.
- **Production of Bioplastics:** The transformation of biomass into monomers and polymers through thermal, chemical, and biological processes.
- **Real-world Applications:** Case studies on bioplastic production using agro-food waste, particularly in the Agro2Circular project.

Application for Educators

- **Case Study Analysis:** Students investigate the advantages and limitations of different bioplastic types.
- **Experimental Activity:** A simple lab-based activity where students compare the degradation process of various plastic materials under controlled conditions.
 - **Suggested procedure:** Prepare small samples of various plastic types (e.g. traditional PET, PLA bioplastic, and a starch-based biodegradable film). Place each sample in separate containers with moist soil or compost, replicating

real-life degradation environments. Ensure equal conditions for all samples (light exposure, humidity, temperature).

- **Materials needed:** Small plastic samples (cut to approx. 3x3 cm), labelled containers, potting soil or compost, water spray bottle, scale (for periodic weighing), gloves.
- **Time required:** Approx. 15–20 minutes setup time. Observations should be recorded weekly over a period of 4–6 weeks.
- **Learning outcome:** Students will observe differences in physical degradation, encouraging critical discussion on the real-world biodegradability of plastics.

6.3.3. Plastic Recycling and Upcycling

Overview

This presentation provides insights into the challenges of plastic recycling, particularly focusing on complex multilayer plastics used in the agri-food industry.

Key Contents

- **Plastic Pollution Problem:** Data on global plastic production and waste accumulation.
- **Recycling Challenges:**
 - Sorting difficulties due to material composition
 - Contamination from food residues and additives
- **Innovative Recycling Solutions:**
 - **Optical sorting** to separate plastics by composition
 - **Delamination techniques** to recover high-value components
 - **Enzymatic treatments** to break down polymers for repurposing
- **The Role of the Agro2Circular Project:** Development of new recycling methods to recover valuable resources from plastic waste.

Application for Educators

- **Waste Analysis Activity:** Students collect different plastic waste samples and classify them based on their recyclability.
- **Recycling Process Simulation:** A role-play exercise where students act as part of a recycling facility, making decisions on sorting and processing materials.

Suggested roles:

- **Sorting Operators:** Identify and separate plastics based on type (e.g. PET, HDPE, multilayer, biodegradable).
- **Contamination Inspectors:** Detect and flag materials contaminated with food residues or non-recyclable components.
- **Process Engineers:** Decide the best recycling or upcycling route (e.g. mechanical recycling, chemical delamination, composting, disposal).
- **Facility Managers:** Oversee decision-making and assess environmental and economic impacts of each route.

Pre-activity preparation: Educators should provide students with a simplified decision-tree or flowchart of plastic waste management routes, including conditions for each path (e.g. “PET with no contamination → mechanical recycling,” “multilayer film → chemical delamination or disposal”). Example materials (empty wrappers, labelled plastic containers, bioplastics) should be collected and pre-classified.

Time required: Approximately 10–15 minutes for role assignment and instruction, 25–30 minutes for the simulation, and 15 minutes for group discussion and reflection.

Learning outcome: Students will gain an understanding of the complexity of recycling decisions, the impact of contamination, and the need for innovation in managing hard-to-recycle materials.

6.3.4. Valorisation of Agri-Food Waste

Overview

This presentation explores how food industry waste can be transformed into valuable bio-based products, reducing environmental impact and promoting circular economy principles.

Key Contents

- **Sources of Agri-Food Waste:** Fruits, vegetables, and organic residues from food processing.
- **Extraction of High-Value Components:**
 - Fibre for food applications
 - Polyphenols with antioxidant properties for nutraceuticals
 - Biodegradable plastics derived from agro-waste

- **Industrial Applications:**
 - Use of natural extracts in cosmetics and food
 - Fermentation processes to create biodegradable materials
- **Agro2Circular Solutions:** Real-world examples of how waste valorisation is being implemented in European industries.

Application for Educators

- **Product Development Exercise:** Students design a sustainable product using agro-waste as a raw material.
- **Field Study:** Visit to a food processing plant or composting facility to observe waste management strategies in action.

6.4. SE4: Debate: circular economy vs lineal economy

6.4.1. Introduction

Objective of the Material

This debate activity aims to help students critically explore the circular economy in contrast to the linear economy. By engaging in structured argumentation, students will evaluate key economic, environmental, and social factors, such as resource efficiency, waste reduction, and job creation.

Target Audience

This material is designed for secondary school teachers who wish to promote critical thinking, research skills, and debate techniques while deepening students' understanding of sustainability and economic models.

Contribution to the Circular Economy in the agrifood sector

Through this debate, students will:

- Understand the differences between the linear and circular economy models.
- Evaluate the environmental, economic, and social impacts of both approaches.
- Develop argumentation skills by using real-world examples from the agri-food sector.
- Reflect on long-term sustainability and the role of policy, industry, and individuals in shaping a greener future.

6.4.2. Activity Overview

Debate Structure

1. Preparation

Students will be divided into two teams:

Team 1: Circular Economy Advocates – Research and argue in favour of the circular economy, emphasising its advantages.

Team 2: Linear Economy Defenders – Research and argue in favour of the linear economy, focusing on its practical and economic benefits.

Students will be given time to conduct research, gather supporting data, and structure their arguments before the debate begins.

2. Debate Phases

- ✓ Introduction (5 minutes): Each team presents its best-supported arguments defending its assigned economic model.
- ✓ Development (15 minutes): Students engage in spontaneous argumentation, responding to and refuting the opposing team's points.
- ✓ Conclusion (5 minutes): The most compelling arguments will be summarised, and the class will reflect on key takeaways.
- ✓ Final Reflection: A teacher-led discussion will help students analyse why the circular economy is considered the preferred model for long-term sustainability.

Evaluation Criteria

Students' performance in the debate will be assessed based on the following:

- Research and Preparation: Depth of research, clarity of arguments, and use of supporting evidence (data, facts, examples).
- Concept Understanding: Demonstrated knowledge of circular and linear economy models, particularly in the agri-food sector.
- Organisation and Clarity: Logical and structured presentation of ideas.
- Use of Examples and Evidence: Application of concrete real-world examples related to the agri-food sector.
- Communication and Expression: Confident, clear speaking, good voice modulation, and audience engagement.
- Active Listening and Refutation: Ability to respond logically to counterarguments while maintaining a respectful debate tone.
- Teamwork: Collaboration, role distribution, and mutual support within teams.
- Time Management: Adherence to assigned speaking times.
- Respect and Debate Etiquette: Consideration for opposing viewpoints, avoiding interruptions, and maintaining constructive discussion.

Topics for Debate

The debate will cover key economic, environmental, and social themes, including:

- Differences between the linear and circular economy
- Resource use and conservation
- Waste reduction and management
- Environmental impact and pollution
- Job creation and economic opportunities
- Long-term sustainability and economic viability
- Food security in a circular economy
- Effects on soil quality and biodiversity
- Water management in food production
- Plastic consumption and reduction strategies
- Reuse and upcycling of materials and waste
- Adaptation to climate change
- Future vision: Which system is better for long-term prosperity?

6.4.3. Suggested References

For research and argument development, students can refer to the following educational resources:

Circular and Linear Economy

[5] Ellen MacArthur Foundation. Introduction to the Circular Economy. [Read More](#)

[6] Ellen MacArthur Foundation. What is the Linear Economy? [Learn More](#)

Water and Resource Management

[7] AEDyR. (2020, April 30). What is Water Reuse? AEDyR

Agri-Food Industry and Sustainability

[8] Agri-Food Industry: Evolution and Challenges. (2024, July 16).

6.5. SE5: Create a prototype business using circular economy principles

6.5.1. Introduction and Learning Objectives

This training material is designed for secondary and bachelor-level students, providing them with a structured approach to developing a prototype business model that integrates circular economy principles. The activity will focus on food waste collection and recycling, aligning with the Agro2Circular (A2C) model, and will encourage students to apply business planning, sustainability strategies, and entrepreneurial thinking.

Through this activity, students will:

- Understand circular economy business models and their relevance in the agri-food sector.
- Develop a business plan that applies circular economy strategies.
- Identify economic and environmental benefits of food waste valorisation.
- Strengthen problem-solving, teamwork, and business analysis skills.

This activity is connected with SE1 (Case Study Analysis of Circular Business Models) and SE2 (Brainstorming New Business Models), forming a progressive learning sequence that allows students to move from theory to practical application. This educational activity **contributes to the circular economy in the agri-food sector** by engaging students in the design of innovative business models focused on food waste collection and recycling. By turning waste into valuable resources and applying circular principles such as upcycling and redistribution, the exercise fosters awareness and entrepreneurial thinking aligned with sustainable food systems.

6.5.2. Background: Circular Economy and Business Models in Agri-Food Systems

Traditional food production and consumption follow a linear model:

Take → Produce → Consume → Dispose

This results in massive food waste, high carbon emissions, and inefficient resource use. In contrast, a circular business model aims to:

- Prevent waste by optimising food production and consumption.
- Repurpose waste into valuable by-products (e.g., compost, bioenergy, animal feed).

- Create new business opportunities through waste management and recycling.

According to Lamolinara et al. (2024), circular business models in agribusiness are still underdeveloped but have high potential for adoption, particularly in food production, processing, and waste management. Barros et al. (2023) highlight that agro-industrial cooperatives play a crucial role in closing resource loops by integrating innovation, collaboration, and new business models.

By designing a business model for food waste collection and recycling, students will explore how companies can reduce waste, create value, and promote sustainability.

6.5.3. Structure of the Activity

Step 1: Defining the Business Concept

Students work in small teams to define their circular economy business prototype. The focus is on creating a food waste collection and recycling business that addresses real sustainability challenges while being economically viable.

Each team should research and identify a specific food waste problem, considering:

- The source of food waste (households, restaurants, supermarkets, food processing industries).
- The scale of the problem (local, regional, national).
- The impact of food waste (economic losses, environmental pollution, resource depletion).

Once they define the problem, students brainstorm potential solutions, ensuring that their proposed business follows circular economy principles such as:

- Waste prevention: reducing food surplus through redistribution.
- Upcycling: transforming food waste into new products (e.g., bio-based packaging, natural fertilisers).
- Recycling: turning organic waste into compost, biofuels, or biogas.

At this stage, students outline the core idea of their business in a problem-solution format, summarising:

- The issue being addressed.
- The innovative solution proposed.
- The expected impact of the business.

Educators should encourage students to justify their choices, linking them to real-world sustainability concerns.

Step 2: Business Model Development

Students structure their business idea using a Business Model Canvas, covering the following key components:

1. **Value Proposition** – What problem does the business solve? What products/services does it offer? How does it incorporate circular economy principles?
2. **Customer Segments** – Who are the primary customers? What needs or pain points does the business address?
3. **Distribution Channels** – How will the business collect food waste? How will it sell or distribute the recycled products?
4. **Revenue Streams** – How will the business generate income? (e.g., waste collection fees, sales of recycled products, government incentives)
5. **Key Resources** – What technologies, infrastructure, or partnerships are needed?
6. **Key Activities** – What are the core operations of the business? (e.g., waste collection, processing, marketing, sales)
7. **Key Partnerships** – Which organisations or stakeholders could support the business? (e.g., local government, waste management firms, research institutions)
8. **Cost Structure** – What are the main costs associated with running the business?

Once the Business Model Canvas is completed, teams should refine and validate their ideas by:

- Researching existing similar businesses for insights and inspiration.
- Identifying challenges and risks in the implementation phase.
- Estimating costs, profitability, and scalability.

Step 3: Presenting the Business Plan

Each team presents their prototype business plan, focusing on:

- The identified problem and solution.
- The circular economy approach integrated into the business model.
- Potential customers and market feasibility.
- Expected economic and environmental benefits.
- Challenges and limitations.

Presentation formats can include:

- Pitch presentations with slides.
- Posters or infographics summarising key business elements.
- Short videos or mock advertisements showcasing their business idea.

Evaluation Criteria

Educators should evaluate projects based on:

- Innovativeness and creativity – How original is the business idea?
- Feasibility and scalability – Can the model realistically be implemented?
- Impact and sustainability – How well does the business address food waste challenges?
- Quality of presentation and teamwork – Is the idea communicated clearly and effectively?

After all teams have presented, educators should facilitate a discussion, asking students:

- Which business model was the most promising? Why?
- What challenges might these businesses face in real-world implementation?
- What role do governments, businesses, and consumers play in making circular businesses successful?

6.5.4. Key Takeaways

By the end of the activity, students should:

- Understand how circular economy business models function.
- Recognise the economic, environmental, and social benefits of food waste recycling.
- Develop entrepreneurial and problem-solving skills.
- Gain insights into real-world applications of circular business strategies.

This activity bridges theory with practice, enabling students to think critically about sustainability challenges and business opportunities in the agri-food sector.

6.5.5. 5. References

[9] B. Lamolinara, M. S. Teixeira, C. G. Marreiros, V. H. S. Ferreira, and A. Pérez-Martínez, "An overview of circular business models in agribusiness," in *Entrepreneurship, Technological Change and Circular Economy for a Green Transition*, C. Rego et al., Eds. Cham: Springer, 2024, pp. 1–18. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-48079-9_7

[10] M. V. Barros, R. H. G. Jesus, B. S. Ribeiro, and C. M. Piekarski, "Going in circles: Key aspects for circular economy contributions to agro-industrial cooperatives," *Circular Economy and Sustainability*, vol. 3, pp. 861–880, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43615-022-00211-8>

6.6. SE6: Circular business challenge: sustainable packaging and food products from waste

6.6.1. Introduction

Objective of the Material

This project-based learning activity introduces students to the circular economy by challenging them to design a business plan focused on sustainable packaging and food products made from food waste. Students will research materials, production technologies, and recycling processes while evaluating costs, benefits, and business strategies for implementing a circular approach in the agri-food sector.

Target Audience

This material is designed for secondary school and baccalaureate teachers who wish to promote entrepreneurial skills, critical thinking, and sustainability awareness among students.

Contribution to the Circular Economy

Through this challenge, students will:

- Understand the problem of food waste and its economic and environmental impacts.
- Explore solutions for circular packaging and food product development from waste.
- Analyse real-world strategies to optimise waste collection, processing, and recycling.
- Apply sustainable production and consumption principles to minimise environmental impact.

6.6.2. Activity Guide: Creating a Circular Business Plan

Students will develop a business plan for a company focused on circular food production and packaging solutions. The class will be divided into four groups, each responsible for a different phase of the project.

1. Research Phase

Identifying the Problem

- ✓ What types of food waste exist in the agri-food sector?
- ✓ What are the environmental and economic problems linked to food waste?
- ✓ Why is transitioning to circular packaging and food products necessary?

Investigating Materials and Technologies

- ✓ Explore sustainable materials for packaging and their properties (e.g., compostable bioplastics).
- ✓ Research methods for collecting food waste and recycling technologies.
- ✓ Investigate food waste transformation techniques (e.g., turning fruit peels into flour or by-products).

Cost-Benefit Analysis

- ✓ Calculate the costs of production, considering raw materials, technology, and logistics.
- ✓ Evaluate economic and environmental benefits, such as material cost savings, reduced waste disposal costs, and added value of sustainable products.

Case Studies

- ✓ Identify existing companies producing packaging or food products from waste.
- ✓ Examine their business models and innovation strategies.

2. Product Design and Development

Sustainable Packaging Design

- ✓ Select eco-friendly materials (recyclable, biodegradable, reusable).

- ✓ Ensure packaging reduces waste, such as minimalist or plastic-free designs.

Food Waste Transformation

- ✓ Choose a type of food waste (e.g., vegetable scraps, fruit peels).
- ✓ Develop a food product incorporating waste (e.g., juices, dried snacks, sauces).

Collection and Recycling Logistics

- ✓ Plan an efficient collection system for food waste.
- ✓ Assess waste recycling options to maximise resource efficiency.

3. Waste Minimisation Strategies in Production

Optimisation and Recycling in the Process

- ✓ Identify waste points in production and eliminate inefficiencies.
- ✓ Implement a "zero waste" policy, ensuring all by-products are reused.

Circular Economy Implementation

- ✓ Design a system to extend the lifespan of products and facilitate recycling or reuse.
- ✓ Reduce water and energy consumption throughout the process.

Consumer Education and Awareness

- ✓ Develop marketing strategies to promote circular food products.
- ✓ Create campaigns to educate consumers on sustainable purchasing habits.

4. Business Plan Development and Presentation

Each group will present their business plan, including:

- ✓ Business model and target audience.
- ✓ Cost-benefit analysis of materials and production.
- ✓ Sustainable packaging and food waste innovation.
- ✓ Marketing and consumer engagement strategy.
- ✓ Distribution and sales plan for the circular products.

Evaluation Criteria

Students will be assessed based on:

- ✓ Research and Innovation: Depth of research and creativity in proposed solutions.
- ✓ Feasibility and Practicality: Realistic application of circular economy principles.
- ✓ Business Plan Clarity: Organisation, logic, and clarity in presenting ideas.
- ✓ Use of Evidence and Data: Integration of relevant case studies, examples, and economic data.
- ✓ Communication and Collaboration: Teamwork, effective presentation skills, and engagement.

6.6.3. Suggested References

Circular Business and Sustainability

- [11] L. Blanco, "The importance of implementing a sustainability strategy in companies," *Atisa*, Feb. 2, 2024.
- [12] L. Caorsi, "Circular food: How to reduce waste and protect the environment," *Eroski Consumer*, Jun. 7, 2022.
- [13] R. Apd, "¿Qué estrategias de sostenibilidad empresarial puedes empezar a implementar en tu empresa?," *APD España*, Jun. 19, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.apd.es/estrategias-sostenibilidad-empresarial/>
- [14] L. Blanco, "La importancia de implementar una estrategia de sostenibilidad en las empresas," *Atisa*, Feb. 2, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://atisa.es/blog/estrategia-sostenibilidad/>
- [15] P. Pérez, "Estrategias de Economía Circular para empresas - Nueva ISO 14001," *Nueva ISO 14001*, Feb. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nueva-iso-14001.com/2024/01/estrategias-de-economia-circular-para-empresas/>

Food Waste and Recycling

- [16] H. Fraga, "Recycling: Everyday objects we can reuse," *Gestán Conteco*, Jun. 25, 2020.

6.7. SE7: Designing a circular economy strategy for a region

6.7.1. Introduction

Objective of the Material

This activity enables students to design a circular economy strategy tailored to a city or region. By analysing local characteristics, exploring circular economy principles, and proposing feasible solutions, students will gain practical insights into sustainability and the ecological transition.

Target Audience

This material is designed for secondary school and baccalaureate teachers looking to introduce students to circular economy planning, regional development, and sustainability strategy design.

Contribution to the Circular Economy

This activity helps students:

- Understand the complexity of circular economy transitions at a regional level.
- Analyse environmental, social, and economic factors affecting sustainability.
- Develop feasible strategies for waste reduction, resource efficiency, and economic resilience.

6.7.2. Activity Guide: Creating a Circular Economy Strategy

Students will simulate the process of designing a circular economy action plan for a city or region. They will consider local resources, infrastructure, policies, and socioeconomic conditions to formulate a realistic and effective strategy.

1. Selection and Research of the City or Region

- ✓ Selecting a location: Students will choose a city or region as their case study.
- ✓ Understanding the local context: They will research the region's economic activities, environmental challenges, and waste management practices.

✓ Identifying key resources: Students should explore local industries, renewable energy potential, and existing circular economy initiatives.

2. Analysis of Regional Characteristics

Students will analyse how their chosen region can transition to a circular economy by considering key factors:

Environmental Factors

- ✓ How is waste currently managed?
- ✓ Are there systems for waste valorisation, recycling, and water efficiency?
- ✓ What environmental challenges does the region face (e.g., pollution, biodiversity loss)?

Socioeconomic Factors

- ✓ What industries dominate the regional economic structure?
- ✓ What is the region's capacity for business innovation and workforce upskilling?
- ✓ How do local cultural attitudes influence circular economy adoption?

Governance and Policy

- ✓ Are there existing circular economy policies or action plans?
- ✓ How engaged are public authorities, businesses, and civil society in circular initiatives?
- ✓ Are there financial incentives or regulatory barriers for circular economy adoption?

Students should document their findings and use data sources, case studies, or policy examples where possible.

3. Strategy Design and Implementation

- ✓ Formulating a circular economy strategy based on the research phase.
- ✓ Incorporating key circular economy principles, such as:
 - Waste reduction, reuse, repair, and recycling.
 - Efficient water and energy use.
 - Sustainable business models.
- ✓ Aligning with the A2C Model to structure the strategy effectively.

Key Challenge: Would the Agro2Circular model be applicable to this region? Students must justify their decision based on the local conditions.

4. Observations on Implementation

✓ Simulating the effects of their strategy by considering:

- Expected economic and environmental benefits.
- Potential barriers or limitations.

✓ Proposing solutions for identified weaknesses.

✓ Adjusting the strategy based on observations.

5. Group Discussion and Reflection

✓ Presenting findings: Each group presents its strategy, highlighting:

- Key research findings.
- Chosen circular economy approach.

Expected benefits and implementation challenges.

✓ Class debate:

- Could the A2C model be successfully applied to the region? Why or why not?
- What are the biggest challenges in implementing circular strategies at a regional level?
- Which strategies were the most innovative and feasible?

✓ Voting on the most effective strategy based on how well it applies circular economy principles.

- Integration of the Agro2Circular (A2C) Model
- Students will be introduced to the Agro2Circular (A2C) model, which serves as a framework for evaluating regional circular economy readiness.

They should assess whether their selected region meets the key dimensions of the A2C model:

Key Dimensions of the A2C Model

- ✚ Environmental: Waste valorisation, resource efficiency, climate adaptation.
- ✚ Socioeconomic: Business innovation, workforce skills, local engagement.

- ✚ Governance: Policy support, multi-level coordination, stakeholder collaboration.
- ✚ Funding & Finance: Availability of CE funding and incentives.
- ✚ Technology & R&D: Infrastructure for waste recovery, innovation potential.

✓ Would this model work in their chosen region? Analysing the resulting spider diagram, what are the most advanced dimensions? What the less advanced? What are the consequences? How can this be overcome?

✓ What adaptations would be needed to apply the A2C model effectively?

Evaluation Criteria

Students will be assessed based on:

- ✓ Depth of Research: Understanding of regional circular economy potential.
- ✓ Strategy Development: Feasibility and innovation of proposed solutions.
- ✓ Application of the A2C Model: Logical assessment of whether the model can be applied.
- ✓ Presentation and Communication: Clear and engaging explanation of their findings.
- ✓ Critical Thinking: Justification of decisions and response to peer feedback.

6.7.3. Suggested references

CORDIS. Agro2Circular Project results: A2C Model and Self-assessment tool:
<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036838/results> & <https://sat.agro2dis.eu/>

6.8. SE8: Exploring circular economy: practical approaches to recycling, repair, and bioremediation

This training plan provides secondary and bachelor-level teachers with practical, hands-on activities to introduce students to circular economy principles and innovative recycling and bioremediation technologies. Each activity includes:

- ✓ Introduction and Learning Objectives – What students will learn and why it matters.
- ✓ Activity Overview – Step-by-step guidance on how to conduct the activity.
- ✓ Materials Needed – What teachers and students need to prepare.
- ✓ Supporting References – Where teachers can find additional information.

6.8.1. Practical Activities for Secondary Education

6.8.1.1. Activity 1: Sorting and Recycling of Plastics

Introduction and Learning Objectives

Understanding how plastics are sorted and recycled is fundamental to waste management.

This activity allows students to:

- ✓ Recognize different types of plastics and their recycling codes.
- ✓ Simulate industrial sorting techniques using hands-on experiments.
- ✓ Understand the challenges of multi-layer plastics recycling.

Activity Overview

Plastic Identification Challenge

- Students collect various plastic waste items from their daily use (bottles, food packaging, containers).
- They examine labels and identify the resin identification codes (RICs, 1-7).
- Students categorize plastics based on ease of recycling and discuss which ones are most problematic.

Density-Based Plastic Sorting Experiment

- Students cut plastic samples and place them in water and different salt solutions to observe floating and sinking behaviors. This mimics industrial sorting by density used in recycling plants.

Real-World Discussion

- Why are some plastics non-recyclable?
- What happens to multi-layer plastics?
- How can we improve sorting technologies?

Materials Needed

- ✂ Plastic waste samples (bottles, food containers, wrappers)
- ✂ Salt, water, beakers, stirring rods
- ✂ Plastic sorting chart (printed or digital)

Supporting References

Teachers should refer to CORDIS (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036838/results>) and search for the following deliverables:

- ◆ A2C_D3.14 D84 – Technologies for sorting and recycling of multilayer plastics residues (Public Summary).v1.0

6.8.1.2. Activity 2: Repair and Upcycling Challenge

Introduction and Learning Objectives

Instead of throwing plastic items away, repairing and repurposing them can extend their lifespan. This activity teaches students to:

- ✓ Use basic plastic repair techniques.
- ✓ Develop creative solutions for upcycling discarded plastic objects.
- ✓ Understand the role of reuse in circular economy.

Activity Overview

Plastic Repair Workshop

- Students bring broken plastic objects (toys, cases, small furniture).
- Using heat welding (glue guns, plastic welding pens), they repair cracks and test the strength of the repaired objects.

Creative Upcycling Challenge

- Students design and create new items from plastic waste (e.g., pen holders, phone stands, plant pots).
- Teams present their upcycled products and discuss their practical applications.

Materials Needed

- ✂ Broken plastic objects
- ✂ Glue guns, plastic welding kits
- ✂ Paints, brushes, crafting tools

Supporting References

Refer to CORDIS (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036838/results>) for:

- ◆ A2C_D3.14 D84 – Technologies for sorting and recycling of multilayer plastics residues (Public Summary).v1.0

6.8.2. 2. Practical Activities for Bachelor-Level Students

6.8.2.1. Activity 3: Mechanical, Chemical, and Enzymatic Recycling of Plastics

Introduction and Learning Objectives

Students will explore three different recycling techniques used in industry:

- ✓ Mechanical recycling – Shredding and remelting plastics into new materials.
- ✓ Chemical recycling – Breaking down plastics into their chemical building blocks.
- ✓ Enzymatic recycling – Using biological enzymes to degrade plastics.

Activity Overview

Mechanical Recycling (Hands-on)

- Students shred plastic bottles into small pieces.
- They heat and remold plastic into simple shapes (e.g., sheets or blocks).
- Discuss material degradation and limits of mechanical recycling.

Chemical Recycling (Lab Experiment)

- Bioplastics experiment based on this [publication](#).
- Observe the reaction process and discuss its industrial applications.

Enzymatic Recycling (Demonstration)

- A lab demonstration of PETase enzyme activity, breaking down PET into monomers (TPA and EG).
- Compare efficiency of enzymatic vs. chemical processes.

Materials Needed

- ✂ Plastic shredders, heating press
- ✂ Chemical reagents for glycolysis (ethylene glycol, catalysts)
- ✂ PETase enzyme sample

Supporting References

Refer to CORDIS (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036838/results>) for:

- ◆ A2C_D3.14 D84 – Technologies for sorting and recycling of multilayer plastics residues (Public Summary).v1.0

6.8.2.2. Activity 4: Bioremediation and Bio-Based Product Synthesis

Introduction and Learning Objectives

Students will explore biological solutions for treating waste and producing bio-based materials:

- ✓ Bioremediation – Using microbes to break down pollutants.
- ✓ Bio-based plastics – Creating biodegradable materials from organic waste.

Activity Overview

Bioremediation Simulation

- Students prepare microbial cultures that degrade hydrocarbons.
- Oil-contaminated soil samples are treated with bacteria (e.g., *Pseudomonas putida*).
- Observe bacterial growth and breakdown of pollutants over time.

Production of Bio-Based Plastics

- Extract starch from food waste (e.g., potatoes, corn).
- Combine starch with glycerol and vinegar to create bioplastics.
- Compare properties of bio-based plastic vs. conventional plastic.

Materials Needed

- ✂ Oil-contaminated soil samples
- ✂ Bacterial cultures (*Pseudomonas putida*)
- ✂ Lab equipment for microbial culturing
- ✂ Food waste (potatoes, corn), glycerol, vinegar

Supporting References

Refer to CORDIS (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036838/results>) for:

- ◆ A2C_D2.5.D83 – Technologies for recycling of organic agrofood waste (Public Summary).v1.0

6.8.3. Summary of Learning Outcomes

By completing these activities, students will:

- ✓ Gain practical experience in plastic recycling and bioremediation.
- ✓ Understand mechanical, chemical, and enzymatic recycling processes.
- ✓ Develop problem-solving skills for sustainable waste management.

6.9. SE9: Career and professions related to the circular economy

6.9.1. Introduction

Objective of the Material

This material introduces students to green jobs and professions linked to the circular economy, showing how various careers contribute to sustainability, resource efficiency, and environmental protection.

Target Audience

This material is designed for secondary school and baccalaureate teachers to educate students on career opportunities in the circular economy and sustainable entrepreneurship.

Contribution to the Circular Economy

Encourages students to explore green careers that promote sustainable economic growth. Illustrates the role of different professions in transitioning from a linear to a circular economy. Raises awareness of the need for innovation, sustainability, and responsible resource management across industries.
materials.

To avoid unnecessary length, the slides accompanying these educational materials have not been included in this document. They are available for consultation on the CORDIS platform at the following link: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036838/results>.

6.9.2. Professions in the Circular Economy

This section outlines key professions linked to the circular economy, which students can explore as potential career paths.

1. Circular Economy Specialist

- ✓ Role: Develops and advises companies on transitioning from a linear to a circular economy by optimising resource use, minimising waste, and promoting reuse and recycling.
- ✓ Key Tasks: Identifying inefficiencies, designing circular economy strategies, and implementing sustainable production models.
- ✓ Relevance: Essential for companies seeking to align with circular economy principles and reduce environmental impact.

2. Sustainability Consultant

- ✓ Role: Advises businesses and institutions on implementing environmental and social responsibility practices.
- ✓ Key Tasks: Conducting sustainability assessments, designing strategies to reduce emissions and optimise resource use, and integrating circular economy models into business operations.
- ✓ Relevance: Helps organisations meet sustainability targets and comply with environmental regulations.

3. Environmental Engineer

- ✓ Role: Designs and implements environmental protection projects, including waste management, pollution control, and clean technology development.
- ✓ Key Tasks: Reducing environmental footprints, developing waste recycling systems, and optimising resource efficiency.
- ✓ Relevance: Plays a critical role in ensuring sustainability in industrial processes.

4. Recycling and Waste Engineer

- ✓ Role: Specialises in waste management, from collection to treatment and recycling.
- ✓ Key Tasks: Designing efficient waste recovery processes, minimising landfill dependency, and integrating recycled materials back into production.
- ✓ Relevance: Key in developing closed-loop production cycles that align with circular economy goals.

5. Renewable Energy Specialist

- ✓ Role: Develops clean and renewable energy sources, such as solar, wind, hydroelectric, and biomass.
- ✓ Key Tasks: Reducing dependency on fossil fuels, implementing sustainable energy solutions, and lowering greenhouse gas emissions.
- ✓ Relevance: Ensures that the transition to circularity is powered by clean energy sources.

6. CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) Manager

- ✓ Role: Integrates sustainability into business strategies, ensuring social and environmental responsibility.
- ✓ Key Tasks: Implementing circular economy practices within companies, such as waste reduction, resource efficiency, and recycling initiatives.
- ✓ Relevance: Helps companies align with sustainable development goals (SDGs) and consumer expectations.

7. Environmental Auditor

- ✓ Role: Evaluates whether an organisation meets environmental regulations and sustainability standards.
- ✓ Key Tasks: Conducting audits, identifying areas for improvement, and ensuring compliance with circular economy principles.
- ✓ Relevance: Ensures that companies are operating in an environmentally responsible manner.

8. Circular Product Designer

- ✓ Role: Designs products with circularity in mind, ensuring they are durable, repairable, and recyclable.
- ✓ Key Tasks: Selecting sustainable materials, creating modular and repair-friendly designs, and promoting product lifecycle extension.
- ✓ Relevance: Fundamental for reducing waste at the design stage, supporting product reuse and recycling.

6.9.3. Suggested References for Further Reading

General Overview of Circular Economy Careers

FormaZion Web (2023). ¿Qué salidas profesionales hay en la economía circular?

Link: https://www.mastermania.com/noticias_masters/que-salidas-profesionales-hay-en-la-economia-circular-org-7828.html

Circular Economy and Green Job Market Trends

Morales, S. (2021). La economía circular genera millones de nuevos perfiles profesionales. Qué!

Link: https://www.que.es/2021/12/22/economia-circular-genera-millones-nuevos-perfiles-profesionales/?utm_campaign=twitter

Promateriales. (2024). Profesiones que impulsan un futuro más sostenible.

Link: <https://prosostenible.es/profesiones-que-impulsan-un-futuro-mas-sostenible/>

ILO Reports on Green Jobs and Youth Employment

Green Jobs for Youth: Boosting Decent Jobs for Young People, Greening the Economy.

Link: <https://www.decentjobsforyouth.org/wordpress/wpcontent/uploads/2017/08/Thematic-Plan-4-Green-Jobs.pdf>

Growing Green: Fostering a Green Entrepreneurial Ecosystem for Youth (ILO Report).

Link: <https://www.youthforesight.org/resource-details/Publications/466>

ILO Report on Green Jobs and Sustainability in Business.

Link: https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_emp/documents/publication/wcms_755851.pdf

6.9.4. How to Use This Material in a Slideshow

Teachers can structure their slideshow as follows:

Option 1: presentation:

- ✓ **Slide 1:** Title and Introduction – Brief explanation of why green jobs are important.
- ✓ **Slide 2-10:** Each profession on a separate slide, including a short description, key tasks, and relevance.
- ✓ **Slide 11:** Future Job Market Trends – Emphasising the growth of circular economy careers.
- ✓ **Slide 12:** Discussion Questions – Encouraging students to reflect on which careers interest them most and why.
- ✓ **Slide 13:** References and Further Reading – Providing students with sources to explore deeper.

Option 2: student presentations:

Design a class activity in which students research these professions and give presentations to explain them to their classmates, including tasks, competencies, how to obtain the diploma, etc. for each profession.

7. ANNEX III - Training Plan for local actors: Higher education

7.1. HE1: Study Modules for Higher Education. Circular Economy Business Models: Analysis and implementation

Target Audience:

Undergraduate students in Business Administration, Economics, and Environmental Sciences.

Course Duration:

8 weeks

Course Objectives:

- Understand the concept of **Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM)**.
- Learn how to **analyse a company's business model** in terms of circularity.
- Develop skills to **propose strategies** to transition a business towards a more circular approach.
- Gain practical insights through **case studies** and real-world applications.

7.1.1. Module 1: Introduction to Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM)

Objective: Understand what Circular Business Models are and how they differ from linear models.

Topics:

1. **Definition of Business Models**
 - What is a business model?
 - Business Model Canvas (BMC) framework overview.
2. **Transition from Linear to Circular Business Models**
 - Linear vs. Circular: Key differences.
 - The role of circularity in business strategy.
3. **Main Types of Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM)**
 - Product-as-a-Service (PaaS).
 - Resource recovery models.
 - Sharing economy models.
 - Extended product life-cycle models (repair, remanufacturing).
 - Closed-loop supply chains.

4. Key Drivers and Barriers to Circular Business Models

- Economic, environmental, and regulatory factors.
- Organisational and market challenges.

Activity:

- **Case study discussion:** Analyse an example of a company that has successfully implemented a circular business model.

To enrich the discussion of case studies on companies that have successfully implemented circular business models, it is proposed to select a company from the **Directory of Good Practices in Circular Economy in the Agri-Food Sector** developed by the Agro2Circular project.

Once the company has been selected, it is suggested that an interview be conducted with a representative or manager of the company to learn more about their experience in implementing circular economy practices. Below are some items that could guide the interview:

1. Initial Motivations:

- What factors prompted the company to adopt a business model based on the circular economy?
- Were there any specific issues they were seeking to resolve through this approach?

2. Implementation Process:

- What key steps did you take to integrate circular economy practices into your operations?
- What challenges did you face during the transition from a linear to a circular model?

3. Innovations and Strategies:

- What outstanding innovations have you implemented to close the loop on your products or services?
- How have you redesigned your supply chain to align with the principles of the circular economy?

4. Impact and Benefits:

- What economic, environmental and social benefits have you observed following the adoption of circular practices?
- How has this transformation influenced the perception of the brand by customers and other stakeholders?

5. **Lessons Learned and Recommendations:**

- What key lessons have you learned throughout the implementation process?
- What recommendations would you offer to other companies in the agri-food sector interested in adopting circular business models?

6. **Future and Sustainability:**

- What are the next steps or projects you are planning to continue advancing in the circular economy?
- How do you ensure the sustainability and scalability of your circular practices in the long term?

7.1.2. **Module 2: Analytical Frameworks for Assessing Circular Business Models**

Objective: Learn how to systematically evaluate a business model's level of circularity.

Topics:

1. **Business Model Canvas (BMC) for Circularity**

- How to adapt BMC to include circular components.
- Circular Value Proposition & Circular Revenue Streams.

What is a Business Model Canvas (BMC)?

The Business Model Canvas (BMC) is a strategic tool used to visualize and design business models. Developed by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010), it consists of nine building blocks that define how a business creates, delivers, and captures value.

Adapting the Business Model Canvas for the Circular Economy

Traditional business models are linear, following a "take-make-dispose" approach. In contrast, a **Circular Business Model Canvas (CBMC)** integrates sustainability by closing resource loops and creating value from waste and by-products.

Nine Key Components of the Circular Business Model Canvas

1. **Customer Segments**

- Who are the key stakeholders benefiting from circular solutions?
- Examples: Sustainable food retailers, eco-conscious consumers, food processing companies needing by-products.

2. Value Proposition

- What unique value does the business offer in terms of circularity?
- Examples: Zero-waste production, upcycled food products, sustainable packaging solutions.

3. Channels

- How does the business reach its customers?
- Examples: Direct sales, online platforms, circular supply chains.

4. Customer Relationships

- How does the business engage customers in circular practices?
- Examples: Deposit-refund systems, subscription models for reusable packaging.

5. Revenue Streams

- How does the company generate revenue from circularity?
- Examples: Selling waste-derived products, leasing equipment instead of selling, extended producer responsibility programs.

6. Key Resources

- What resources are essential for implementing a circular model?
- Examples: Waste valorization infrastructure, renewable energy, local sourcing networks.

7. Key Activities

- What processes ensure circularity in the business model?
- Examples: Reverse logistics, product take-back systems, composting or biogas production.

8. Key Partnerships

- Who are the external stakeholders supporting the circular economy transition?
- Examples: Agricultural cooperatives, waste management firms, research institutions.

9. Cost Structure

- What are the major costs involved in maintaining a circular business?
- Examples: Investment in closed-loop processing systems, certification costs for sustainable products.

Applying the Circular Business Model Canvas to the Agri-Food Sector

BMC Component	Traditional Business Model	Circular Business Model
Customer Segments	General food consumers	Consumers who prioritize sustainable and circular products
Value Proposition	Selling fresh produce	Selling fresh produce while converting food waste into value-added products
Channels	Supermarkets, distributors	Direct-to-consumer, partnerships with zero-waste retailers
Customer Relationships	One-time transactions	Engagement through loyalty programs and waste-return incentives
Revenue Streams	Sales of food products	Subscription models, upcycling food waste into secondary products
Key Resources	Raw materials, processing facilities	Renewable resources, waste recovery systems
Key Activities	Traditional food processing	Waste valorization, reverse logistics
Key Partnerships	Distributors, suppliers	Circular packaging providers, sustainability certifiers
Cost Structure	Linear production costs	Investment in circular technologies and processes

Why Use a Circular Business Model Canvas?

- Helps visualize circular opportunities in the business model.
- Supports the transition from linear to circular value creation.
- Encourages stakeholder collaboration for sustainability.

2. Circularity Gap Analysis

- Identifying inefficiencies and waste streams.

- How to measure circular performance (KPIs, lifecycle assessment).

Circularity Gap Analysis

A **Circularity Gap Analysis** is a critical step in assessing the current state of a company's resource flows and identifying inefficiencies that hinder the transition from a linear to a circular business model. This analysis helps pinpoint key intervention areas where circular strategies can reduce waste, improve resource efficiency, and create economic and environmental value.

Identifying Inefficiencies and Waste Streams

Identifying inefficiencies involves mapping out material, energy, and water flows throughout a company's operations to detect points of resource loss, excessive consumption, or underutilization. The following areas should be evaluated:

1. Raw Material Use:

- Are virgin materials used instead of recycled or renewable resources?
- Is there a high reliance on non-renewable inputs?

2. Production and Processing Waste:

- What percentage of materials become waste during manufacturing?
- Are by-products currently reused, repurposed, or disposed of?

3. Product Lifecycle:

- How long does the product last before it becomes waste?
- Are design choices limiting reuse, repairability, or recyclability?

4. End-of-Life Management:

- Are take-back schemes or closed-loop recycling systems in place?
- What percentage of products/materials re-enter the supply chain after use?

5. Logistics and Supply Chain Inefficiencies:

- Are transportation methods optimised for emissions and resource efficiency?
- Is packaging excessive, single-use, or non-recyclable?

6. Energy and Water Consumption:

- Are energy-intensive processes in place that could be optimised?
- What water recovery and reuse strategies are implemented?

How to Measure Circular Performance

To track progress in circularity, businesses can adopt various measurement tools and key performance indicators (KPIs). The most effective frameworks include:

1. **Circular Economy KPIs:**

- **Material Circularity Indicator (MCI):** Measures how effectively materials are cycled within a system.
- **Percentage of Secondary Raw Materials Used:** Tracks the proportion of recycled or recovered materials in production.
- **Waste-to-Product Ratio:** Measures the amount of waste generated per unit of product produced.

2. **Lifecycle Assessment (LCA):**

- A systematic methodology to evaluate the environmental impact of a product throughout its entire lifecycle (from raw material extraction to disposal).
- Helps businesses identify hotspots of resource inefficiency and carbon emissions.

3. **Product Longevity Metrics:**

- Average lifespan of a product before it is discarded.
- Percentage of products designed for reuse, refurbishment, or remanufacturing.

4. **Recycling and Recovery Rates:**

- Percentage of post-consumer products that are recycled or recovered for secondary use.
- Rate of closed-loop material recovery vs. open-loop recycling.

5. **Energy and Water Efficiency Metrics:**

- Reduction in energy consumption per unit of production.
- Percentage of water reused in processing operations.

3. **Impact-Feasibility Matrix for Circular Strategies**

- Prioritising circular interventions based on impact and feasibility.

Impact-Feasibility Matrix for Circular Strategies

The **Impact-Feasibility Matrix** is a strategic decision-making tool that helps businesses **prioritise circular interventions** based on their potential benefits and practicality of

implementation. This structured approach ensures that companies focus on initiatives that deliver the highest impact with realistic execution pathways.

How to Use an Impact-Feasibility Matrix

The matrix is a **2x2 grid** where circular initiatives are assessed based on:

1. Impact:

- Reduction in waste, emissions, and resource use.
- Cost savings and revenue generation from circular practices.
- Social and environmental benefits, such as job creation and lower ecological footprint.

2. Feasibility:

- Technical and technological readiness.
- Financial viability and return on investment (ROI).
- Organisational and regulatory barriers.

High Feasibility	Low Feasibility
High Impact (Priority Actions) – These are initiatives with significant circular benefits and relatively easy implementation. Examples: lightweighting packaging, improving recycling processes.	Long-Term Goals – Strategies that have high potential but face technological or financial barriers. Examples: full product-service system transformation.
Quick Wins – Initiatives that are simple to implement but have moderate impact. Examples: reducing single-use materials, process optimisation.	Low-Priority Actions – Strategies with minimal impact and high difficulty in implementation. Often not pursued.

Steps to Apply the Matrix:

1. **List Potential Circular Interventions:** Gather a set of circular economy initiatives tailored to the business or value chain.
2. **Assess Their Impact:** Rank each initiative based on environmental, economic, and social impact.
3. **Evaluate Feasibility:** Consider the cost, complexity, and regulatory or technological requirements.

4. **Position on the Matrix:** Categorise interventions into quick wins, priority actions, long-term goals, or low-priority actions.
5. **Develop an Action Plan:** Prioritise high-impact, high-feasibility actions while allocating resources for longer-term strategies.

4. Key Circularity Metrics and Tools

- Material flow analysis (MFA).
- Carbon footprint and sustainability indicators.
- Tools like Ellen MacArthur Foundation's **Circulytics**.

Key Circularity Metrics and Tools

A structured approach to measuring circularity is crucial for tracking progress and identifying areas for improvement. Several analytical tools and frameworks help quantify material flows, emissions, and sustainability performance.

Material Flow Analysis (MFA)

MFA is a quantitative method used to track the **flow of materials** within a system, from input to output. It helps companies:

- Identify inefficiencies in resource use.
- Optimise material cycles by reducing waste generation.
- Improve supply chain transparency and identify opportunities for closed-loop systems.

Application in Circular Business Models:

- Identifying hotspots in the supply chain where circularity can be improved.
- Evaluating how well materials are retained within the economic system (recycling rates, secondary raw material use).
- Designing interventions to **reduce resource consumption and enhance circular loops**.

Carbon Footprint and Sustainability Indicators

Monitoring a company's **carbon footprint** and other sustainability indicators is essential for circular business models. These include:

- **CO₂ Emissions per Product Unit** – Helps track the environmental footprint of production.
- **Water and Energy Intensity** – Measures the efficiency of water and energy use.

- **Biodiversity and Land Use Impact** – Evaluates the effects of resource extraction on ecosystems.
- **Waste Diversion Rate** – Measures the proportion of waste that is diverted from landfill to recycling or reuse.

Companies can use **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)** tools to evaluate these impacts across the entire product lifecycle.

Tools for Measuring Circularity

1. Circulytics (Ellen MacArthur Foundation)

- A free assessment tool that measures a company's **circularity performance** across key business areas.
- Provides insights on circular design, material flows, and economic benefits.
- Offers benchmarks to compare circularity progress with industry peers.

2. GRI (Global Reporting Initiative) Standards for Circular Economy

- Guidelines for measuring and reporting circular performance.
- Includes indicators for waste reduction, resource efficiency, and sustainability impact.

3. ISO 14040/14044 Standards (Life Cycle Assessment Guidelines)

- Frameworks for conducting **life cycle assessments** to measure environmental impacts.

4. EU Circular Economy Monitoring Framework

- A set of **macro indicators** tracking progress toward circularity in different industries.
- Focuses on material use, waste generation, and resource efficiency.

Activity:

- **Practical Exercise:** Conduct a basic **Circularity Gap Analysis** of a selected company's business model.

7.1.3. Module 3: Designing a Circular Business Strategy

7.1.3.1. Phase 1: Business Opportunity Identification

 Objective: Define a circular business idea based on market needs and sustainability challenges.

Key Steps:**1. Identify a Market Gap or Circular Opportunity**

- Analyse existing circular trends in various sectors (e.g., agri-food, manufacturing, retail).
- Research waste streams, inefficiencies, and potential circular interventions.
- Use PESTLE Analysis (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, Environmental) to identify drivers and barriers.

2. Define the Circular Business Value Proposition

- Use the Value Proposition Canvas to determine how the business will create environmental and economic value.
- Consider different Circular Business Models, such as:
 - Product-as-a-Service (PaaS).
 - Sharing economy models.
 - Closed-loop supply chains.
 - Upcycling and waste valorisation.

 Deliverable: 1-page Circular Business Concept Statement, including a problem-solution definition and initial value proposition.

7.1.3.2. Phase 2: Market Strategy Development

 Objective: Define a clear business model and market approach.

Key Steps:**1. Develop the Business Model Canvas (BMC) for Circularity**

- Adapt Osterwalder & Pigneur's Business Model Canvas to integrate circular principles (e.g., circular value chain, take-back systems, secondary markets).
- Include Revenue Models for circularity (e.g., leasing, pay-per-use, remanufacturing fees).

2. Target Market & Customer Segments

- Use Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) analysis.
- Define key customer needs and willingness to adopt circular solutions.

3. Competitive Analysis & Differentiation

- Conduct a SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats).
- Identify direct and indirect competitors in the circular economy space.

📌 Deliverable: Circular Business Model Canvas & Market Strategy Report (3-4 pages).

7.1.3.3. Phase 3: Developing a Sustainable Supply Chain

📌 **Objective:** Design an efficient supply chain that integrates circularity principles.

Key Steps:

1. Circular Supply Chain Mapping

- Define raw material sourcing (recycled, bio-based, upcycled).
- Identify partners for industrial symbiosis.
- Map logistics, reverse logistics, and waste management strategies.

2. Sustainable Production & Distribution

- Analyse energy efficiency, waste minimisation, and eco-design principles.
- Consider digitalisation (blockchain for traceability, AI for resource optimisation).

3. Stakeholder Engagement & Partnerships

- Identify key actors in the value chain (suppliers, recyclers, logistics providers).
- Develop collaboration strategies to enhance circularity.

📌 Deliverable: Supply Chain Blueprint & Partnership Strategy (2-3 pages).

7.1.3.4. Phase 4: Environmental & Economic Impact Assessment

📌 **Objective:** Evaluate the potential environmental and economic performance of the business model.

Key Steps:

1. Circularity Gap Analysis

- Identify inefficiencies and potential improvements.
- Calculate waste reduction, energy savings, and resource efficiency gains.

2. Impact-Feasibility Matrix

- Rank proposed circular interventions based on their impact and implementation difficulty.

3. Economic Feasibility & Investment Needs

- Estimate cost structures and revenue streams.

- Identify potential funding sources (EU grants, impact investors, green financing).

📌 Deliverable: Impact Assessment Report (3-5 pages), including Circularity Metrics and Feasibility Matrix.

7.1.3.5. Final Submission & Presentation

📌 **Objective:** Present the Circular Business Innovation Project to a panel (professors, industry experts, policymakers).

Final Deliverables (Week 8-9)

📌 **Final Project Report (10-12 pages) including:**

- Circular Business Concept.
- Business Model & Market Strategy.
- Sustainable Supply Chain Design.
- Impact & Feasibility Assessment.

📌 **PowerPoint Pitch (10 slides max) for a 5-10 minute presentation.**

📌 **Q&A Session with feedback from peers and instructors.**

Assessment Criteria

Criteria	Weight (%)	Description
Innovation & Circularity	30%	How well does the business model integrate circular principles?
Feasibility & Market Readiness	25%	Is the model economically viable and competitive?
Sustainability & Impact Assessment	20%	Does the business contribute to environmental and social sustainability?
Quality of Analysis & Research	15%	Depth of market analysis, supply chain mapping, and feasibility study.
Presentation & Report Quality	10%	Clarity, structure, and persuasiveness of the final pitch and report.

Key Learning Outcomes

- ✓ Ability to design an innovative circular business model using structured frameworks.
- ✓ Application of analytical tools to assess circularity, impact, and feasibility.
- ✓ Development of strategic skills in market positioning and supply chain management.
- ✓ Experience in interdisciplinary collaboration (business, economics, sustainability).

This project provides students with hands-on experience in circular business design while fostering problem-solving, strategic thinking, and impact-driven innovation.

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7.2. HE2: Financial mechanism assessment for the circular economy: study modules

7.2.1. Introduction

The transition to a circular economy is becoming a key strategic priority for businesses, policymakers, and researchers worldwide. As industries face increasing environmental challenges and resource constraints, understanding circular economy principles and the financial mechanisms that enable their implementation is crucial. This course module is designed to provide higher education students and educators with a structured approach to understanding the financial dimension of the circular economy, equipping them with the necessary knowledge to navigate funding opportunities and integrate sustainability into business decision-making.

This material is particularly relevant for **students enrolled in business-related degrees**, including finance, economics, and management, as it explores how financial instruments can be leveraged to support circular business models. It also serves as a **valuable complementary resource for students in technical and environmental science programmes**, providing insight into how sustainability initiatives can be financed and scaled within the private and public sectors. By bridging financial knowledge with environmental and technological innovation, this module helps future professionals develop a multidisciplinary perspective on sustainability transitions.

Additionally, this resource is intended for **university instructors** seeking to introduce circular economy financing into their courses. It provides structured content that can be integrated into lectures, case studies, and discussions, helping educators incorporate circular economy financing into broader topics such as corporate sustainability, sustainable business strategies, and innovation management.

The course material is structured to gradually introduce key concepts, beginning with an overview of the circular economy, followed by an analysis of the role of funding in its implementation. It then delves into **international financial schemes**, covering European Union funding programmes, global financial institutions, and private investment mechanisms that support circular economy projects. The **national financial schemes** section focuses on a case study from the **Region of Murcia, Spain**, providing concrete examples of funding opportunities at the regional level.

By engaging with this material, students and educators will gain a comprehensive understanding of:

- The core principles of the circular economy and its relevance to sustainable development.
- The importance of financial support in implementing circular economy models.
- The different types of funding mechanisms available at international, national, and regional levels.
- Practical examples of funding schemes and how businesses and public institutions can access them.

Ultimately, this resource aims to enhance **financial literacy in circular economy projects**, helping students and professionals make informed decisions about funding strategies that promote sustainability. Whether used as part of a business curriculum or as a complementary module in technical or environmental sciences, this material provides essential insights into how financial mechanisms can drive the shift toward a more sustainable and resource-efficient economy.

1. Circular Economy Concept

The concept of circular economy has gained increasing attention as a response to the limitations of the traditional linear economic model, which follows a "take-make-dispose" approach. The origins of the circular economy concept can be traced back to different schools of thought, including industrial ecology, cradle-to-cradle design, and biomimicry, which emphasize resource efficiency, waste reduction, and regenerative practices. Over time, these ideas have been consolidated into a coherent framework that seeks to close material loops and maintain the value of products, materials, and resources for as long as possible.

The main characteristics of circular economy include designing out waste and pollution, keeping products and materials in use, and regenerating natural systems. Unlike the linear model, where economic growth is often associated with resource depletion and environmental degradation, circular economy models promote sustainability by integrating reuse, refurbishment, remanufacturing, and recycling strategies into production and consumption cycles. The implementation of circular economy practices is not only relevant

for reducing environmental impacts but also for enhancing economic resilience, improving resource security, and fostering innovation across industries.

From a sustainable development perspective, circular economy aligns with several of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly those related to responsible consumption and production, climate action, and life on land and below water. By reducing waste generation, improving resource efficiency, and promoting sustainable industrial practices, circular economy contributes to a more sustainable and regenerative economic system. Many governments, businesses, and institutions worldwide have started to integrate circular economy principles into their strategies to transition towards greener and more resource-efficient economies.

7.2.2. 2. Relevance of Funding for Implementing Circular Economy Models

One of the key enablers of circular economy implementation is the availability of adequate financial resources. Funding plays a crucial role in transforming circular business models from theoretical concepts into practical, scalable solutions. Circular economy projects often require investment in new technologies, infrastructure, and business models that differ significantly from traditional approaches. In this context, both public and private funding mechanisms are essential to drive the transition.

Public funding is often provided through government grants, subsidies, and incentives that support research, development, and implementation of circular solutions. International institutions such as the European Union, the World Bank, and national governments have introduced financial instruments to encourage circular economy initiatives. These funds help businesses and local governments overcome financial barriers that might otherwise prevent them from adopting sustainable practices.

Private funding also plays an important role, particularly for businesses looking to innovate and scale circular economy solutions. Venture capital, impact investment, and green bonds are among the financial mechanisms available for companies with sustainable business models. Private investors are increasingly recognizing the long-term economic benefits of circular business practices, which can reduce costs, improve supply chain resilience, and open new market opportunities.

A well-structured financial ecosystem that includes both public and private sources of funding is necessary to support the circular economy transition. By ensuring access to

capital, financial mechanisms can enable businesses, municipalities, and research institutions to develop innovative solutions, test new models, and expand successful practices to a larger scale. The effective allocation of funding towards circular initiatives will be essential to achieving a sustainable economic transformation.

7.2.3. 3. International Financial Schemes

Implementing circular economy projects often requires substantial financial resources, as they involve developing new business models, technologies, and infrastructure to enhance resource efficiency and waste reduction. International financial schemes play a fundamental role in supporting such initiatives by providing grants, loans, equity financing, and other financial mechanisms. These schemes come from supranational institutions such as the European Union, international financial institutions like the World Bank, and private investors specialising in sustainability-oriented projects.

The availability of financial resources from international sources ensures that circular economy projects can be scaled up beyond national or regional boundaries, benefiting from cross-border collaboration, innovation, and knowledge-sharing. Many of these schemes are structured to promote sustainability, climate resilience, and green growth, aligning closely with circular economy principles.

7.2.3.1. European Union Funds

The European Union has established multiple funding programmes to support the transition towards a circular economy across different sectors, including industry, urban planning, waste management, agriculture, and innovation. These funds help businesses, researchers, and public authorities implement sustainable practices by providing financial assistance tailored to different needs and project scales.

Horizon Europe

Horizon Europe is the EU's primary research and innovation programme for 2021-2027, with a total budget of **€95.5 billion**. It supports projects that develop new technologies, materials, and processes aligned with circular economy principles, such as waste minimisation, eco-design, and industrial symbiosis.

Horizon Europe includes several **thematic clusters** relevant to circular economy projects:

- **Cluster 4 (Digital, Industry, and Space):** Supports circular manufacturing, sustainable materials, and resource-efficient production methods.
- **Cluster 5 (Climate, Energy, and Mobility):** Funds research on energy efficiency, sustainable cities, and alternative materials to replace non-renewable resources.
- **Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environment):** Focuses on reducing waste in the food and agricultural sectors and developing bio-based alternatives.

Within Horizon Europe, the **European Innovation Council (EIC)** plays a key role in funding high-risk, high-reward innovations, including those related to circular economy. The **EIC Accelerator** specifically supports startups and SMEs working on breakthrough sustainability solutions, offering blended financing (grants and equity investments).

Additionally, the **Missions Programme** under Horizon Europe includes sustainability-focused missions, such as “**A Soil Deal for Europe**” and “**Restore our Ocean and Waters**”, which intersect with circular economy efforts by promoting regenerative practices and waste reduction.

Regional Policy Support

The EU’s **Regional Policy** provides funding to member states and regions to promote sustainable economic growth, infrastructure development, and environmental protection.

The two key funding mechanisms in this area are:

- **European Regional Development Fund (ERDF):** Finances projects that enhance sustainability, resource efficiency, and innovation in different European regions. It supports businesses and public authorities in adopting circular economy models.
- **Cohesion Fund:** Targets EU member states with lower GDP levels, focusing on waste management, energy efficiency, and green urban infrastructure to align with circular economy principles.

These funds play a critical role in **regional circular economy action plans**, helping local authorities implement waste reduction strategies, circular business models, and eco-innovation projects.

A complementary initiative is the **Just Transition Fund (JTF)**, which assists regions with economies heavily reliant on fossil fuels or resource-intensive industries in transitioning towards circular and sustainable alternatives.

Interreg Europe

Interreg Europe is a cooperation programme that helps **regional and local governments exchange knowledge and best practices** on implementing circular economy policies. It funds transnational projects that promote circular business models, waste reduction, and industrial symbiosis.

Some key initiatives supported by Interreg include:

- **CIRCE (Circular Economy Model for European Regions)**, which helps regional authorities implement circular economy strategies.
- **CESME (Circular Economy for SMEs)**, which provides support to small businesses integrating circular principles into their operations.

By promoting **cross-border cooperation**, Interreg Europe helps ensure that circular economy practices can be adapted to different regional contexts, facilitating the large-scale transition towards sustainability.

LIFE Programme

The **LIFE Programme** is the EU's funding instrument dedicated to **environmental and climate action**. It has a **budget of €5.4 billion** for 2021-2027, with a significant portion allocated to circular economy projects.

LIFE funding focuses on:

- **Waste prevention and resource efficiency:** Supporting innovative solutions to reduce material use and improve waste treatment processes.
- **Sustainable production and consumption:** Encouraging businesses to adopt eco-design, extended producer responsibility schemes, and new recycling techniques.
- **Industrial symbiosis and circular business models:** Facilitating the exchange of by-products between industries to reduce waste and enhance resource efficiency.

Successful LIFE projects serve as **demonstration cases**, proving the feasibility of circular economy models before scaling them at a national or European level.

Single Market Programme

The **Single Market Programme (SMP)** aims to enhance the competitiveness of businesses, particularly SMEs, and support sustainability efforts. The programme integrates various EU initiatives, including circular economy funding schemes.

Within the SMP, key mechanisms that support circular economy projects include:

- **Enterprise Europe Network (EEN):** Assists SMEs in accessing funding, markets, and sustainability expertise to integrate circular practices.

- **InvestEU**: Mobilises public and private investments in sustainability, including funding for green infrastructure, clean technologies, and circular business models.

InvestEU includes the **Sustainable Infrastructure Window**, which supports projects that contribute to environmental objectives, such as **waste-to-resource technologies**, **recycling plants**, and **energy-efficient production systems**.

The SMP plays a crucial role in **integrating circular economy principles into businesses**, making sustainability-driven economic growth more accessible to SMEs across Europe.

Key Takeaways

- EU funds provide **multiple financing options** for circular economy projects, including grants, loans, and equity investments.
- **Horizon Europe** supports cutting-edge research and innovation in circular economy solutions.
- **Regional Policy Funds (ERDF, Cohesion Fund, and Just Transition Fund)** finance large-scale sustainable development initiatives at national and regional levels.
- **Interreg Europe** enables cross-border collaboration and knowledge-sharing for circular economy implementation.
- **LIFE Programme** specifically targets environmental and sustainability initiatives, offering direct support to circular economy projects.
- **The Single Market Programme (SMP) and InvestEU** focus on integrating circular economy principles into business operations, especially for SMEs.

7.2.3.2. Financial Institutions

Beyond the European Union's funding programmes, several international financial institutions provide funding for circular economy projects. These institutions play a crucial role in supporting businesses, governments, and organisations that aim to transition towards more sustainable economic models. Their financing mechanisms include loans, investment guarantees, blended finance instruments, and technical assistance, helping to mobilise both public and private capital for circular economy initiatives.

Many of these institutions focus on long-term sustainability, integrating environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria into their funding decisions. Their financial products

are designed to reduce risks associated with circular investments, ensuring that sustainable business models receive the necessary financial backing to scale up and thrive.

World Bank Group

The World Bank Group is one of the most significant global financial institutions supporting sustainable development, including circular economy initiatives. It offers a wide range of funding instruments, including grants, loans, and technical assistance, primarily to governments but also to private sector actors through its affiliate institutions.

Several key programmes within the World Bank Group are particularly relevant to circular economy projects:

- The **International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD)** and the **International Development Association (IDA)** finance large-scale infrastructure projects related to waste management, resource efficiency, and sustainable urban development.
- The **International Finance Corporation (IFC)** provides funding to private companies investing in sustainable solutions, including recycling, eco-design, and circular supply chains.
- The **Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency (MIGA)** offers guarantees to investors, reducing risks associated with financing circular economy projects in developing regions.

The World Bank has increasingly integrated circular economy principles into its broader climate and sustainability agenda. Through its **Climate Investment Funds (CIF)** and **PROBLUE Initiative**, it supports countries in adopting policies that promote the circular use of resources, particularly in the blue economy and waste management sectors.

European Investment Bank

The European Investment Bank (EIB) is the European Union's financial arm, providing long-term loans and investment support for sustainable projects. It plays a leading role in financing the green transition, including circular economy initiatives, by offering both direct and intermediated financing to businesses, municipalities, and research institutions.

Some of the main financial products relevant to circular economy projects include:

- **Green loans** for businesses investing in circular business models, eco-innovation, and resource efficiency.

- **Equity financing and venture debt** for startups and SMEs working on circular solutions.
- **Project loans** for large-scale public and private initiatives promoting waste reduction, recycling infrastructure, and sustainable production methods.

The EIB has also established the **Circular Economy Initiative**, a programme dedicated to financing projects that support the transition away from a linear economic model. Under this initiative, the bank co-finances projects aligned with circular economy principles, such as industrial symbiosis, waste valorisation, and extended producer responsibility schemes.

Additionally, the EIB works in collaboration with the European Commission and other financial partners through the **InvestEU programme**, mobilising private investment for sustainable business ventures.

Joint Initiative on Circular Economy

The Joint Initiative on Circular Economy (JICE) is a collaborative effort between several European national promotional banks and the EIB to accelerate the transition to a circular economy. This initiative was launched to mobilise at least **€10 billion** between 2019 and 2023 for circular economy projects across Europe.

JICE focuses on financing projects that:

- Improve resource efficiency in production and consumption.
- Develop innovative recycling and reuse processes.
- Promote sustainable product design and waste reduction strategies.
- Enhance circular business models, such as leasing and remanufacturing.

The initiative provides both direct financing and guarantees, making it easier for businesses and local governments to secure funding for circular economy activities. By pooling resources from different financial institutions, JICE helps de-risk investments and encourages broader adoption of circular economy principles.

European Bank for Reconstruction and Development

The European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) supports the transition to sustainable and market-driven economies, particularly in Europe, Central Asia, and North Africa. It provides financial assistance to governments, municipalities, and private businesses that seek to adopt circular economy principles.

The EBRD finances circular economy projects through:

- **Direct loans** to businesses implementing sustainable production and waste reduction strategies.
- **Blended finance mechanisms**, combining grants with concessional loans to promote circular innovations.
- **Green Economy Financing Facilities (GEFFs)**, which offer credit lines to local banks for lending to businesses investing in sustainability.

A significant portion of the EBRD's funding is aligned with the **EU Green Deal** and **Paris Agreement**, supporting industries in adopting circular practices such as renewable energy integration, industrial waste valorisation, and sustainable packaging.

Key Takeaways

- International financial institutions play a crucial role in **de-risking circular economy investments**, making them more accessible to businesses and governments.
- The **World Bank Group** provides financial support through a mix of grants, loans, and guarantees, with a strong focus on emerging economies.
- The **European Investment Bank (EIB)** is one of the largest lenders for circular economy projects in Europe, offering loans, equity financing, and guarantees.
- The **Joint Initiative on Circular Economy (JICE)** pools resources from multiple European financial institutions to provide targeted financing for circular projects.
- The **European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD)** offers specialised credit lines and blended finance to support sustainability efforts in emerging economies.

7.2.4. 4. International Private Investment and Other Private Funding Opportunities

Private investment plays a fundamental role in financing circular economy initiatives, providing businesses with the necessary capital to develop and scale sustainable business models. Unlike public funding, private investment is typically driven by return on investment (ROI) expectations, making it crucial for circular economy projects to demonstrate financial viability alongside environmental and social benefits.

Several private funding mechanisms exist for circular economy initiatives, ranging from large-scale institutional investments to grassroots crowdfunding campaigns. These

mechanisms provide funding at different stages of business development, from early-stage ventures to mature companies seeking expansion.

7.2.4.1. Asset Management Firms

Asset management firms manage large pools of capital on behalf of institutional investors, high-net-worth individuals, pension funds, and sovereign wealth funds. These firms allocate investments across various asset classes, including equities, bonds, real estate, and alternative investments such as impact investing and green bonds.

In recent years, many asset management firms have integrated **environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria** into their investment strategies, leading to increased funding opportunities for circular economy businesses. The rise of **sustainable investment funds** and **thematic investment strategies** focused on resource efficiency, waste management, and sustainable production processes has created new channels for financing circular projects.

Some key examples of asset management firms with circular economy-focused investment portfolios include:

- **BlackRock's Circular Economy Fund:** This fund focuses on investing in companies that support a transition to a circular economy, including recycling, sustainable packaging, and circular business models.
- **RobecoSAM Circular Economy Equities Fund:** This fund targets businesses with circular economy strategies, particularly in waste management, material reuse, and sustainable resource extraction.
- **BNP Paribas Circular Economy Fund:** A thematic investment fund that allocates capital to businesses developing innovative circular solutions across industries.

Asset managers typically invest in publicly traded companies or private equity-backed enterprises, making them more relevant for established businesses with proven revenue models rather than startups in their early stages.

7.2.4.2. Investment Funds

Investment funds provide pooled capital from multiple investors to support businesses and projects, with a growing number focusing specifically on circular economy innovations.

These funds can take various forms, including **venture capital funds, private equity funds, and impact investment funds.**

- **Venture capital funds** target high-growth startups, often focusing on early-stage companies with innovative circular solutions. Venture capitalists provide not only financial support but also strategic guidance, helping companies scale and commercialize their technologies.
- **Private equity funds** invest in more established businesses, often restructuring operations, scaling production, or facilitating acquisitions to enhance circular business models.
- **Impact investment funds** specifically allocate capital to businesses generating positive environmental and social impacts while maintaining financial returns. These funds often align with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly those related to responsible consumption and production.

Several notable investment funds dedicated to circular economy businesses include:

- **Circularity Capital:** A venture capital firm exclusively focused on circular economy businesses, investing in companies that create closed-loop systems and reduce resource consumption.
- **Blue Horizon Fund:** Specialises in funding companies that develop sustainable food systems, particularly plant-based and waste-reducing technologies.
- **Breakthrough Energy Ventures:** Backed by Bill Gates and other investors, this fund targets innovative technologies that contribute to sustainability and circular economy practices.

Many of these funds work in collaboration with public financing schemes, leveraging blended finance structures where public grants de-risk private investment.

7.2.4.3. Crowdfunding

Crowdfunding provides an alternative approach to financing circular economy projects by raising capital from a large number of individual investors or donors, often through online platforms. This method is particularly useful for startups, social enterprises, and small businesses that may struggle to secure traditional financing.

There are three main types of crowdfunding relevant to circular economy initiatives:

- **Reward-based crowdfunding:** Investors contribute money in exchange for a non-financial reward, such as early access to products. This is common for consumer-facing circular economy products, such as reusable packaging innovations or upcycled fashion brands. Platforms: Kickstarter, Indiegogo.
- **Equity crowdfunding:** Investors receive shares in the company in return for their financial contribution. This approach is useful for startups seeking to raise capital without relying on traditional venture capital. Platforms: Crowdcube, Seedrs.
- **Debt-based crowdfunding (peer-to-peer lending):** Businesses receive loans from individual investors, repaying them with interest over time. This can be an alternative to bank loans, particularly for circular economy businesses with high upfront costs. Platforms: Funding Circle, Kiva.

Crowdfunding has proven to be an effective tool for financing circular economy businesses, particularly those with strong consumer appeal. Successful crowdfunding campaigns can also serve as a market validation tool, demonstrating demand for sustainable products and services before scaling up production.

Key Takeaways

- **Asset management firms** provide capital for larger, more established companies, often through sustainable investment funds that integrate circular economy principles.
- **Investment funds**, including venture capital, private equity, and impact investment funds, play a crucial role in supporting both early-stage and mature circular economy businesses.
- **Crowdfunding** offers an accessible financing route for startups and small enterprises, allowing them to raise capital directly from consumers and investors while validating market demand.

7.2.5. 5. National Financial Schemes – The Region of Murcia

The Region of Murcia offers various public and private funding opportunities to support circular economy initiatives, with mechanisms available for businesses, research institutions, and entrepreneurs. These financial schemes aim to encourage innovation, sustainability, and economic transformation by providing grants, loans, and investment opportunities tailored to circular business models.

This section outlines the key financial resources available in Murcia, focusing on public grants, research and development (R&D) support, and banking sector initiatives.

7.2.5.1. Grant Programmes from INFO Murcia and Regional Government of Murcia

The Instituto de Fomento de la Región de Murcia (INFO Murcia) plays a central role in supporting business growth and economic development in the region. It provides financial assistance for companies, startups, and entrepreneurs, offering direct grants and facilitating access to European funding opportunities. The **Regional Government of Murcia** also complements these efforts by implementing funding schemes aligned with sustainability, green growth, and circular economy objectives.

Key grant programmes supporting circular economy initiatives include:

- **Sustainability Vouchers:** This programme provides financial support for businesses conducting carbon footprint calculations (at both company and product levels), water footprint assessments, and eco-design evaluations. The funding covers the costs of implementing resource-efficient and circular economy strategies.
- **Energy Efficiency Grants:** These grants target businesses aiming to reduce their energy consumption and environmental impact. Funding is provided for energy audits, efficiency upgrades, and the adoption of renewable energy solutions.
- **Eco-innovation and Circular Economy Grants:** This initiative funds businesses developing circular products and services, supporting projects that incorporate waste reduction, recycling, and sustainable materials into their production processes.
- **Support for SME Internationalisation:** While not exclusively circular economy-focused, these grants help businesses expand into international markets, particularly those offering green and sustainable solutions.

Additionally, Murcia's regional authorities work closely with **European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF)** to channel resources toward green transition projects, supporting businesses in complying with EU sustainability policies.

7.2.5.2. R&D Support

Research and development play a crucial role in advancing circular economy solutions, particularly in sectors such as waste management, sustainable agriculture, and resource-

efficient manufacturing. Murcia has several R&D funding schemes designed to support innovation in these fields.

Key R&D funding sources in the region include:

- **INFO Murcia R&D Grants:** These grants are available for research projects that promote sustainable practices, improve industrial efficiency, and develop new circular technologies. They are open to SMEs, research centres, and universities.
- **Technology Centres and University Research Support:** Murcia's **technological institutes**, such as CETENMA (Technological Centre for Energy and Environment), CTNC (National Centre for Food Technology and Safety), and CETEC (Centre for Plastic Technologies), offer funding and research collaboration opportunities for businesses working on circular economy innovations. Additionally, **Murcia's public universities (UMU and UPCT)** provide funding opportunities through innovation and technology transfer programmes.
- **CDTI (Centre for the Development of Industrial Technology) Support:** Nationally managed but accessible in Murcia, CDTI provides grants and soft loans for R&D projects focused on industrial innovation and sustainability. Businesses can apply for funding to develop new processes, materials, and business models in the circular economy sector.
- **European R&D Funding Facilitation:** INFO Murcia assists businesses and research centres in applying for European funding opportunities, including Horizon Europe and Interreg projects that promote circular economy innovation.

7.2.5.3. Banks in the Region of Murcia

The banking sector in Murcia plays an essential role in financing circular economy projects, offering loans, green financing, and impact investment products. Several financial institutions have developed funding instruments specifically aimed at businesses transitioning toward sustainable practices.

Key banks supporting circular economy initiatives in Murcia include:

- **Cajamar Cooperative Group:** As a cooperative bank with strong ties to the **agri-food sector**, Cajamar provides specialised financing solutions for businesses adopting circular production methods. It has also secured funding from the **European Investment Bank (EIB)** to support green investment projects, particularly in rural and

agricultural sectors. Cajamar's financial products include sustainability-linked loans and funding for eco-innovation initiatives.

- **CaixaBank:** This bank offers a range of **green financing options**, including loans linked to sustainability performance indicators, green loans for renewable energy and waste reduction projects, and eco-financing for SMEs investing in resource-efficient solutions. CaixaBank also provides advisory services to help businesses align with ESG criteria.
- **BBVA:** BBVA supports circular economy initiatives through **green mortgages, sustainable business loans, and impact investment funds**. Its financing schemes prioritise projects in renewable energy, recycling, and resource efficiency. BBVA also collaborates with research institutions and public entities to fund large-scale sustainability projects.
- **Unicaja Banco:** With a growing commitment to sustainability, Unicaja offers **eco-efficiency loans** for businesses investing in green technologies, circular economy initiatives, and waste management solutions. It also provides investment funds focusing on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria.

Key Takeaways

- Murcia provides **public funding opportunities** through INFO Murcia and the regional government, with specific grants for circular economy initiatives.
- The region supports **R&D and innovation** in circular economy through university research programmes, technology centres, and national funding schemes.
- Several **banks in Murcia** offer tailored financing solutions, including **green loans, sustainability-linked investment funds, and impact financing options** for circular economy businesses.

7.3. HE3: Implementing Circular Economy in the agrifood sector: a case study approach

7.3.1. Introduction

The circular economy is emerging as a key model for sustainable industrial transformation, particularly in sectors that generate large amounts of waste, such as the agri-food industry. Traditionally, food production and processing have relied on linear economic models, where resources are extracted, used, and discarded. However, increasing environmental pressures and regulatory demands are driving a shift towards **circular practices**, where waste is minimised, and by-products are upcycled into valuable resources.

This case study explores how the **Agro2Circular (A2C) project** has implemented technological solutions to recover and transform agri-food waste into high-value materials. The initiative integrates **innovative extraction technologies, biotechnology applications, and industrial collaborations**, demonstrating a **multi-sectoral approach** to circular economy implementation.

Beyond the direct stakeholders in the agri-food sector, the case study also highlights the **role of supporting industries**, such as recyclers, biotechnology companies, and cosmetics manufacturers. These **non-food** sectors contribute expertise and infrastructure to maximise resource efficiency and create **new market opportunities for upcycled materials**.

Through this case study, students will explore:

- How companies can implement **circular economy principles** in the agri-food industry.
- The role of **technological innovation** in waste valorisation.
- The collaboration between different industries to **enhance sustainability**.
- The challenges and opportunities of **scaling up circular solutions**.

The following sections provide a structured guide for educators to use this case study in the classroom, facilitating **critical thinking, problem-solving, and application of circular economy concepts**.

7.3.2. Teacher's Guide

7.3.2.1. Objectives of the Case Study

This case study is designed to help students:

1. Understand how **circular economy principles** can be applied in the agri-food industry.
2. Analyse the **technological processes** used to transform waste into valuable products.
3. Identify **cross-sectoral collaborations** that support circular business models.
4. Evaluate the **scalability and economic viability** of circular solutions.
5. Discuss the **barriers and policy frameworks** influencing circular economy adoption.

7.3.2.2. Target Audience

This case study is suited for students in:

- **Business and management** (circular business models, sustainability strategies).
- **Industrial and chemical engineering** (process optimisation, technology scale-up).
- **Biotechnology and chemistry** (waste valorisation, bio-based innovations).

7.3.2.3. Implementation Formats

This case study can be used in different educational settings:

- **Classroom Discussion:** Analysing the case study in small groups and presenting insights.
- **Problem-Solving Workshop:** Designing strategies for improving the circular processes described.
- **Industry Simulation:** Assigning students different stakeholder roles (e.g., agri-food company, biotech firm, regulator) and having them negotiate solutions.
- **Individual/Group Assignment:** Writing a report evaluating the business and technical feasibility of the A2C approach.

7.3.2.4. Suggested Activities

1. **Understanding Circular Economy in Practice**
 - Before reading the case study, students should research **basic circular economy concepts**.
 - Discussion: How does the circular model differ from traditional waste management approaches?

2. Technical and Business Feasibility Analysis

- Students will analyse the **technological innovations** in A2C and discuss their feasibility at a commercial scale.
- Task: Identify potential **barriers to upscaling** (e.g., financial, technical, regulatory).

3. Cross-Sector Collaboration Mapping

- Task: Identify the key players involved in the A2C project.
- Discussion: Why is collaboration between the agri-food, biotech, and recycling industries necessary?

4. Policy and Market Impact Evaluation

- Students will research relevant **EU and national policies** supporting circular economy initiatives.
- Task: Propose policy recommendations to enhance circular economy adoption in the agri-food sector.

5. Strategic Business Development Exercise

- Students will develop a **business proposal** for a startup that uses upcycled agrifood waste to produce a new product.
- Deliverable: A **pitch presentation** outlining the product, market potential, and sustainability impact.

7.3.2.5. Assessment and Discussion Questions

1. What are the key **circular economy principles** applied in the A2C project?
2. How do **extraction and stabilisation technologies** contribute to waste valorisation?
3. What challenges could arise when **scaling up** these solutions to an industrial level?
4. How can biotechnology support **sustainable material recovery** in the agri-food sector?
5. In what ways can **cross-sector partnerships** enhance circular economy adoption?
6. What policy incentives could help **companies transition to circular models**?

7.3.3. Case study: the A2C solution

The **Agro2Circular (A2C) project** is an ambitious European initiative under the **Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation Programme (GA No. 101036838)**, aimed at developing

territorial circular solutions for upcycling waste generated by the agrifood industry. The project focuses on two main types of waste streams in the **Murcia region, Spain**:

1. **Multilayer-multi-material metallised plastic films**, widely used in food packaging but difficult to recycle.
2. **Fruit and vegetable waste**, generated in large quantities by the agrifood sector.

The project integrates innovative technological solutions to recover valuable resources from these waste streams, transforming them into secondary raw materials that can be reintroduced into the industrial cycle. By implementing multiple pilot-scale demonstrators (DEMOS), Agro2Circular showcases practical applications of circular economy principles in real-world industrial settings, proving the feasibility of waste valorisation at a territorial level.

2. Objectives of Agro2Circular

The primary goals of Agro2Circular are:

- To develop and demonstrate upcycling technologies for difficult-to-recycle plastics and organic waste from the agrifood industry.
- To enhance resource efficiency by creating high-value secondary raw materials for reintroduction into industrial processes.
- To support the transition towards a circular economy through advanced traceability and data integration systems for efficient waste management.
- To reduce the environmental footprint of the agrifood industry by minimising waste sent to landfills and optimising the use of raw materials.
- To foster industrial collaboration by creating regional circular economy models that can be replicated in other European territories.

3. Technological innovations and pilot demonstrators

Agro2Circular integrates multiple cutting-edge technologies into a series of **DEMOS**, each focused on a different aspect of waste upcycling and resource recovery. These demonstrators showcase novel processes and technological advancements aimed at creating **sustainable and profitable circular economy models**.

3.1 DEMO 1: Upcycling multilayer/multi-material metallised packaging

One of the greatest challenges in plastic recycling is the aseptic multilayer packaging, widely used in the food industry. This type of packaging consists of multiple layers of plastics and aluminium, making it difficult to separate and recycle. The Agro2Circular project has developed a multi-step recycling process to overcome these challenges:

- Collection, cutting, washing, and drying: Using the GWC recycling process, waste is prepared for further separation.
- Optical sorting technology: The IRIS system identifies and separates metallised from non-metallised plastic fractions using advanced spectroscopic techniques (NIR-HSI and LIBS spectroscopy).
- Delamination technology: The saperatec process efficiently removes aluminium from plastics and separates different plastic layers, making them suitable for reintroduction into packaging production.
- Enzymatic degradation: Epoch Biodesign has developed engineered enzymes that break down certain plastic fractions into their monomers and oligomers, which can be repurposed in bioprocesses.

This approach enables the recovery of polyethylene (PE), polyethylene-amide (PE-PA), and polyethylene-ethylene vinyl alcohol (PE-EVOH), which can be reused as secondary raw materials in the packaging industry, reducing reliance on virgin materials.

3.2 DEMO 2: Biotechnological conversion of plastic waste and organic residues into cosmetic ingredients

This demonstrator focuses on converting enzymatically degraded PET waste and fruit and vegetable residues into valuable cosmetic ingredients, using advanced microbial biotechnology processes:

- Microbial biotransformation of ethylene glycol (EG) into glycolic acid (GA): The University of Milano-Bicocca has demonstrated that specific yeast strains can efficiently convert EG into GA, a key ingredient in cosmetic formulations.
- Microbial oil production: Oleaginous yeast species can accumulate microbial oils when grown on fruit and vegetable waste. These oils serve as sustainable alternatives to fossil-derived and plant-based oils commonly used in the cosmetics industry.
- Green solvent extraction: Environmentally friendly solvents are used for oil extraction, ensuring that the process aligns with circular economy principles and minimises environmental impact.

3.3 DEMOs 3 & 4: Recovery of bioactive compounds and dietary fibres from fruit and vegetable waste

The industrialisation of natural product extraction from fruit and vegetable waste represents a crucial step in achieving sustainability within the agrifood sector. Agro2Circular has developed and upscaled two green extraction technologies for the recovery of bioactive compounds and dietary fibres:

- Route 1: Enzymatic extraction (EAE), developed by CTNC and CITROMIL, using cellulase to release phenolic compounds and dietary fibres from waste materials such as artichoke, lemon, broccoli, apple, and grape.
- Route 2: Microwave-assisted extraction (MAE), developed by SSICA and DOMCA, which applies microwaves and enzymatic pre-treatment to improve the efficiency of polyphenol extraction.

These technologies have demonstrated:

- High extraction efficiency, with phenolic extracts reaching purities of up to 70%.
- Significant dietary fibre recovery, with purities of up to 75% in dry matter.
- Successful stabilisation techniques, ensuring the longevity and usability of recovered compounds in nutraceutical, food, and cosmetic applications.

However, challenges such as energy-intensive stabilisation processes and water consumption during fibre purification remain key areas for further optimisation.

3.4 DEMO 5: Production of biodegradable PHBV plastics from agrifood waste

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biodegradable bioplastics that can replace conventional fossil-based plastics. Agro2Circular has focused on producing polyhydroxybutyrate-co-hydroxyvalerate (PHBV) from organic waste using the microorganism *Haloferax mediterranei*. The process:

- Uses lemon and apple waste as a carbon source for microbial fermentation.
- Produces biodegradable plastics that can be used in sustainable packaging solutions.
- Ensures eco-friendly extraction techniques using chlorine-free solvents.

3.5 DEMO 10: Data integration system for waste traceability and management

To ensure the traceability and transparency of waste streams, Agro2Circular has developed a data integration system (DIS) that enables:

- Blockchain-based traceability to track waste from its source to its final reuse.
- Machine learning-based waste management recommendations, optimising environmental, economic, and social impacts.

- Digital product passports (DPPs) that allow companies to identify the composition and sustainability credentials of their materials.

This system ensures regulatory compliance, enhances material circularity, and prevents greenwashing by providing verifiable sustainability claims.

The A2C Demos result from the application of the following technologies:

7.3.3.1. Technologies for Recycling Organic Agrifood Waste

The Agro2Circular (A2C) project implements innovative technologies to optimise the recovery, purification, and stabilisation of valuable compounds from agrifood waste, focusing on fruit and vegetable residues such as citrus, apple, grape, cauliflower, broccoli, and artichoke. These technologies aim to enhance the efficiency, scalability, and sustainability of the extraction process, ensuring that recovered compounds can be integrated into food, nutraceutical, and cosmetic applications.

1. Classification & Conditioning of Agrifood Waste

Before extraction, agrifood waste undergoes pre-treatment to improve processing efficiency.

These steps include:

- Refrigeration or freezing upon reception to maintain quality before processing.
- Mechanical size reduction to enhance mass transfer and increase extraction efficiency. Agrifood waste is shredded into 20mm x 20mm cubes for homogenisation.
- Separation of waste fractions (when required) to ensure that different waste streams are processed according to their specific bioactive content.

2. Green Extraction Technologies

The project has prioritised the use of eco-friendly and efficient extraction technologies, avoiding hazardous solvents and maximising the yield and purity of bioactive compounds.

The most promising methods include:

2.1 Green Solvent Extraction

The project has developed solvent-based extraction routes using alternatives to conventional chemical solvents, including:

- **Natural Deep Eutectic Solvents (NADES):** A class of green solvents derived from natural compounds, designed to replace toxic organic solvents while maintaining high extraction yields.

- **Subcritical Water Extraction (SWE):** A process that uses water at high temperatures and pressures (but below its critical point) to act as a solvent for polyphenol and fibre extraction, eliminating the need for chemical reagents.
- **Enzyme-Assisted Extraction (EAE):** Uses enzymatic hydrolysis (e.g., cellulases and pectinases) to break down cell walls and release bioactive compounds more efficiently.

2.2 Assisted Extraction Technologies

To further optimise efficiency, purity, and sustainability, the project has integrated assisted extraction techniques that enhance solvent penetration and bioactive release, including:

- **Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction (UAE):** Uses ultrasonic waves to create microbubbles that disrupt plant cell walls, improving solvent penetration and increasing extraction yields. This technique significantly reduces processing time and solvent consumption.
- **Microwave-Assisted Extraction (MAE):** Applies microwave radiation to rapidly heat the sample, leading to faster and more efficient extraction of phenolic compounds and fibres. The project demonstrated that microwave-assisted enzymatic extraction (MAE-EAE) delivers the highest extraction yields and purity for phenolic compounds.

Each of these technologies has been optimised for specific agrifood residues to ensure maximum recovery of bioactive compounds.

3. Purification & Stabilisation of Extracts

Once bioactive compounds are extracted, they undergo purification and stabilisation processes to ensure they meet industrial standards for use in food, nutraceutical, and cosmetic applications.

3.1. Purification Technologies

Purification enhances extract purity and bioactive concentration, removing unwanted components that may affect quality or safety. The following techniques have been applied:

- **Ultrafiltration (UF):** A membrane-based process used to separate bioactive compounds from unwanted residues, achieving higher purity levels.
- **Adsorption & Desorption with Resins:** Selective adsorption resins (e.g., Diaion HP20) are used to isolate and concentrate polyphenols, improving their antioxidant capacity and stability.

- **Oxidation & Washing Treatments:** Used to purify dietary fibres, removing organic residues that may affect colour, taste, or odour.

3.2. Stabilisation Techniques

To ensure extracts maintain their functionality, safety, and shelf-life, the project has tested various stabilisation methods:

- **Freeze-Drying (Lyophilisation):** Used for liquid extracts rich in phenolic compounds, preserving bioactivity while ensuring a longer shelf life.
- **Microencapsulation:** A technique that coats bioactive compounds with a protective layer, improving stability against oxidation and degradation. This is particularly useful for polyphenol extracts intended for nutraceuticals.
- **Dehydration (Hot-Air Drying):** Applied to fibre-rich extracts, reducing moisture content to below 5%, making them suitable for incorporation into food products with high-fibre claims.

3.3. Key Achievements & Industrial Viability

The technologies applied in Agro2Circular have demonstrated:

- **High extraction efficiency:** Polyphenol extracts with $\geq 70\%$ purity and dietary fibres with $\geq 75\%$ purity in dry matter.
- **Scalability potential:** The developed methods have been successfully scaled to pilot level, with plans for industrial validation.
- **Sustainability benefits:** Reduction of toxic solvents, lower energy consumption, and improved waste valorisation align with circular economy principles.
- **Industrial applications:** The recovered extracts are suitable for use in food (e.g., enriched juices, fibre-enhanced products), nutraceuticals (e.g., antioxidant supplements), and cosmetics (e.g., polyphenol-based skincare products).

7.3.3.2. Scaling and Upcycling of Recycled Agrifood Materials

The Agro2Circular (A2C) project has not only developed cutting-edge technologies for the valorisation of agrifood waste but has also taken a strategic approach to scaling up these processes. This section details the methodologies used to transition from laboratory-scale research to semi-industrial pilot implementation, ensuring that agrifood waste upcycling is viable, efficient, and ready for replication at an industrial level.

1. From Laboratory to Pilot Scale: Optimising Upcycling Routes

The transition from lab-scale extraction methods to pilot-scale processes was designed to ensure that the technologies developed under WP2 could be efficiently upscaled and implemented in real-world settings. This transition followed a systematic approach:

1. Small-scale formulation and validation (WP4.1)
2. Pilot-scale upscaling of extraction processes (WP4.2, WP4.3)
3. Validation of pilot-scale extractions (WP4.4)
4. pilot industrial demonstrations (WP6)

This approach ensures that only the most effective and sustainable methodologies move forward, reducing technological risk and optimising resource efficiency.

2. Upcycling Processes: Key Technologies in Pilot-Scale Implementation

At the pilot stage, A2C focused on optimising two major extraction routes for agrifood waste valorisation, each addressing different waste streams and bioactive compounds.

2.1 Route 1: Enzymatic and Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction (EAE + UAE)

This route focused on recovering fibres and polyphenolic compounds from lemon, artichoke, apple, and grape waste. The key processes involved:

- Enzymatic hydrolysis to break down cell walls and release target compounds.
- Ultrasound-assisted extraction to enhance mass transfer and reduce processing time.
- Purification using resins to isolate high-purity phenolic compounds.
- Freeze-drying and dehydration to stabilise the final extracts.

Key Outcomes:

- Polyphenol purity reached $\geq 70\%$, particularly in artichoke and grape extracts.
- Fibre extraction yields exceeded 75%, making them suitable for food fortification.
- The use of oxidising agents in fibre purification improved colour and sensory properties.

2.2 Route 2: Microwave-Assisted Extraction (MAE)

This route targeted the extraction of polyphenols and soluble fibres from lemon and artichoke waste using a custom-built microwave extractor designed for large-scale operations.

- Combined enzymatic and microwave treatment optimised the breakdown of plant cell structures.
- Hydroalcoholic green solvents (ethanol + water) minimised environmental impact.

- Ultrafiltration and resin-based purification ensured high extract purity.

Key Outcomes:

- Higher polyphenol concentrations compared to enzymatic treatment alone.
- Increased antioxidant capacity in lemon extracts, likely due to organic acids and flavonoids.
- Successful pilot-scale validation, paving the way for full-scale implementation in WP6.

3. Scaling Challenges and Optimisation Strategies

As the extraction routes were scaled up, several operational challenges emerged, which were systematically addressed to ensure efficiency and feasibility.

3.1 Equipment Adaptations and Facility Conditioning

For the MAE process, a 120-litre microwave extractor was developed, requiring significant facility adaptations at DMC's pilot plant:

- Thermal and acoustic insulation was installed to accommodate high-power microwave and ultrasound operations.
- Temperature-controlled environment was established to prevent overheating of electrical components.
- Custom-designed mechanical stirring and unloading systems were added for better process control.

These modifications ensured that the microwave system could operate efficiently at a semi-industrial scale, maintaining reproducibility and quality.

3.2 Water and Energy Consumption Optimisation

One of the main challenges in pilot-scale implementation was reducing resource consumption, particularly:

- High water usage in fibre washing → Implemented a counter-current washing system to reduce water consumption.
- Energy-intensive stabilisation methods → Identified opportunities to bypass freeze-drying when extracts could be used directly in food formulations.

These improvements significantly enhanced the sustainability and cost-effectiveness of the processes.

3.3 Validation of Extracts for Industrial Applications

To ensure that the extracts met regulatory and industrial standards, comprehensive characterisation was performed on both fibre and phenolic extracts:

- Microbiological testing confirmed absence of pathogens (Salmonella, Listeria, E. coli).
- Chemical composition analysis verified that extracted compounds retained their bioactivity and purity.
- Quality assessment for food and nutraceutical applications demonstrated compliance with EU food safety regulations.

4. Industrial Applications and Market Readiness

Following successful pilot-scale validation, the upcycled agrifood materials have demonstrated significant potential for industrial adoption across multiple sectors:

1. Food Industry:

- Fibre extracts can be incorporated into functional foods, such as high-fibre veggie burgers, enriched juices, and dietary supplements.
- Polyphenol extracts serve as natural antioxidants in food preservation.

2. Nutraceutical Industry:

- Polyphenol-rich extracts can be used in dietary supplements with proven antioxidant activity.
- Extracts from lemon, artichoke, and grape have shown potential as alternatives to synthetic antioxidants in commercial nutraceutical formulations.

3. Cosmetic Industry:

- Phenolic compounds with high antioxidant capacity are suitable for skin-care formulations, although further studies are required to refine stability and efficacy.

7.3.3.3. Integration of Circular Solutions for Agrifood and Plastic Waste Valorisation

The Agro2Circular (A2C) project advances a holistic approach to waste valorisation by integrating innovative technologies for both agrifood and plastic waste streams. While previous sections have detailed the technological developments in organic waste upcycling and bioactive compound extraction, this section highlights the convergence of these solutions with the sorting and recycling of multilayer plastic residues. The integration of these

processes ensures that both organic and plastic waste are recovered efficiently, contributing to the overall sustainability and circularity of the agrifood sector.

1. Cross-Sectoral Integration of Waste Valorisation Technologies

A key objective of A2C is to establish synergies between the recovery of bioactive compounds from agrifood waste and the recycling of multilayer plastic residues. To achieve this, the project has developed complementary strategies that align organic waste treatment with advanced plastic sorting and recycling techniques. The following cross-sectoral integrations have been implemented:

- **Shared Pre-Treatment Infrastructures:** Agrifood waste conditioning and plastic waste shredding facilities have been co-located to optimise resource efficiency and minimise logistical costs.
- **Optimised Separation of Organic and Plastic Fractions:** Advanced sorting technologies, including optical detection and enzymatic delamination, ensure that plastics contaminated with organic residues are effectively cleaned and processed.
- **Coordinated Extraction and Purification Processes:** The purification of bioactive compounds from agrifood waste aligns with the decontamination and modification of recycled plastics, enabling their use in food-safe applications.

2. Valorisation of Organic By-Products in Plastic Recycling

One of the most promising intersections between agrifood and plastic waste valorisation is the recovery and reuse of organic by-products in plastic recycling processes. Within A2C, the following advancements have been achieved:

- **Organic Fraction Recovery for Bioplastic Production:** Wastewater generated during plastic washing contains organic matter with potential for biopolymer synthesis, particularly Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA). This represents a novel approach to transforming agrifood residues into biodegradable plastics.
- **Mitigation of Microplastic Contamination in Wastewater:** Pilot-scale ultrafiltration and electrocoagulation have been tested to remove microplastics from water used in plastic washing, reducing environmental pollution and ensuring cleaner processes.
- **Use of Recovered Polyphenols in Plastic Formulation:** Extracted polyphenols from citrus, artichoke, and grape residues exhibit antioxidant properties that could enhance the stability of recycled plastic products, extending their lifespan and reducing degradation.

3. Pilot-Scale Validation and Industrial Readiness

To ensure the feasibility of integrating agrifood and plastic waste valorisation, A2C has initiated pilot-scale validation of these processes. The main activities include:

- **Demonstration of Plastic Delamination and Enzymatic Modification:** The separation of aluminum-plastic composites through enzymatic treatment has been optimised to facilitate the recycling of multi-layer plastic residues.
- **Implementation of a Counter-Current Washing System:** Reducing water and energy consumption in plastic decontamination while ensuring the removal of agrochemical residues.
- **Assessment of Industrial Applications:** Extracted fibres and polyphenols have been tested for food, nutraceutical, and plastic applications, while recycled plastics have been evaluated for use in packaging, cosmetics, and biodegradable polymer formulations.

4. Sustainability and Circular Economy Contributions

The integration of agrifood and plastic waste valorisation within A2C aligns with the principles of circular economy by:

- **Closing Nutrient and Material Loops:** Converting waste into valuable bioactive compounds, functional fibres, and recyclable plastics.
- **Enhancing Resource Efficiency:** Optimising energy and water use across both agrifood and plastic processing chains.
- **Reducing Environmental Footprint:** Minimising landfilling and greenhouse gas emissions through innovative waste recovery technologies.

7.4. HE4: Introductory coursework on governance in the circular economy

7.4.1. About this course

This course provides a structured and comprehensive examination of governance in the circular economy, offering insights into key policies, regulatory frameworks, and governance models that facilitate the transition from a linear to a circular economic system. It is designed as an academic resource for legal and political science students, with adaptations for those studying environmental science, and aims to equip learners with the conceptual and analytical tools needed to understand and evaluate circular economy governance.

Through coursework, written modules, and practical research activities, this material enables students to explore best practices in governance and assess the effectiveness of public policies in fostering circular economy initiatives. The course also examines how multi-level governance, stakeholder engagement, financial mechanisms, and cultural and political contexts shape circular economy policies across different regions and sectors, with a particular focus on the agri-food industry.

7.4.2. Objectives of this course

The course is structured to achieve the following objectives:

- **Introduce key governance concepts** in the context of the circular economy, differentiating between hierarchical, network, and polycentric governance models.
- **Explore legal and regulatory frameworks** that facilitate or hinder circular economy adoption, with a focus on waste management, extended producer responsibility (EPR), and resource efficiency policies.
- **Examine financial mechanisms and incentives**, such as green subsidies, tax benefits, and circular investment funds, that support circular business models.
- **Assess the role of public and private actors** in the governance of the circular economy, analysing collaboration between governments, businesses, and civil society.
- **Investigate best practices in circular economy governance**, drawing from case studies of countries that have successfully implemented circular policies, such as Finland and the Netherlands.

- **Evaluate policy effectiveness**, using governance indicators and impact assessment methods to measure the success of circular economy initiatives.
- **Encourage practical application** through research-based activities where students analyse governance models, policy frameworks, and institutional arrangements supporting the circular economy.

7.4.3. Intended audience and usage

This course is designed for **higher education institutions and instructors** teaching **legal, political, and environmental science disciplines**. It serves as a structured teaching tool that can be incorporated into university curricula, offering:

- **Lecture material** for courses on governance, sustainability, and environmental policy.
- **Coursework assignments**, enabling students to develop analytical skills through case studies, policy evaluations, and comparative governance analysis.
- **Research activities**, guiding students in conducting independent research on best practices in circular economy governance.
- **Assessment tools**, including discussion prompts and policy evaluation frameworks to support critical thinking and policy analysis.

By integrating theoretical concepts with **practical applications**, this material provides students with a **solid foundation in circular economy governance** while fostering their ability to critically assess policies and propose innovative solutions for sustainable development. This course material is intended to be **flexible and adaptable**, allowing instructors to tailor its content according to their specific teaching objectives and the academic level of their students.

7.4.4. Course on Governance in the Circular Economy

7.4.4.1. Introduction to the circular economy

The circular economy is an economic model that aims to reduce waste and maximise resource efficiency by implementing strategies such as reuse, recycling, and regeneration of products and materials within a closed-loop system. This approach contrasts with the traditional linear economy, which follows a “take, make, use, and dispose” model. The circular economy seeks to extend the life cycle of materials and products through strategies

such as eco-design, industrial symbiosis, and waste valorisation, with the overarching objective of minimising environmental impact and fostering long-term sustainability.

The fundamental principles of the circular economy include:

- **Preservation and enhancement of natural capital**, ensuring efficient resource management and the adoption of renewable energy sources.
- **Optimisation of resource use** by promoting maintenance, repair, and reuse of products.
- **Improvement of system efficiency**, reducing negative externalities and ensuring closed loops of material and energy flows in production processes.

1.1 Differences between the linear and circular economy

The linear economy is based on a production and consumption model where natural resources are extracted, processed, consumed, and ultimately discarded. This model presents several limitations, including resource overexploitation, environmental pollution, and excessive waste generation. Moreover, it creates a strong dependency on finite and increasingly scarce raw materials.

Conversely, the circular economy fosters a system in which materials are continuously reused and recycled, preventing waste generation. Key strategies for this transition include the servitisation of products, the extension of product life cycles, and the increased use of secondary raw materials in industrial processes, thereby reducing reliance on virgin materials and mitigating environmental pollution.

1.2 Economic, environmental, and social benefits

The adoption of circular economy principles generates multiple benefits across economic, environmental, and social dimensions:

- **Economic benefits:** Enhances business competitiveness, fosters innovation, and creates new employment opportunities in sectors such as recycling, sustainable production, and remanufacturing.
- **Environmental benefits:** Reduces the extraction of natural resources, minimises waste generation, and lowers carbon emissions, thereby contributing to environmental sustainability.
- **Social benefits:** Supports social equity by generating employment in emerging sectors, improves quality of life by reducing pollution, and strengthens community resilience to environmental and economic challenges.

7.4.4.2.2. Governance and its role in the circular economy

2.1 Defining governance in the circular economy

Governance in the circular economy refers to the mechanisms, policies, and regulations established to manage and coordinate the transition towards circular production and consumption models. This governance framework involves multiple actors, including governments, the private sector, civil society, and international organisations, all of whom play a role in shaping and implementing policies that support circularity.

2.2 Models of governance

Governance models in the circular economy can be classified into the following categories:

- **Hierarchical governance:** Based on state-led regulations and policies, following a top-down approach with strict regulatory frameworks.
- **Network governance:** Characterised by collaboration among diverse stakeholders, fostering public-private partnerships, citizen participation, and strategic alliances.
- **Polycentric governance:** Involving multiple centres of decision-making with relative autonomy, enabling cooperation across different levels of government and economic sectors to achieve common objectives.

2.3 Key factors for effective governance in the circular economy

For governance to be effective in promoting circular economy initiatives, the following factors must be considered:

- **Strong governmental leadership**, providing clear regulatory frameworks and strategic direction.
- **Participation of multiple stakeholders**, ensuring an inclusive decision-making process.
- **Transparency and access to information**, enhancing accountability and public trust.
- **Economic and financial incentives**, supporting circular innovation and investment.

7.4.4.3.3. Key factors in circular economy governance

Formal governance mechanisms have the potential to enhance overall sustainability performance, ensure legitimacy, and exercise control over the technological transition towards the circular economy. Governments play a central role in this process by designing

and implementing legislation, regulatory frameworks, public policies, and economic incentives to support circular practices.

Effective governance in the circular economy requires strong governmental leadership to formulate clear policies and provide structured guidance for their implementation. Strong leadership is essential for mobilising resources, setting objectives, and driving initiatives that facilitate the transition to circular models. Countries with robust governmental leadership tend to develop more dynamic circular economy policies, ensuring broader engagement from industries and local governments. In contrast, those with weaker governmental leadership often struggle to implement effective circular economy measures, relying primarily on proactive businesses to drive initiatives.

Beyond governmental action, ensuring that all relevant actors—including businesses—possess the necessary skills and knowledge is fundamental to the effective implementation of circular economy practices. This necessitates support for education and training programmes that focus on the principles of circularity, enabling stakeholders to engage meaningfully in governance processes and decision-making.

3.1 Participation of public and private actors

Active participation from stakeholders across different sectors, particularly industry, is crucial to the governance of the circular economy. Broad stakeholder engagement ensures that policies are informed by diverse perspectives and that a collective commitment to circular economy objectives is established. Collaborative approaches, facilitated through networks and partnerships, help align efforts and promote shared ownership of circular economy goals.

However, limited stakeholder engagement can hinder the effectiveness of circular economy implementation. A lack of diverse inputs and broad-based support may result in fragmented strategies, delays in policy adoption, and reduced effectiveness in achieving long-term circular economy objectives.

The success of circular governance depends on collaboration between public and private sectors, as well as civil society. Businesses, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and citizens must work together to develop sustainable circular solutions, improve resource efficiency, and facilitate knowledge exchange. Effective governance structures should also provide mechanisms for cooperation, encouraging the development and dissemination of best practices across sectors and geographical regions.

3.2 Governance networks and interinstitutional collaboration

Governance networks play a critical role in fostering knowledge exchange and the dissemination of best practices across countries, cities, and industrial sectors. These collaborative structures help scale circular solutions, enhance policy coherence, and strengthen the resilience of production systems.

Network governance should complement traditional public governance models, enabling greater flexibility and inclusivity. By promoting partnerships among different stakeholders, networked governance can drive innovation, improve coordination, and enhance community participation in circular economy initiatives.

3.3 Influence of cultural and political contexts

Circular economy strategies must be adapted to the cultural and political contexts of each country to ensure their feasibility and acceptance by society. The sociopolitical environment influences how circular economy policies are formulated, implemented, and received by stakeholders.

Several factors shape circular economy governance, including government structure (e.g., centralised vs. decentralised governance models) and societal attitudes towards collaboration. For example, consensus-oriented governance systems—such as those in Northern European countries—tend to experience fewer barriers in adopting networked governance approaches. In contrast, societies with more polarised governance structures or autocratic tendencies may face greater challenges in fostering stakeholder collaboration. These contextual differences influence how stakeholders interact and cooperate within circular economy governance frameworks. Policymakers must therefore tailor governance strategies to align with local institutional settings, ensuring that circular economy initiatives are effectively integrated into existing political and administrative structures.

3.4 Financial incentives and regulations

The availability of financial resources and incentives plays a crucial role in stimulating innovation and encouraging businesses and communities to participate in circular economy initiatives. Financial mechanisms must be strategically aligned with circular economy objectives to ensure effective implementation and long-term viability.

Key financial instruments include:

- **Green subsidies and grants**, supporting businesses and municipalities in adopting circular solutions.

- **Favourable loan schemes and tax incentives**, reducing the financial burden on companies transitioning to circular business models.
- **Public-private funding partnerships**, enabling shared investments in circular infrastructure and technology development.

In addition to financial incentives, well-designed regulatory frameworks are essential for ensuring compliance with circular economy principles. Effective regulations should facilitate the safe reuse of materials, promote extended producer responsibility, and establish clear standards for waste reduction and resource efficiency. The development and enforcement of such regulations help create an enabling environment for circular economy practices, ensuring that businesses and consumers adopt sustainable behaviours in a structured and consistent manner.

7.4.4.4. Governance in the agri-food sector and the circular economy

The agri-food sector presents unique challenges in transitioning to a circular economy due to the complexity of its value chain and the imperative to ensure food security. As a resource-intensive sector with significant waste generation, its integration into circular economy strategies is crucial for achieving sustainability goals. The implementation of circular models in agri-food systems focuses on optimising water use, reducing food waste, and promoting soil regeneration. These measures contribute to improving resource efficiency while minimising environmental impacts.

Adopting circular principles in this sector requires addressing structural constraints such as supply chain fragmentation, logistical challenges, and regulatory barriers. Moreover, ensuring that circular practices align with food safety and quality standards is fundamental for their successful integration.

4.1 Integrating circularity into agri-food production

The circular economy in agri-food production involves a series of practices aimed at reducing waste, maximising resource efficiency, and promoting sustainable agricultural systems. Key strategies include:

- **Valorisation of by-products**: Repurposing agricultural residues for new uses, such as animal feed, biogas production, or organic fertilisers.

- **Use of organic fertilisers:** Encouraging the application of compost and other organic soil amendments to enhance soil health and reduce dependency on synthetic fertilisers.
- **Adoption of regenerative agricultural practices:** Implementing techniques such as crop rotation, conservation tillage, and agroforestry to improve soil fertility and biodiversity.
- **Agroecology and sustainable bioeconomy approaches:** Leveraging natural ecosystems and biological processes to create closed-loop agricultural systems that reduce external inputs and enhance resilience.

These strategies contribute to minimising waste and pollution while fostering more sustainable food production and distribution systems. They also align with broader sustainability goals, including reducing greenhouse gas emissions and mitigating climate change impacts.

4.2 Governance models in circular agri-food systems

Effective governance models in the agri-food sector must ensure coordination among key stakeholders, including farmers, food processing industries, policymakers, and consumers.

Governance structures should facilitate:

- **Multi-stakeholder engagement**, ensuring that diverse perspectives are considered in policy formulation and implementation.
- **Regulatory alignment**, integrating circular economy principles into food safety and agricultural regulations.
- **Incentive mechanisms**, providing financial and technical support for farmers and businesses adopting circular practices.
- **Knowledge transfer and capacity building**, fostering innovation and dissemination of best practices in circular agri-food production.

Governance mechanisms must balance economic competitiveness with sustainability goals, ensuring that circular practices do not compromise food security or affordability. Additionally, the integration of digital technologies—such as blockchain for supply chain transparency and precision agriculture for resource optimisation—can support the governance of circular agri-food systems.

4.3 Costs and benefits of circular transitions in the agri-food sector

The transition towards circular models in the agri-food sector entails initial investment costs, particularly in adapting infrastructure, implementing new technologies, and ensuring compliance with evolving regulatory frameworks. However, in the long term, the benefits outweigh these initial challenges, including:

- **Reduced input costs**, through more efficient resource use and reduced reliance on synthetic fertilisers and chemical pesticides.
- **Increased productivity**, as soil regeneration and waste valorisation improve agricultural output and efficiency.
- **Climate change mitigation**, through lower carbon emissions, enhanced carbon sequestration in soils, and reduced food waste.
- **Economic resilience**, by diversifying revenue streams for farmers and promoting value-added products derived from agricultural by-products.

The long-term sustainability of circular economy transitions in the agri-food sector depends on well-designed governance frameworks that provide financial support, ensure market incentives, and promote collaboration among stakeholders. Policymakers must address potential trade-offs between environmental objectives and economic feasibility to enable a smooth and equitable transition.

7.4.4.5. Challenges and opportunities in circular economy governance

The transition towards a circular economy presents both structural challenges and significant opportunities. While governance frameworks are essential in facilitating this transition, several barriers must be addressed to enable widespread adoption of circular practices. At the same time, the circular economy offers potential economic, social, and environmental benefits, making it a key driver for sustainable development.

5.1 Challenges in circular economy governance

One of the primary challenges in circular economy governance is the absence of specific regulatory frameworks. Many existing policies are designed for linear economic models, making the implementation of circular economy principles difficult. In some cases, waste regulations impose restrictions on material reuse due to rigid classification systems, hindering the development of circular business models. The degree of regulatory preparedness varies significantly across countries. For example, nations like Finland and

the Netherlands have well-defined circular economy strategies, whereas others lack formal policies, resulting in fragmented and less effective governance approaches.

Regulatory and institutional barriers

- **Inconsistencies in policy frameworks:** The lack of harmonised policies at the international, national, and regional levels creates uncertainty for businesses and investors.
- **Short-term governmental perspectives:** Policy decisions often prioritise immediate economic gains over long-term sustainability, limiting commitment to circular economy initiatives.
- **Administrative silos:** Coordination among government departments is often weak, with different ministries operating in isolation, reducing policy coherence.

Financial and economic constraints

Circular economy initiatives often require high initial investments, particularly for the development of infrastructure, technological adaptation, and new business models. Without adequate financial mechanisms, companies—especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)—struggle to adopt circular practices. Common financial challenges include:

- **Limited access to funding:** Traditional financial institutions often perceive circular economy projects as risky due to their longer return on investment timelines.
- **Lack of economic incentives:** In many cases, subsidies and tax incentives still favour linear economic models, making it financially unattractive for businesses to transition to circularity.
- **High costs of technology adoption:** While technological advancements support circular economy practices, their high costs can discourage companies from investing in solutions such as advanced recycling, biodegradable materials, and resource-efficient production systems.

Cultural resistance and lack of awareness

The successful implementation of the circular economy requires a cultural shift in consumption and production patterns. However, resistance to change is a significant obstacle. Many businesses and consumers lack awareness of the benefits of circularity, resulting in low demand for circular products and services. Barriers to behavioural change include:

- **Consumer habits:** Linear consumption patterns, based on disposability and low-cost production, continue to dominate global markets.
- **Corporate resistance:** Companies accustomed to traditional business models may be reluctant to alter production processes or invest in sustainable alternatives.
- **Lack of skills and knowledge:** Many industries require capacity-building efforts to equip workers with the skills needed for circular economy implementation.

Addressing these challenges requires integrated policy measures, strong financial incentives, and targeted awareness campaigns to encourage the transition towards circularity.

5.2 Opportunities in circular economy governance

Despite the challenges, the circular economy presents numerous opportunities for technological innovation, economic growth, and sustainability. The transition towards circular models can drive job creation, enhance resilience, and contribute to environmental protection.

Technological innovation and industrial transformation

The circular economy encourages the development of new technologies and production methods that optimise resource efficiency. Advances in recycling technologies, biodegradable materials, and smart manufacturing systems have the potential to transform industries. Key opportunities include:

- **Advanced recycling techniques**, enabling higher recovery rates for valuable materials.
- **Industrial symbiosis**, where waste from one industry serves as a resource for another, reducing raw material consumption.
- **Digital solutions**, such as blockchain and AI-driven supply chain management, improving traceability and efficiency.

Innovation also facilitates business model transformation, with the emergence of product-as-a-service models, extended producer responsibility (EPR) schemes, and decentralised production systems that minimise waste.

Economic growth and job creation

Circular economy strategies contribute to sustainable economic growth by generating new business opportunities and employment in emerging sectors. A report from the Finnish

Innovation Fund estimates that circular economy activities could contribute an additional 3% to Finland's GDP and create 80,000 new jobs by 2030.

Circular economy job creation is expected in:

- Recycling and waste management
- Remanufacturing and repair industries
- Sustainable product design and eco-innovation
- Green finance and circular business consultancy

The bandwagon effect plays a crucial role in accelerating adoption. Once a critical mass of businesses and consumers embrace circular practices, market momentum increases, making circularity more mainstream and commercially attractive.

Sustainability and resilience

One of the most significant advantages of the circular economy is its ability to reduce dependence on finite resources and enhance resilience against supply chain disruptions.

By minimising waste and closing material loops, circular models help economies:

- **Mitigate environmental impact**, reducing emissions and pollution.
- **Enhance energy security**, by promoting renewable resources and localised production systems.
- **Reduce price volatility**, by decreasing reliance on raw material imports and stabilising resource availability.

By strengthening resource independence, the circular economy improves economic resilience in the face of global challenges, such as climate change, supply chain crises, and geopolitical instability.

5.3 Conclusion

Governance structures play a fundamental role in overcoming barriers and capitalising on opportunities in the circular economy. A **coordinated, multi-level approach** is essential to align policies, enhance financial support, and foster cultural acceptance of circularity. Key priorities for governance improvement include:

- **Regulatory adaptation**, ensuring that policy frameworks facilitate rather than hinder circular economy adoption.
- **Financial support mechanisms**, including green subsidies, tax incentives, and circular economy investment funds.

- **Stakeholder engagement**, encouraging collaboration across governments, businesses, and civil society.
- **Education and public awareness**, integrating circular economy principles into curricula and industry training programmes.

Moving forward, international cooperation and knowledge-sharing networks will be crucial in accelerating the global transition towards circular models. By addressing governance challenges and leveraging emerging opportunities, the circular economy can become a cornerstone of sustainable development.

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7.5. HE5: Evaluating circular economy solutions: Lifecycle based approaches

7.5.1. Introduction: Multidimensional evaluation of the circular economy.

The transition towards a circular economy requires a comprehensive evaluation approach that goes beyond traditional environmental assessments. While life cycle assessment (LCA) focuses on environmental impacts, other dimensions such as economic feasibility and social sustainability play a crucial role in ensuring the long-term success of circular initiatives. A multidimensional evaluation framework integrates LCA, life cycle costing (LCC), and social-organisational life cycle assessment (SO-LCA) to provide a holistic perspective on circular economy projects. This approach ensures that circular strategies are not only environmentally beneficial but also economically viable and socially equitable.

By incorporating multiple dimensions into circular economy assessments, decision-makers can identify trade-offs and synergies between environmental, economic, and social objectives. For instance, while a recycling process may reduce carbon emissions, it may also increase costs or create social challenges related to labour conditions. A multidimensional evaluation framework helps to balance these factors, providing a more robust foundation for policy development, business strategies, and stakeholder engagement in circular economy transitions.

7.5.2. Description of the activity

This activity is designed for legal and political science degrees, with adaptations for environmental science. It is intended to provide educators with resources to develop their own activities, facilitating a deeper understanding of multidimensional evaluation techniques. The primary objective is to equip participants with the ability to critically assess the environmental, economic, and social performance of circular economy strategies.

7.5.2.1. Objectives:

- Understand the importance of integrating LCA, LCC, and SO-LCA in circular economy assessments.

- Learn how to apply these methodologies to real-world case studies, using examples from the Agro2Circular (A2C) project.
- Identify key challenges and limitations associated with multidimensional evaluation approaches.
- Develop the ability to interpret results and formulate recommendations for improving circular economy interventions.

7.5.3. Life cycle assessment (LCA)

7.5.3.1. Overview of life cycle assessment

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a scientific method used to evaluate the environmental impacts associated with all stages of a product's life cycle. This includes raw material extraction, production, transportation, use, and end-of-life management (such as recycling or disposal).

LCA is based on ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards, which provide a structured methodology for assessing environmental performance. It is widely used in policy-making, corporate sustainability strategies, and industrial innovation, ensuring that environmental improvements in one area do not create unintended negative effects in another.

Why use LCA?

- Holistic assessment: LCA evaluates the entire life cycle of a product, avoiding the risk of burden-shifting (i.e., reducing impact in one stage but increasing it in another).
- Quantitative approach: It provides measurable environmental indicators, such as carbon footprint, energy consumption, and water usage.
- Comparative analysis: It allows decision-makers to compare different materials, processes, or products to identify the most sustainable options.
- Support for circular economy strategies: LCA helps assess how circular economy initiatives (such as recycling, upcycling, and waste valorisation) contribute to environmental sustainability.

Phases of LCA

The LCA methodology follows four key phases:

1. Goal and scope definition

- Determines what will be assessed, which environmental impacts will be considered, and which system boundaries apply.

- Defines the functional unit, which serves as the basis for comparison (e.g., evaluating the carbon footprint of producing 1 kg of recycled plastic vs. 1 kg of virgin plastic).

2. Life cycle inventory (LCI)

- Collects data on inputs and outputs throughout the product's life cycle (e.g., raw materials, energy consumption, emissions, and waste generation).
- Data can come from databases (e.g., ecoinvent), direct measurements, or scientific literature.

3. Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)

- Translates inventory data into environmental impact categories, such as:
 - Carbon footprint (global warming potential)
 - Resource depletion
 - Water use
 - Acidification and eutrophication (impacts on ecosystems)
- Uses characterisation factors to express different environmental impacts in common units (e.g., CO₂ equivalents for climate change).

4. Interpretation and recommendations

- Identifies hotspots (the most impactful life cycle stages).
- Provides recommendations for process optimisation, material selection, or energy efficiency improvements.
- Ensures results are reliable and transparent, avoiding misleading conclusions.

LCA can be retrospective (evaluating existing systems) or prospective (predicting the impact of new technologies and innovations). In the context of the circular economy, LCA is particularly useful for evaluating the sustainability of recycling, reuse, and waste valorisation strategies.

7.5.3.2. Application of LCA in Agro2Circular (A2C)

The Agro2Circular (A2C) project applies LCA to assess the environmental impact of circular economy solutions in the agri-food and plastics sectors. The goal is to determine whether the circular processes developed in the project genuinely reduce environmental burdens compared to conventional practices.

The A2C LCA study focuses on two main areas:

1. **Plastics:** Upcycling multi-layer plastic residues into new high-value products to reduce dependency on virgin plastics.
2. **Agri-food waste:** Extracting bioactive compounds from fruit and vegetable residues for applications in food, nutraceuticals, and cosmetics.

Each case study follows a cradle-to-gate approach, meaning that the assessment covers all life cycle stages up to the point where the new circular product is ready for industrial use.

LCA findings in the A2C plastics sector

Objective:

To assess the carbon footprint of A2C recycled plastic pellets compared to conventional virgin LDPE pellets.

Key results:

- A2C plastic pellets reduced carbon footprint by 26% compared to virgin LDPE pellets.
- The most significant environmental burden in both cases came from energy consumption in processing.
- Using 100% renewable electricity instead of the Spanish electricity mix could reduce emissions by an additional 21%.
- Virgin plastic production (ethylene synthesis) contributed 72% of total emissions, making material substitution a key strategy for emissions reduction.

Implications for industry:

- Increasing the proportion of recycled material in plastic pellets can significantly improve environmental performance.
- Investing in renewable energy sources for processing facilities is essential to maximising the benefits of plastic recycling.
- Future studies should incorporate end-of-life analysis to determine how recycled plastics behave after use.

7.5.3.3. LCA findings in the A2C agri-food waste sector

Objective:

To assess the carbon footprint of valorised agri-food waste, focusing on the production of:

- Dehydrated fibre extracts (used in food and nutraceutical applications)
- Phenolic extracts (used for their antioxidant properties in food and cosmetics)

Key results:

- Lyophilisation (freeze-drying) was the most energy-intensive process, accounting for the majority of emissions.
- Switching to 100% renewable energy reduced the carbon footprint of the extracts by 77%.
- Comparing A2C fibre extracts to inulin (a common dietary fibre):
 - A2C fibre had 3–6 times higher emissions than inulin.
 - This was due to the pilot-scale nature of the process—optimisation at an industrial scale could significantly lower its impact.
- Phenolic extract benchmarks were more difficult to establish because commercial antioxidant extracts vary widely in composition and production impact.

Implications for industry:

- Process optimisation (e.g., improving energy efficiency in lyophilisation) is critical for scaling up agri-food waste valorisation.
- The use of waste biomass as a low-carbon feedstock could further reduce emissions.
- Market analysis should explore economic incentives for bio-based ingredients, as higher sustainability could increase consumer demand.

7.5.3.4. Student assignments and discussions

Analysing circular strategies in plastics and agri-food waste

- Identify key environmental benefits of the A2C project's approach to circularity.
- Discuss how these findings could be applied in other industries.

Applying LCA to real-world scenarios

- Choose a product or process and conduct a simplified LCA to assess its sustainability.
- Compare two different materials or technologies using LCA principles.

Identifying barriers to circular economy implementation

- What technological, economic, and regulatory challenges affect the scalability of circular solutions?
- How can policy and financial incentives support companies in adopting circular strategies?

Designing a circular economy initiative

- Develop a proposal for a new circular economy strategy in a specific sector (e.g., fashion, automotive, construction).
- Justify the strategy using LCA-based arguments.

7.5.4. Life Cycle Costing

7.5.4.1. Introduction to Life Cycle Costing (LCC)

Life Cycle Costing (LCC) is an essential methodology used to assess the total cost of ownership of a product, process, or service throughout its entire lifecycle. Unlike conventional cost accounting, which often focuses only on direct costs incurred during production, LCC incorporates all financial implications from raw material extraction to disposal or recycling. This holistic approach provides decision-makers with a more comprehensive economic evaluation of sustainable initiatives, including circular economy strategies.

Why LCC is Important in Circular Economy Projects

The transition to a circular economy requires an assessment framework that goes beyond traditional financial metrics. LCC allows for a structured evaluation of how different circular strategies (reuse, recycling, remanufacturing) impact the total costs associated with a product or process.

By integrating LCC, companies and policymakers can:

- Identify hidden costs that might not be evident in a traditional cost analysis.
- Justify investments in circular economy strategies by demonstrating long-term savings.
- Compare circular and linear business models from a financial standpoint.
- Improve decision-making regarding materials selection, waste management, and product design.
- Provide transparency to stakeholders, supporting sustainable procurement and investment.

Circular economy projects often involve high initial costs due to innovation, infrastructure adjustments, and compliance with sustainability regulations. LCC helps balance these upfront costs against long-term savings, demonstrating financial feasibility.

7.5.4.2. Key Components of LCC Analysis

LCC consists of several cost categories that together define the total cost of a product's lifecycle. These include:

- **Investment costs:** Initial expenditures, including research and development (R&D), equipment, and infrastructure.
- **Operational costs:** Expenses incurred during the production phase, including labor, raw materials, energy, and maintenance.
- **End-of-life costs:** Costs related to waste management, recycling, repurposing, or disposal.
- **Externalities and hidden costs:** Costs related to environmental impacts, regulatory compliance, and resource depletion.

Understanding and categorizing these cost elements is crucial for an accurate LCC assessment.

7.5.4.3. Applying Life Cycle Costing in Circular Economy Projects

The application of LCC follows a structured methodology, ensuring that all relevant costs are considered. Below is a step-by-step approach to conducting an LCC analysis in circular economy projects.

Defining the Scope and Boundaries

Before conducting an LCC assessment, it is essential to define its scope, ensuring clarity on what is included and excluded in the analysis. Key considerations include:

- **System boundaries:** What lifecycle stages will be considered? Will the assessment include raw material extraction, production, distribution, use, and disposal?
- **Functional unit:** How will costs be measured? For example, cost per kilogram of recycled material, cost per functional service delivered, or cost per product lifetime.
- **Timeframe:** Over what period will costs be assessed? Many circular economy strategies require long-term evaluation to capture cost benefits.
- **Stakeholders involved:** Identifying decision-makers and users of the LCC analysis (e.g., businesses, policymakers, investors).

Data Collection and Cost Estimation

Accurate data collection is crucial for a reliable LCC analysis. The data sources typically include:

- **Direct costs:** Material procurement, labor, energy consumption.
- **Indirect costs:** Maintenance, repair, training.
- **External costs:** Environmental impact costs, regulatory compliance costs.
- **Cost discounting factors:** Adjusting future costs to present value using discount rates.

Challenges in data collection include data availability, accuracy, and variability in cost structures across industries. To mitigate these issues, sensitivity analysis can be used to test different cost scenarios.

Cost Allocation and Modelling Techniques

Allocating costs accurately is critical for ensuring that the LCC reflects real economic implications. Some key modelling techniques include:

- **Process-based costing:** Assigning costs based on the actual production processes and material flows.
- **Activity-based costing (ABC):** Distributing overhead costs based on activities performed rather than generic allocations.
- **Monte Carlo simulations:** Running probabilistic models to account for uncertainties in cost predictions.
- **Scenario analysis:** Comparing different business models (e.g., traditional linear economy vs. circular economy).

Interpreting and Using LCC Results

The final stage involves analyzing the LCC results and applying them to decision-making processes. The results should address:

- **Break-even points:** When does the circular strategy become cost-effective compared to a traditional approach?
- **Sensitivity analysis:** How do variations in key parameters affect overall costs?
- **Comparative analysis:** Evaluating different circular interventions (e.g., material substitution, design changes, reverse logistics).
- **Policy and investment recommendations:** Using LCC insights to support sustainable procurement, policy design, and innovation funding.

7.5.4.4. Implementation of LCC in Agro2Circular

The Agro2Circular (A2C) project applied Life Cycle Costing (LCC) alongside Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to evaluate economic feasibility and environmental impacts of circular economy strategies in the agri-food and plastic sectors.

LCC in the Agri-food Sector

A2C conducted an environmental LCC (eLCC) assessment on selected demonstration case studies focused on valorizing agri-food waste streams. Two key demonstrations were analyzed:

- Demo 3 and Demo 4: These demonstrations extracted high-value bioactive compounds from food waste such as lemon, artichoke, and broccoli waste to produce fibres and phenolic extracts for food, nutraceutical, and cosmetic applications.
- The cost categories analyzed included:
 - Physical input and output costs (raw materials, energy, water, waste management).
 - Equipment and installation costs, considering amortization over expected use.
 - Labour and maintenance costs.
 - Waste management costs related to disposal and treatment of by-products.
 - Environmental externalities monetized using impact assessment methodologies from the Delft University of Technology.

A sensitivity analysis was performed to evaluate the impact of production scale on cost efficiency. The results showed that upscaling the recycling process could reduce LCC by up to 61% for fibres and 66% for phenolic extracts. These cost reductions were mainly attributed to improved resource efficiency, economies of scale in waste processing, and optimized logistics.

LCC in the Plastic Recycling Sector

A2C also assessed LCC for plastic waste valorisation, focusing on upcycling agricultural mulch film waste and aseptic bag residues into high-value plastic pellets.

- The assessment compared:
 - A2C-developed recycled plastic pellet (33% recycled content, 67% virgin LDPE).
 - 100% virgin LDPE pellet.

- Findings demonstrated that A2C's recycled pellet had a 21% lower total LCC than virgin plastic, driven by reduced raw material and environmental costs.
- Equipment amortization and waste management costs were identified as key cost drivers, emphasizing the need for scaling up recycling operations.
- Sensitivity analysis highlighted that increasing recycled content above 50% further reduced costs, although regulatory compliance and mechanical properties of recycled plastics must be carefully managed.

7.5.4.5. Challenges and Best Practices in LCC for Circular Economy

Common Challenges

- **Data availability and accuracy:** Circular economy projects often lack historical data, requiring estimations or industry benchmarks.
- **Standardization:** LCC methodologies vary across industries, making cross-sector comparisons complex.
- **Incorporating externalities:** Many sustainability benefits (e.g., reduced emissions, resource conservation) are difficult to quantify in monetary terms.

Best Practices

- **Use reliable data sources:** Collaborate with suppliers, industry associations, and academia to improve data quality.
- **Apply multi-scenario analysis:** Consider different assumptions and discount rates to capture uncertainty.
- **Integrate LCC with other assessment tools:** Combine with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) for a holistic view.
- **Engage stakeholders early:** Ensure that decision-makers, financial analysts, and sustainability teams collaborate in the LCC process.

7.5.5. Social-organisational life cycle assessment (SO-LCA) in circular economy project evaluation

7.5.5.1. Methodological overview of SO-LCA and its value in circular economy project evaluation

The **social-organisational life cycle assessment (SO-LCA)** is a methodology designed to evaluate the social performance of organisations, particularly in the context of

sustainability and circular economy (CE) transitions. Unlike traditional life cycle assessments (LCA) that focus on environmental or economic aspects, SO-LCA incorporates social indicators to assess how organisations impact stakeholders such as workers, consumers, local communities, and society at large.

SO-LCA plays a crucial role in circular economy project evaluation by providing a structured approach to understanding the social sustainability of organisations engaged in circular business models. By incorporating social indicators alongside economic and environmental assessments, SO-LCA enables a holistic evaluation of circular economy initiatives, ensuring that sustainability is pursued beyond material flows and resource efficiency.

The fundamental premise of SO-LCA is that organisations play a pivotal role in fostering sustainability and CE practices. By evaluating their performance in key social dimensions, SO-LCA helps identify areas for improvement and facilitates the adoption of socially responsible practices. The approach is structured around a **stakeholder-based assessment**, where the social impact of an organisation is measured according to various categories, including:

- **Workers:** Employment conditions, fair wages, health and safety, workers' rights.
- **Value chain actors:** Fair competition, supplier relations, respect for intellectual property rights.
- **Society:** Economic contribution, public commitment to sustainability, corruption prevention.
- **Local community:** Access to material and immaterial resources, cultural heritage support, local employment.
- **Consumers:** Health and safety, transparency, end-of-life responsibility.

The methodology is primarily guided by the **United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) guidelines** for SO-LCA. Indicators are selected based on their relevance, measurability, reliability, and comparability, ensuring a robust framework for social performance evaluation.

SO-LCA has proven particularly valuable in circular economy project evaluation as it enables policymakers, businesses, and researchers to assess whether social benefits are equitably distributed across stakeholders. It also helps ensure that circular economy transitions do not create unintended negative social consequences, such as job losses in traditional sectors or adverse working conditions in new business models.

7.5.5.2. Application of SO-LCA in the Agro2Circular (A2C) project

In the context of the **Agro2Circular (A2C) project**, SO-LCA has been applied as part of the social assessment framework to evaluate the impact of organisations engaged in circular economy initiatives. The evaluation focused on organisations participating in two distinct value chains: agrifood and plastics, and grouped them into three categories: private for-profit organisations, research organisations, and civil society organisations (CSOs).

Goal and scope of the A2C SO-LCA

The primary goal of the SO-LCA in A2C was to analyse the social performance of organisations to promote improved social conditions and stakeholder well-being. The assessment adopted a “cradle-to-gate” system boundary, meaning that only the social impacts associated with organisational operations up to the production phase were considered.

The stakeholder approach was crucial in this evaluation. Five stakeholder categories were selected based on their relevance to the project, with specific impact subcategories linked to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This approach allowed for a structured comparison of how different organisational types contribute to social sustainability within the circular economy.

Inventory and data collection

The SO-LCA in A2C was structured in two phases: **screening and final evaluation**. The screening phase (reported in Deliverable D7.8) established a preliminary set of social indicators based on a **fuzzy Delphi study and UNEP guidelines**, which were refined and updated in the final evaluation.

Data collection tools included:

- **Project manager form:** A questionnaire targeting senior management, focusing on organisational policies and performance in SO-LCA categories.
- **Workers' questionnaire:** Designed to capture employee perspectives on workplace conditions, circular economy awareness, and engagement.

Indicators were selected based on methodological criteria such as relevance, reliability, clarity, and availability. The final dataset enabled a comparative analysis of social impacts across different organisational types.

Key findings from the A2C SO-LCA

1. Workers' rights and conditions

- Across all organisations, no forced labour incidents were reported.
- Fair salary disparities were observed, with private sector organisations paying below the living wage while research organisations and CSOs paid above it.
- Health and safety measures were reported as adequate, but research organisations exhibited a higher lost time injury frequency rate.
- Trade union density was below national averages across all groups, highlighting a lack of worker representation mechanisms.

2. Value chain and supplier relations

- No cases of anti-competitive behaviour or corruption were reported.
- Private companies showed higher engagement in corporate social responsibility (CSR) compared to research organisations and CSOs.
- Supplier audits for social responsibility compliance were inconsistent across sectors.

3. Local community and society impact

- Economic contributions varied significantly depending on organisation type, with private companies paying higher taxes compared to CSOs.
- Technology transfer and innovation investments were concentrated in research organisations and plastics-sector firms.
- Local employment generation was highest among private firms, while CSOs engaged more in community health and cultural heritage initiatives.

4. Consumer and transparency considerations

- Product labelling and safety certifications were well established in private companies and research organisations, but CSOs lacked formal mechanisms.
- Transparency in organisational communication was higher among research institutions and CSOs compared to private companies.
- End-of-life product management systems were primarily found in private firms, with limited implementation in research organisations.

Research limitations and challenges

Despite its robust framework, the SO-LCA methodology faced several challenges in A2C:

- Lack of standardised social performance indicators for circular economy projects.
- Difficulties in quantifying social impacts and establishing cause-effect relationships.
- Limited availability of comparable datasets at national and sectoral levels.

- Heterogeneity of organisations, making direct comparisons difficult.

7.5.6. Exercises

1. Comparing evaluation approaches

- Divide participants into three groups, each assigned one of the methodologies (LCA, LCC, or SO-LCA).
- Each group will analyse the same circular economy case study and present their findings based on their assigned methodology.
- Discuss the differences and complementarities between the approaches, highlighting their strengths and limitations.

2. Multidimensional assessment of a product or process

- Ask students to select a product or industrial process and conduct a simplified LCA, LCC, and SO-LCA assessment.
- Compare the results and discuss how trade-offs between environmental, economic, and social aspects influence decision-making.

3. Scenario analysis

- Provide participants with a set of different circular economy scenarios (e.g., increasing recycled content in plastics, implementing an extended producer responsibility scheme, or introducing new waste valorisation strategies).
- Ask them to assess the scenarios using a multidimensional evaluation approach, considering environmental, economic, and social criteria.
- Encourage discussion on which strategies provide the most balanced sustainability outcomes.

4. Developing circular economy recommendations

- Based on the case studies analysed, participants will develop recommendations for improving circular economy initiatives.
- They should justify their recommendations using insights from LCA, LCC, and SO-LCA, ensuring a well-rounded argument.

7.6. HE6: A2C Data Integration System (DIS) Training Outline for Computer Science Students

7.6.1. 1. Introduction

The A2C Data Integration System (DIS) is a digital tool that enhances waste traceability, decision-making, and process optimisation within the circular economy. This training plan provides higher education students—particularly in computer science and data management—with the necessary skills to understand and interact with data-driven environmental solutions.

By engaging with real-world case studies, students will explore the application of digital technologies in waste management and circular economy systems.

7.6.2. 2. Training Objectives

Upon completion, participants will:

- ✓ Understand how digital platforms improve waste traceability and resource management.
- ✓ Explore blockchain, AI, and cloud-based traceability systems in real-world applications.
- ✓ Develop skills in data integration, decision support tools, and traceability mechanisms.
- ✓ Analyse case studies to assess practical implementations of digital solutions in sustainability.

7.6.3. 3. Target Audience

This module is designed for:

- Computer Science & Informatics students – Interested in environmental applications of data integration systems.
- Sustainability & Circular Economy professionals – Who wish to leverage digital tools for impact assessment.

7.6.4. 4. Training Modules & Content

MODULE 1: Introduction to the A2C Data Integration System (DIS)

- ✦ Overview of Digital Tools in the Circular Economy
- ✦ DIS as a Case Study – Features, Functions, and Implementation
- ✦ Real-time Data Monitoring & Blockchain-based Traceability

Practical Activity: Students explore user interfaces and test basic functionalities of the DIS tool.

MODULE 2: Data Management & Interoperability in Circular Economy Systems

- ✦ Data Integration Frameworks – API, Cloud Computing, and IoT Connectivity
- ✦ Ensuring Interoperability Across Sectors – Challenges and Solutions
- ✦ Regulatory Compliance & Digital Traceability

Practical Activity: Simulating waste data tracking using real-world scenarios.

MODULE 3: Decision Support Systems (DSS) in Environmental Management

- ✦ AI & Big Data Analytics in Circular Economy
- ✦ Predictive Modelling for Waste Valorisation
- ✦ Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) for Resource Optimization

Practical Activity: Students use data-driven tools to make decisions on waste recovery strategies.

MODULE 4: Case Studies & Applications of Digital Circular Economy Tools

- ✦ DIS in Agro2Circular (A2C) – A real-world case study
- ✦ Comparative Study – How DIS compares with other waste traceability platforms
- ✦ Future Trends in Digital Sustainability Solutions

Practical Activity: Students develop their own digital circular economy solution proposal.

7.6.5. 5. Learning Approach

- ✔ Interactive Lectures – Conceptual explanations with real-world insights.
- ✔ Hands-on Exercises – Direct interaction with DIS & other platforms.
- ✔ Group Discussions – Debates on the role of digital tools in sustainability.
- ✔ Case Study Analysis – Exploring how existing tools address waste traceability challenges.

7.6.6. 6. Expected Outcomes

At the end of this training, participants will:

- ◆ Grasp the importance of data-driven solutions in waste management.
- ◆ Apply digital tools to monitor waste streams and optimise recycling strategies.
- ◆ Develop decision-making skills using AI-based tools.
- ◆ Critically assess the potential and limitations of existing traceability systems.

7.6.7. 7. Further Information & Resources

For full technical documentation and case studies, visit:

 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036838/results>

Search for:

- 📌 A2C_D1.10 – Data Integration System (BETA Version)
- 📌 A2C_D6.2 – Data Integration System v1.0
- 📌 A2C_Deliverable_D1.13 – A2C Data Integration System (Public Summary)

8. ANNEX IV – Training Plan for local actors: Industry/business

8.1. IB1: Circular Business Models: guidelines & regional success stories

8.1.1. Guidelines for developing Circular Business Models

The transition to circular economy business models (CEBM) is essential for reducing waste, improving resource efficiency, and enhancing business competitiveness. These guidelines integrate insights from A2C's work and from multiple studies to provide a structured approach for businesses aiming to adopt circular practices.

1. Strategic Foundations for Circular Business Models

To implement a circular business model successfully, businesses must define two critical strategic choices:

- **Resource Strategy:** How materials and resources are used and cycled within the business.
- **Innovation Strategy:** The level of collaboration and openness in implementing circular solutions.

Businesses can adopt one or more of the following circular strategies:

- **Narrowing the loop:** Reducing resource consumption through efficiency improvements in design and production (e.g., minimising material use and energy consumption).
- **Closing the loop:** Enabling materials and products to be reused or recycled into new production cycles (e.g., upcycling, remanufacturing, or industrial symbiosis).
- **Slowing the loop:** Extending the product lifecycle through durability, reparability, and leasing models instead of single-use consumption.

(Source: Bocken & Ritala, 2022)

2. Key Steps in Developing Circular Business Models

Step 1: Assess Circular Opportunities

Before transitioning to a circular model, businesses must evaluate:

- Their resource and waste streams.
- Potential for reducing, reusing, or recycling materials.
- Business and regulatory incentives that support circular practices.
- Market demand for circular products or services.

For example, in agribusiness, opportunities exist to turn organic waste into bioproducts, reducing environmental impact while generating additional revenue.

(Source: Lamolinara et al., 2024)

Step 2: Define the Circular Value Proposition

A clear value proposition should outline:

- **What problem is being solved?** (e.g., reducing food waste, creating sustainable packaging)
- **Who are the key customers?** (e.g., businesses, governments, consumers)
- **What differentiates the business from linear competitors?** (e.g., cost savings, sustainability benefits, new revenue streams)

A circular business model should deliver both environmental benefits and economic value, ensuring financial viability.

(Source: Barros et al., 2023)

Step 3: Develop Circular Supply Chains

At this stage, learners or business teams should analyse their current supply chains and redesign them to support circularity. This includes identifying where and how materials can be reused, recycled, or recovered, and how partnerships can enable closed-loop systems.

Key actions include:

- Mapping the supply chain to locate critical resource inputs and waste outputs.
- Exploring sources of secondary raw materials (e.g., recycled plastics, organic by-products).
- Designing systems for returning, repairing, or refurbishing products.
- Seeking partnerships with suppliers, logistics providers, or waste processors to close material loops.
- Investigating digital tools (e.g., blockchain, traceability systems) that can support transparent circular supply chains.

(Source: Bocken & Ritala, 2022)

Step 4: Build an Innovation Strategy

Businesses can choose between:

- **Closed innovation:** Developing circular solutions internally (e.g., a company creating an in-house recycling system).

- **Open innovation:** Collaborating with external partners, communities, or digital platforms to scale circular solutions (e.g., second-hand markets for refurbished goods).

For example, agro-industrial cooperatives can share bioenergy and organic waste processing facilities to achieve economies of scale in circular practices.

(Source: Barros et al., 2023)

Step 5: Establish Revenue and Business Models

Circular models should consider diverse revenue streams, such as:

- **Product-as-a-Service (PaaS):** Leasing rather than selling (e.g., renting agricultural equipment instead of purchasing).
- **Material recovery models:** Selling recovered materials or by-products (e.g., converting agricultural waste into biofertilisers).
- **Extended product life models:** Offering maintenance, repair, and refurbishment to extend product use.

(Source: Lamolinara et al., 2024)

Step 6: Monitor and Scale Circular Practices

Performance metrics should track:

- Reduction in raw material consumption.
- Waste reduction and resource recovery rates.
- Financial performance and customer adoption of circular solutions.

Governments and businesses should collaborate to align incentives, ensuring the long-term viability of circular practices.

(Source: Bocken & Ritala, 2022)

Conclusion

Developing a circular business model requires a strategic shift in how businesses approach resource use, innovation, and value creation. By adopting a mix of narrowing, slowing, and closing resource loops, businesses can achieve sustainability while maintaining competitiveness. Collaboration within industries, particularly in high-impact sectors like agribusiness, plays a crucial role in accelerating the transition to a circular economy.

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8.1.2. Regional success stories

The **Rethink Milano 2022 Report**, developed within the Circular Economy Forum, presents a selection of best practices showcasing innovative approaches to sustainability and circularity. These initiatives highlight the diverse ways in which businesses and institutions are embracing circular economy principles across different sectors.

One notable case is the **urban circular hubs** implemented in Milan, designed to foster local circular networks by integrating waste management, repair, and reuse initiatives within neighbourhood communities. These hubs serve as multifunctional spaces where citizens can exchange, repair, and upcycle items, reducing waste while promoting a circular mindset. Another exemplary initiative is the **regenerative design approach** adopted by several Milanese companies in the fashion and textile industries. By leveraging post-consumer materials and bio-based alternatives, these businesses aim to close production loops, extending the life cycle of products and minimising environmental impact. The report also highlights the role of **public-private partnerships** in facilitating the transition towards circularity, with local authorities supporting businesses through funding schemes and regulatory incentives that encourage sustainable practices.

These examples illustrate the growing commitment to circular solutions at a regional level, demonstrating how policy support, community engagement, and innovation converge to accelerate the circular transition.

Additional Resources

Beyond the insights from Milan, further initiatives have emerged to support the implementation of circular economy practices. The **Directory of Best Practices** developed under the Agro2Circular project offers a structured repository of innovative circular models across various sectors.

Additionally, since October 2024, the **Dynamic Catalogue of Good Practices in Circular Economy**, promoted by the Institute for the Promotion of the Region of Murcia, has been made available. This tool complements existing directories by allowing companies in Murcia to showcase their circular business models while providing visibility to organisations fostering circular initiatives in the business community.

 <https://looparm.es/casos-de-exito/>

Reference: Milano Circular Economy Forum; Rethink Milano 2022 [Report](#).

8.2. IB2: Guidelines for value chain analysis session on circular business models in the agrifood sector

These guidelines provide a structured approach for businesses in the agri-food sector to analyse their value chain, identify inefficiencies, and explore circular opportunities. The methodology integrates value chain analysis with circular economy principles, using tools such as the Business Model Canvas (BMC) to support decision-making.

Session Objectives

1. Understand the current value chain and identify key activities, resources, and partnerships.
2. Map material and energy flows to detect inefficiencies and waste generation.
3. Identify opportunities to reduce waste, optimize resources, and develop circular business models.
4. Develop a strategic roadmap for integrating circular economy principles into business operations.

8.2.1. Session 1: Mapping the Value Chain and Identifying Circularity Gaps

Duration: 2–3 hours

Participants: Management, production, sustainability, supply chain, and R&D teams

8.2.1.1. Introduction and Context (30 min)

- Overview of circular economy principles and their relevance to the agri-food sector.
- Explanation of value chain analysis and Business Model Canvas as tools to diagnose circularity gaps.
- Examples of circular economy initiatives in food processing, agriculture, and waste valorization.

8.2.1.2. Value Chain Mapping (45 min)

- Identify and map each step of the business value chain, from raw material sourcing to product distribution.
- Focus on:

- Input materials such as water, energy, fertilizers, and packaging.
- Production processes, including food processing, storage, and logistics.
- By-products and waste streams at different stages.
- Key partners in the supply chain and their role in material flows.
- Consumer use and end-of-life management, including recycling, composting, and reuse.
- Use visual tools such as post-its or digital platforms (Miro, MURAL) to represent material flows.

8.2.1.3. Circularity Gap Analysis (45 min)

Step 1: Identifying Inefficiencies in the Value Chain

Participants should critically assess each stage of their value chain to locate inefficiencies.

The following categories serve as guidance:

a) Resource Inefficiencies

- **Water waste:** Excessive water use in washing, processing, or irrigation.
 - *Example:* A dairy company using large amounts of water to clean production lines without a recovery system.
- **Energy consumption:** High energy use in processing, storage, or transport.
 - *Example:* Cold storage in food logistics running continuously at non-optimal temperatures.

b) Material Losses and Waste Generation

- **Food loss during production:** Crops left unharvested, production errors, spoilage in storage.
 - *Example:* A fruit processing plant discarding misshapen fruits that could be used for juices or jams.
- **Packaging inefficiencies:** Use of non-recyclable, excessive, or single-use packaging.
 - *Example:* A meat processing company using styrofoam trays instead of compostable or reusable alternatives.

c) Supply Chain and Logistics Inefficiencies

- **Overproduction:** Producing more than what the market demands, leading to waste.

- *Example:* A bakery producing large batches of fresh bread with high daily unsold leftovers.
- **Inefficient distribution:** Transporting goods with high carbon emissions or poor route optimization.
 - *Example:* A vegetable supplier using individual trucks instead of consolidated logistics for deliveries.

Step 2: Identifying Potential Circular Strategies

After mapping inefficiencies, the group should explore ways to integrate circular economy principles.

a) Waste Valorization and By-Product Utilization

- **Reusing production waste as secondary products**
 - *Example:* Converting fruit peels into animal feed or extracting essential oils from citrus waste.
- **Biogas generation from organic waste**
 - *Example:* A dairy farm installing an anaerobic digester to produce energy from manure and food residues.

b) Resource Optimization and Efficiency

- **Water recirculation systems**
 - *Example:* A brewery implementing a closed-loop water system to reuse wastewater for cooling purposes.
- **Energy efficiency measures**
 - *Example:* A food processing plant installing heat recovery systems from ovens.

c) Sustainable Packaging and Circular Logistics

- **Reusable and compostable packaging**
 - *Example:* A pasta company shifting from plastic packaging to biodegradable cellulose-based alternatives.
- **Optimized transportation and shared logistics**
 - *Example:* Multiple local producers consolidating deliveries to reduce emissions and costs.

d) New Business Models Based on Circularity

- **Product-as-a-service models**

- *Example:* A coffee supplier offering coffee grounds as fertilizer or mushroom-growing kits instead of disposal.
- **Upcycling initiatives**
 - *Example:* A dairy company creating cosmetic creams from whey protein, a by-product of cheese production.

8.2.1.4. Prioritizing Circular Opportunities (30 min)

- Identify the most promising circular strategies based on feasibility and impact.
- Categorize ideas using an Impact vs. Feasibility matrix.
- Discuss potential business and policy support mechanisms for implementation.

What is an Impact-Feasibility Matrix?

The Impact-Feasibility Matrix is a decision-making tool that helps businesses prioritize circular economy initiatives based on two key dimensions:

1. **Impact** – The potential environmental, economic, and social benefits of implementing a given circular strategy.
2. **Feasibility** – The technical, financial, and organizational ease of implementing the strategy within the current business context.

This matrix allows businesses to systematically assess different circular economy actions, ensuring that resources are allocated to the most effective and achievable initiatives.

How to Create an Impact-Feasibility Matrix

1. List Potential Circular Strategies

- Identify specific circular actions for the agri-food sector (e.g., waste valorization, sustainable packaging, water recirculation).
- Consider strategies along the entire value chain: raw material sourcing, production, logistics, consumption, and end-of-life management.

2. Evaluate Impact and Feasibility

- **Impact** can be assessed based on:
 - Reduction of environmental footprint (e.g., lower carbon emissions, water savings).

- Economic benefits (e.g., cost savings, revenue generation from waste valorisation).
- Social benefits (e.g., job creation, enhanced consumer perception).
- **Feasibility** depends on:
 - Technological readiness.
 - Financial investment required.
 - Regulatory and market acceptance.

3. Score and Position on the Matrix

- Assign scores (e.g., 1-5) for impact and feasibility.
- Plot the strategies on a 2x2 matrix:
 - **High Impact, High Feasibility:** Prioritize and implement immediately.
 - **High Impact, Low Feasibility:** Develop a long-term plan and seek external support.
 - **Low Impact, High Feasibility:** Consider quick wins but avoid large resource allocation.
 - **Low Impact, Low Feasibility:** Avoid or deprioritize.

Example Application in the Agri-Food Sector:

Circular Strategy	Impact Score (1-5)	Feasibility Score (1-5)	Matrix Position
Biogas production from organic waste	5	3	High Impact, Low Feasibility
Reusable packaging for food distribution	4	5	High Impact, High Feasibility
Water recirculation in processing plants	3	4	Low Impact, High Feasibility
Conversion of by-products into animal feed	5	5	High Impact, High Feasibility

8.2.2. Session 2: Circular Business Model Innovation

Duration: 2–3 hours

Participants: Management, sustainability team, product innovation team

8.2.2.1. Recap and Defining Circular Strategies (30 min)

- Review key findings from the previous session.
- Identify priority areas for business model adaptation.

8.2.2.2. Adapting the Business Model Canvas (60 min)

- Modify the Business Model Canvas to integrate circular economy principles:
 - Key Resources: Introduce renewable inputs and by-product valorization strategies.
 - Key Partnerships: Identify collaborations to create value from waste or optimize resource flows.
 - Value Proposition: Explore new product offerings based on circular principles.
 - Customer Segments: Assess potential demand for circular products and services.
 - Revenue Streams: Evaluate opportunities to monetize waste or resource efficiency improvements.
- Use real-world case studies from different segments of the agri-food sector to illustrate potential applications.

What is a Business Model Canvas (BMC)?

The Business Model Canvas (BMC) is a strategic tool used to visualize and design business models. Developed by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010), it consists of nine building blocks that define how a business creates, delivers, and captures value.

Adapting the Business Model Canvas for the Circular Economy

Traditional business models are linear, following a "take-make-dispose" approach. In contrast, a **Circular Business Model Canvas (CBMC)** integrates sustainability by closing resource loops and creating value from waste and by-products.

Nine Key Components of the Circular Business Model Canvas

1. Customer Segments

- Who are the key stakeholders benefiting from circular solutions?
- Examples: Sustainable food retailers, eco-conscious consumers, food processing companies needing by-products.

2. Value Proposition

- What unique value does the business offer in terms of circularity?
- Examples: Zero-waste production, upcycled food products, sustainable packaging solutions.

3. Channels

- How does the business reach its customers?
- Examples: Direct sales, online platforms, circular supply chains.

4. Customer Relationships

- How does the business engage customers in circular practices?
- Examples: Deposit-refund systems, subscription models for reusable packaging.

5. Revenue Streams

- How does the company generate revenue from circularity?
- Examples: Selling waste-derived products, leasing equipment instead of selling, extended producer responsibility programs.

6. Key Resources

- What resources are essential for implementing a circular model?
- Examples: Waste valorization infrastructure, renewable energy, local sourcing networks.

7. Key Activities

- What processes ensure circularity in the business model?
- Examples: Reverse logistics, product take-back systems, composting or biogas production.

8. Key Partnerships

- Who are the external stakeholders supporting the circular economy transition?

- Examples: Agricultural cooperatives, waste management firms, research institutions.

9. Cost Structure

- What are the major costs involved in maintaining a circular business?
- Examples: Investment in closed-loop processing systems, certification costs for sustainable products.

Applying the Circular Business Model Canvas to the Agri-Food Sector

BMC Component	Traditional Business Model	Circular Business Model
Customer Segments	General food consumers	Consumers who prioritize sustainable and circular products
Value Proposition	Selling fresh produce	Selling fresh produce while converting food waste into value-added products
Channels	Supermarkets, distributors	Direct-to-consumer, partnerships with zero-waste retailers
Customer Relationships	One-time transactions	Engagement through loyalty programs and waste-return incentives
Revenue Streams	Sales of food products	Subscription models, upcycling food waste into secondary products
Key Resources	Raw materials, processing facilities	Renewable resources, waste recovery systems
Key Activities	Traditional food processing	Waste valorization, reverse logistics
Key Partnerships	Distributors, suppliers	Circular packaging providers, sustainability certifiers
Cost Structure	Linear production costs	Investment in circular technologies and processes

Why Use a Circular Business Model Canvas?

- Helps visualize circular opportunities in the business model.
- Supports the transition from linear to circular value creation.

- Encourages stakeholder collaboration for sustainability.

Figure 8 - Business Model Canvas example template (2)

8.2.2.3. Action Plan and Implementation Roadmap (60 min)

- Select three priority circular initiatives for short- and long-term implementation.
- Define specific actions, required resources, and key stakeholders.
- Consider regulatory frameworks, financial incentives, and technological needs.
- Establish performance indicators to track progress toward circularity goals.

8.2.2.4. Tools and Resources

- Templates for value chain mapping and Business Model Canvas.
- Case studies from different agri-food industries.
- Digital tools for collaborative mapping and analysis (Miro, MURAL, PowerPoint, Excel).

8.2.2.5. Expected Outcomes

1. A structured visualization of the business value chain and its circularity gaps.

2. Identified opportunities for improving resource efficiency and reducing waste.
3. A revised Business Model Canvas that integrates circular economy principles.
4. A concrete action plan with clear implementation steps.

8.3. IB3: Industrial symbiosis: guidelines with case studies in the agrifood industry

8.3.1. Introduction

Industrial symbiosis (IS) is a key strategy in the transition towards a circular economy, where businesses collaborate to optimise resource use by exchanging materials, energy, water, and by-products. By applying IS principles, industries reduce waste, increase efficiency, and create economic and environmental benefits. In the agri-food sector, which generates significant amounts of organic waste and by-products, IS offers opportunities to transform waste into valuable resources, improving sustainability and competitiveness. Despite its potential, the implementation of IS in the agri-food industry faces several barriers, including regulatory challenges, logistical constraints, lack of stakeholder collaboration, and technological adaptation issues. This guide provides an overview of IS in the agri-food sector, offering practical guidelines for implementation and showcasing successful case studies that highlight its economic and environmental benefits.

8.3.2. Benefits of industrial symbiosis in the agri-food sector

The application of IS in the agri-food sector can lead to multiple advantages, including:

- **Waste reduction:** The repurposing of agricultural and food processing by-products minimises landfill disposal, contributing to reduced environmental pollution and better resource efficiency.
- **Resource efficiency:** By exchanging and reusing materials, water, and energy, industries can lower production costs and reduce dependency on raw materials.
- **Economic gains:** IS facilitates cost savings in waste disposal, opens new revenue streams through the sale of by-products, and enhances supply chain resilience.
- **Environmental sustainability:** The reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, water consumption, and land use contributes to climate change mitigation and improved environmental stewardship.
- **Regulatory compliance:** IS aligns businesses with circular economy policies, corporate sustainability goals, and extended producer responsibility frameworks.

- **Innovation and competitiveness:** By adopting IS practices, companies can develop new products and services, creating business opportunities that improve their market position.

8.3.3. Guidelines for implementing industrial symbiosis

The successful implementation of IS in the agri-food sector requires a structured approach, involving multiple stakeholders, technological adaptation, and policy alignment. Below are five key steps for businesses looking to integrate IS into their operations:

8.3.3.1. Step 1: Identify potential symbiotic relationships

- Conduct a **resource flow analysis** to determine waste streams and by-products that can be repurposed or exchanged.
- Map out **local businesses, suppliers, and industries** that could benefit from material or energy exchanges.
- Engage with **stakeholders**, including research institutions, policymakers, and industry associations, to facilitate partnerships and knowledge-sharing.

8.3.3.2. Step 2: Develop partnerships and collaboration mechanisms

- Establish **formal agreements** between businesses to ensure long-term cooperation and the security of resource-sharing commitments.
- Create **digital platforms** and data-sharing tools to improve transparency, trust, and communication between industrial partners.
- Participate in **eco-industrial parks (EIPs) and regional clusters** to foster resource exchanges and enhance economic synergies.

8.3.3.3. Step 3: Implement technological solutions

- Invest in **processing technologies** such as enzymatic extraction, anaerobic digestion, and biorefining to enhance resource recovery.
- Adopt **waste-to-energy systems**, including biogas generation and cogeneration processes, to improve energy efficiency.

- Utilise **green solvents and sustainable processing techniques** to ensure environmental compliance and minimise resource depletion.

8.3.3.4. Step 4: Address logistical and regulatory challenges

- Ensure that **material exchanges comply with food safety, environmental, and waste management regulations**.
- Develop **efficient transport and storage solutions** to facilitate the movement of by-products between industries while minimising costs.
- Advocate for **policy incentives**, such as tax benefits and subsidies, to support IS adoption and ensure economic viability.

8.3.3.5. Step 5: Monitor, evaluate, and scale up

- Implement **life cycle assessment (LCA) and economic analysis** to quantify the benefits of IS initiatives.
- Continuously **track resource flows and process efficiency** to identify areas for improvement.
- Expand partnerships to **include additional industries and scale up symbiotic networks** across the value chain.

8.3.4. 4. Case studies: successful industrial symbiosis applications

8.3.4.1. Case study 1: upcycling food processing waste into nutraceuticals (Hamam et al., 2023)

- **Location:** Various European food processing companies.
- **Process:** Lemon and artichoke waste are processed using enzymatic and microwave-assisted extraction to produce polyphenol-rich nutraceuticals.
- **Challenges:** High energy consumption and regulatory barriers.
- **Solution:** Optimised purification techniques increased polyphenol stability, allowing successful commercialisation of antioxidant supplements.
- **Outcome:** New nutraceutical products were introduced into the market, demonstrating the economic feasibility of waste valorisation.

8.3.4.2. Case study 2: waste-to-energy conversion in food supply chains (Kostyshak et al., 2024)

- **Location:** Agro-industrial regions implementing anaerobic digestion systems.
- **Process:** Organic food waste is converted into biogas for renewable energy production, reducing reliance on fossil fuels.
- **Challenges:** Initial investment costs and logistical constraints.
- **Solution:** Strategic integration with regional energy networks improved economic feasibility and reduced processing costs.
- **Outcome:** Energy savings of 12–19% in food processing plants, contributing to circular economy goals while lowering emissions.

8.3.4.3. Case study 3: industrial symbiosis in the Lombardy region (Sbaffoni et al., 2022)

- **Location:** Italy, Lombardy region.
- **Process:** By-products from the olive and wine industries are repurposed into bio-oils, natural biosurfactants, and animal feed.
- **Challenges:** Geographic distance between companies and regulatory complexity.
- **Solution:** Coordinated logistics and policy support facilitated material exchanges between businesses.
- **Outcome:** Over 100 synergistic exchanges were identified, increasing sustainability and economic resilience in the region.

8.3.5. 5. References

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8.4. IB4: Creating value from waste in the agro-industry: cases

8.4.1. Introduction

The agro-food industry generates substantial amounts of waste, but through circular economy approaches, these residues can be transformed into valuable resources. This guide provides practical recommendations for businesses and industry stakeholders on how to upcycle agro-food waste into marketable products. The insights are based on findings from the Agro2Circular (A2C) project, specifically work package 4 (WP4), which explored the upcycling of agrifood residues through innovative extraction and formulation techniques.

8.4.2. Key opportunities for upcycling agro-waste

Agricultural waste can be converted into high-value bioactive compounds used in food, nutraceutical, and cosmetic applications. Some of the key opportunities include:

- **Food applications:** Fortifying food products with extracted fibres, antioxidants, and flavonoids.
- **Nutraceuticals:** Using phenolic-rich extracts to develop dietary supplements.
- **Cosmetics:** Formulating natural skincare products with plant-based bioactives.
- **Industrial uses:** Developing biodegradable packaging materials from agro-waste by-products.

8.4.3. Case studies: successful upcycling practices

8.4.3.1. Case study 1: upcycling lemon and artichoke waste into nutraceuticals

- **Process:** Polyphenols and fibres were extracted from lemon and artichoke residues using enzymatic and microwave-assisted extraction.
- **Challenges:** High energy consumption during extraction and difficulties in maintaining polyphenol stability.
- **Solution:** Optimised purification techniques and resin-based concentration increased polyphenol yield and stability.
- **Outcome:** The extracts were successfully used in antioxidant-rich nutraceuticals, meeting market standards for health supplements.

8.4.3.2. Case study 2: enhancing food products with agro-waste extracts

- **Process:** Apple fibre and flavonoid-rich lemon peel extracts were tested in juices, jams, and veggie burgers.
- **Challenges:** Changes in taste and texture at higher extract concentrations.
- **Solution:** Reformulated product compositions to balance nutritional benefits with consumer acceptability.
- **Outcome:** The enriched food products maintained good market appeal while adding value to what would otherwise be waste.

8.4.3.3. Case study 3: industrial implementation of microwave-assisted extraction (MAE)

- **Process:** A 120L pilot-scale microwave reactor was developed to extract polyphenols from agrifood residues.
- **Challenges:** High initial investment and operational energy costs.
- **Solution:** Process efficiency was improved using green solvents and combining MAE with enzymatic pre-treatment.
- **Outcome:** The scaled-up system successfully extracted bioactives with high yield, reducing the need for chemical additives.

8.4.4. Barriers to implementation

Despite the potential of agro-waste valorisation, businesses face several challenges:

1. **Regulatory barriers:** Compliance with food safety and environmental regulations can be complex.
2. **Economic constraints:** Initial investment costs for upcycling technologies can be high.
3. **Technological challenges:** Some extraction processes require advanced equipment and expertise.
4. **Market acceptance:** Consumer perception of waste-derived ingredients can impact product demand.
5. **Supply chain issues:** Seasonal availability of agro-waste affects consistency in raw material sourcing.

8.4.5. Overcoming barriers: recommendations for industry

To successfully create value from agro-waste, businesses should consider the following strategies:

- **Leverage existing incentives:** Seek funding opportunities and government incentives supporting circular economy initiatives.
- **Collaborate with research institutions:** Partnering with universities and innovation hubs can provide technological support.
- **Invest in scalable technologies:** Start with pilot-scale projects before full industrial implementation.
- **Optimise processing techniques:** Implement energy-efficient extraction methods and green solvents to reduce operational costs.
- **Raise consumer awareness:** Engage in marketing campaigns that highlight the environmental benefits of upcycled products.

8.4.6. Future perspectives

The Agro2Circular project has demonstrated that upcycling agro-waste is a viable and sustainable business opportunity. Future developments will focus on:

- **Larger-scale demonstration projects:** Expanding pilot projects to full industrial production.
- **Integration with other circular economy practices:** Combining upcycling with renewable energy and biodegradable packaging solutions.
- **Regulatory advancements:** Advocating for policies that facilitate the market adoption of bio-waste-based products.

8.5. IB5: Funding opportunities for the circular economy: infosheet

8.5.1. 1. European Union Funds

The EU provides several funding schemes to support circular economy initiatives in the industry and business sector. Key programmes include:

- **Horizon Europe:** Supports research and innovation projects with a budget of €95.5 billion for 2021-2027. SMEs can benefit through the European Innovation Council (EIC), which funds high-risk, high-potential innovations.
- **European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) & Cohesion Fund (CF):** Provides funding for regional circular economy initiatives, waste management, and sustainable business models.
- **LIFE Programme:** Focuses on environmental and climate action, with €1.3 billion allocated to circular economy projects.
- **Single Market Programme (SMP):** Supports SMEs in sustainability, digitalisation, and access to European markets.

8.5.2. 2. Financial Institutions and Circular Economy Investments

Several financial institutions offer investment and funding mechanisms for circular economy projects:

- **European Investment Bank (EIB):** Provides loans and advisory services for circular economy businesses, particularly SMEs, through the European Fund for Strategic Investments (EFSI).
- **Joint Initiative on Circular Economy (JICE):** A partnership of European banks that has committed up to €16 billion to circular economy projects.
- **European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD):** Offers financing for SMEs and circular economy models, focusing on sustainability and resource efficiency.
- **World Bank Group:** Funds municipal solid waste management and circular economy projects in developing regions.

8.5.3. 3. Private Investments and Alternative Funding Sources

- **Green Bonds:** Issued by institutions such as the EIB and World Bank to finance sustainable projects.
- **Investment Funds:** Dedicated funds like Circularity Capital and the Circular Innovation Fund provide venture capital for circular businesses.
- **Crowdfunding:** Platforms like Kickstarter and GoFundMe offer alternative financing routes for small-scale circular economy projects.

8.5.4. 4. National and Regional Public Funding Schemes

Several EU member states and regions provide specific funding to industry and businesses:

- **Spain (Region of Murcia Example):**
 - **INFO Murcia Grants:** Support for energy efficiency, R&D, eco-innovation, and sustainability projects.
 - **Agricultural Sector Funding:** Grants for circular agri-food initiatives, including support for sustainable farming and water reuse.

8.5.5. 5. Private Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia

Private financing plays a crucial role in driving the growth and development of circular economy initiatives. By providing essential capital, expertise, and networks, private funding enables businesses to scale, innovate, and advance their sustainability goals.

The optimal financing mechanism for a circular economy project depends on its development stage and unique business model. Early-stage ventures may rely on angel investors or venture capital firms, while more established companies might seek funding from private equity funds or institutional investors.

The following sections outline the key private financing options available for circular economy initiatives, categorized into two main groups:

1. **Bank and Financial Cooperative Systems:** Examines traditional debt financing options, such as loans and green loans, as well as other financial products offered by banks and cooperative banks.

- 2. Alternative Private Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia:** Explores a broader spectrum of financing mechanisms, including equity financing, crowdfunding, leasing, and impact investing.

8.5.5.1.5.1 Bank and Financial Cooperatives Schemes

Traditional banking institutions, including commercial banks and cooperative banks, offer a range of financing mechanisms that can be tailored to the specific needs of circular economy initiatives. These institutions often provide debt-based financing, such as loans and green loans, as well as other financial products like guarantees and leasing. An overview of the different private financing mechanisms is given in the table below.

Financial Mechanism	Sub-type	Description
Debt	Loans	Traditional debt financing, often secured by collateral. Can be used for various purposes, including working capital, equipment purchases, and facility expansion.
	Green Loans	Loans specifically designed to finance environmentally friendly projects, such as renewable energy, energy efficiency, and waste reduction.
	Bonds	Debt securities issued by banks or corporations to raise capital. While not as common for smaller businesses, some cooperative banks may offer bond issuance services.
	Green Bonds	Bonds specifically issued to finance environmental projects, such as renewable energy, clean transportation, and sustainable agriculture.
Alternative forms of funding	Guarantees	Financial instruments that guarantee repayment of a loan, reducing the risk for lenders and improving access to credit.

	Leasing	A financing arrangement where the bank purchases an asset and leases it to the borrower. This can be particularly useful for financing equipment or vehicles.
Equity	Equity Investments	In some cases, banks, especially development banks, may invest equity in promising circular economy ventures, particularly those with a strong social or environmental impact.

In Spain, the Bank of Spain has demonstrated its commitment to the sustainable economy through the analysis of climate change impacts and the transition towards a more sustainable growth model in its research agenda.

Key Regional Financial Institutions Supporting Circular Economy:

- **Cajamar Cooperative Group:** Focuses on the agri-food sector and supports businesses through sustainable financing initiatives, R&D, and innovation.
- **CaixaBank:** Offers sustainability-linked loans, green loans, and eco-financing lines for various environmental projects.
- **Banco Sabadell:** Promotes sustainability through financing circular economy projects and supporting SMEs in sustainable transitions.
- **Banco Santander:** Implements sustainability grants and green financing programs, including funding for energy efficiency and self-consumption projects.

8.5.5.2.5.2 Alternative Private Financing Schemes in the Region of Murcia

- **Venture Capital (VC):** Firms such as Murcia Emprrende invest in early-stage circular economy startups with high growth potential.
- **Private Equity:** Large national and international private equity funds invest in sustainable businesses.
- **Crowdfunding:** Platforms like Kickstarter and Indiegogo enable businesses to raise funds for sustainability-focused projects.
- **Angel Investors:** Networks like MurciaBan connect business angels with entrepreneurs in the region.

8.5.6. 6. Good Practices in Financing the Circular Economy

- **CIRCWASTE (Finland):** EU LIFE-funded project supporting waste management and circular economy initiatives.
- **URBIOFIN (Spain & EU partners):** Demonstrating the transformation of municipal solid waste into new biobased products.
- **Murcia Circular Economy for Businesses:** Regional efforts to integrate sustainability into business models through financial and advisory support.
- **EIB Financed Circular Projects:** Notable investments in biochemicals, food waste management, and waste-to-energy transitions.

8.5.7. 7. Financing Recommendations

- Businesses should explore a mix of public and private funding sources.
- Engaging financial advisory services is crucial for securing funding.
- Circular businesses should leverage innovative financing mechanisms such as green bonds and impact investments.
- Developing clear sustainability reporting measures can enhance access to financing.
- Multi-stakeholder collaboration is key to successful circular economy funding.

For further details on specific funding schemes, visit the official websites of regional and European funding institutions.

8.5.8. 8. How to Access These Funding Opportunities

1. **Identify Suitable Programmes:** Review eligibility criteria and match your business model to the most appropriate scheme.
2. **Prepare a Strong Proposal:** Clearly define objectives, expected outcomes, and alignment with circular economy goals.
3. **Leverage Advisory Services:** Institutions like the EIB and national development agencies provide guidance on funding applications.
4. **Explore Co-Funding Options:** Many programmes encourage combining multiple funding sources for broader financial support.

For more details, visit the respective programme websites or consult national and regional funding agencies.

8.6. IB6: Circular Economy regulation in the agrifood sector: infosheet

The transition to a circular economy is reshaping the agri-food sector, with evolving EU regulations requiring businesses to adopt more sustainable practices. This infosheet provides a practical guide to the key regulatory developments affecting the industry, covering packaging, food waste, water and nutrient management, biodiversity, sustainable production, and livestock farming. Designed for **agri-food businesses**, this document highlights the main regulatory obligations, business implications, and opportunities for innovation. It also outlines the most relevant standards that support compliance and best practices, helping companies navigate the regulatory landscape and improve their sustainability performance.

8.6.1. Packaging Regulation and Its Implications for Agri-food Businesses

- **EU Packaging Waste Reduction Targets (Directive 94/62/EC – Revision in Progress)**
 - All packaging must be **reusable or recyclable in an economically viable way by 2030**.
 - Businesses must **reduce over-packaging and prevent packaging waste**, with potential new reduction targets.
 - Restrictions on **certain packaging materials** may be introduced, particularly where reusable alternatives exist.
 - **Complexity of packaging materials** should be minimised by reducing the number of polymers used.
- **Impact on Agri-food Businesses**
 - Need to **redesign packaging** to meet recyclability and reuse criteria.
 - Increased **pressure to phase out certain packaging materials** (e.g., multi-layer plastics).
 - Businesses may face **higher compliance costs** for non-recyclable packaging.
 - **EU-wide labelling system for packaging waste** may require adjustments to packaging design.

- New **rules on plastic recycling for food contact materials** will affect packaging choices in the food sector.
- **Opportunities for the Sector**
 - Innovation in **bio-based and compostable packaging solutions** (e.g., ISO 18604, EN 17033).
 - Investment in **closed-loop packaging systems** (reuse/refill models).
 - Improved brand reputation through **eco-friendly packaging initiatives**.

8.6.2. Food Waste and Circular Economy in the Agri-food Sector

- **EU Food Waste Reduction Target (Directive 2008/98/EC – Review Underway)**
 - Aims to reduce **20% of all food produced** that is currently wasted in the EU.
 - Businesses will need to **optimise food production and distribution** to cut waste.
 - Strengthened **Farm to Fork Strategy** to address sustainability across the food supply chain.
- **Impact on Agri-food Businesses**
 - **Mandatory waste reduction targets** for food producers and retailers.
 - Increased focus on **redistribution of surplus food** (e.g., donation incentives, waste valorisation).
 - Stricter **traceability requirements** for food waste reporting.
 - Potential regulations to **phase out single-use packaging, tableware, and cutlery in food services**.
- **Opportunities for the Sector**
 - Development of **valorisation technologies** for food by-products (e.g., bio-based fertilisers, animal feed, bioplastics).
 - Investment in **digital solutions** to optimise food logistics and reduce waste.
 - Growth of **food upcycling initiatives** and alternative uses for surplus products.

8.6.3. Water and Nutrient Management in Agri-food Processing

- **Water Reuse Regulation and Nutrient Management (EU Sustainable Products Initiative & Water Reuse Regulation 2020)**

- Encourages **reuse of treated wastewater** in agriculture and industrial processes.
- Development of an **Integrated Nutrient Management Plan** to optimise fertiliser use.
- Potential **review of wastewater treatment and sewage sludge directives**.
- **Impact on Agri-food Businesses**
 - Stricter rules on **water efficiency and wastewater treatment** in food production.
 - New obligations for **recovered nutrient use** in fertilisers.
 - Increased demand for **on-site water recycling solutions** in food processing plants.
- **Opportunities for the Sector**
 - Adoption of **circular water systems** to reduce dependency on freshwater resources.
 - Investment in **nutrient recovery technologies** (e.g., phosphate extraction, bio-based fertilisers).
 - Potential for **certification schemes** for water-efficient food production.

8.6.4. Biodiversity and Sustainable Agriculture

- **EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 – Impact on Agriculture**
 - Focus on **preserving biodiversity** in agricultural landscapes.
 - 10% of farmland must include **high-diversity landscape features** (e.g., hedgerows, buffer zones, fallow land).
 - Expansion of **eco-schemes and result-based payment schemes** in the CAP.
- **Impact on Agri-food Businesses**
 - Stricter requirements for **sustainable land management** and biodiversity restoration.
 - Increased funding for **organic farming and agroecology practices**.
 - Potential phasing out of **chemical pesticides** (50% reduction target by 2030).
- **Opportunities for the Sector**
 - Incentives for **organic and regenerative farming**.

- Potential revenue streams from **carbon sequestration initiatives**.
- Growth of **biodiversity certification schemes** for food products.

8.6.5. Sustainable Food Production and Carbon Farming

- **Farm to Fork Strategy – Transforming Agri-food Production**
 - Targets **50% reduction in pesticide use** by 2030.
 - Focus on **carbon farming as a business model** (e.g., rewarding CO2 sequestration).
 - Promotion of **bio-based industries** (e.g., bio-fertilisers, bioenergy, protein feed).
- **Impact on Agri-food Businesses**
 - Stricter rules on **pesticide reduction and alternative pest control methods**.
 - More investment required in **precision farming and digital monitoring systems**.
 - New **certification framework for carbon sequestration** in agriculture.
- **Opportunities for the Sector**
 - Market incentives for **sustainable feed alternatives** (e.g., insect-based proteins, algae-based feeds).
 - Expansion of **biogas and anaerobic digestion** facilities using food waste and manure.
 - Financial support for **solar energy and renewable solutions** on farms.

8.6.6. Sustainable Animal Farming and Livestock Feed

- **Reducing the Environmental Impact of Livestock Farming**
 - Aim to cut **livestock-related greenhouse gas emissions**.
 - **50% reduction in antibiotic use** in animal farming by 2030.
 - Development of **sustainable feed alternatives** (e.g., insect protein, marine feedstocks).
- **Impact on Agri-food Businesses**
 - Stricter requirements for **animal welfare and antibiotic use**.
 - Need for **alternative feed sources** to reduce reliance on imported soy.
 - Increased regulation of **GHG emissions from livestock farming**.

- **Opportunities for the Sector**

- Growth of **low-carbon livestock farming initiatives**.
- Expansion of **alternative protein markets** for animal feed.
- Investment in **precision livestock monitoring technologies**.

8.6.7. 7Green Labelling, Consumer Trust, and Market Access

- **Stronger Green Claims and Certification Requirements**

- EU considering **eco-labelling schemes for sustainable food**.
- Potential **mandatory sustainability disclosures** for food products.

- **Impact on Agri-food Businesses**

- Stricter requirements for **substantiating green claims**.
- Need for **full lifecycle assessments of food products**.
- Increased **consumer demand for sustainable and organic products**.

- **Opportunities for the Sector**

- Expansion of **organic farming and certified sustainable products**.
- Growth in **plant-based, regenerative, and carbon-neutral food brands**.
- Development of **traceability solutions** to verify sustainability claims.

8.6.8. 8. Relevant Standards for Circular Economy in the Agri-food Sector

8.6.8.1.1. Packaging Standards

- **ISO 18604** – Packaging and the environment: Material recycling.
- **EN 17033** – Biodegradable mulch films for use in agriculture and horticulture.
- **CEN/TC 194** – Standards for packaging materials in contact with food.

8.6.8.2.2. Food Waste and Circular Economy Standards

- **ISO 22000** – Food safety management systems.
- **ISO 20001 (Draft)** – Food loss and waste management system.
- **CWA 18149:2024** – Guidelines for characterisation of extracts from agro-food waste.

8.6.8.3.3. Water and Nutrient Management Standards

- **ISO 14046** – Water footprint – Principles, requirements, and guidelines.

- **ISO 16620** – Bio-based content determination in materials and products.
- **EN 16751** – Sustainability criteria for bio-based products.

8.6.8.4.4. Biodiversity and Sustainable Agriculture Standards

- **ISO 14001** – Environmental management systems.
- **ISO 14055** – Guidelines for sustainable land management.
- **CEN/TC 411** – Bio-based products.

8.6.8.5.5. Sustainable Food Production and Carbon Farming Standards

- **ISO 14064** – Greenhouse gas measurement and reporting.
- **EN 16760** – Life cycle analysis of bio-based products.
- **ISO 59020** – Circular economy performance measurement.

8.6.8.6.6. Sustainable Animal Farming and Livestock Feed Standards

- **ISO 22005** – Traceability in feed and food chain.
- **ISO 34700** – Animal welfare management.
- **EN 16785-2** – Bio-based content determination in feed.

8.7. IB7: Regulation of the circular economy in Spanish industry: a guide for companies.

The transition to a circular economy in Spain is shaped by an evolving regulatory framework that impacts key industrial sectors. This guide provides practical information on the main national and regional regulations affecting businesses regarding by-products, end-of-waste status, and secondary raw material markets. Targeted at companies and industrial stakeholders, this factsheet highlights legal obligations, opportunities, and support mechanisms to facilitate the adoption of circular solutions in Spanish industry. Key topics covered include:

- **By-product and end-of-waste status** – Regulations enabling material reuse instead of classification as waste.
- **Incentives and barriers in secondary raw materials markets.**
- **Sector-specific regulations**, including for the agri-food, plastics, and industrial waste sectors.
- **Regional strategies and tools available for businesses.**

8.7.1. 1. General Regulatory Framework for the Circular Economy in Spain

Spain has developed a set of regulations aligned with European directives to facilitate the transition to a circular economy. The most relevant regulations include:

Regulation	Type (Law, Order, Regulation, Directive)	Year	Key Aspects	Impact on the Agri-Food Sector
Law 7/2022 on Waste and Contaminated Soils for a Circular Economy	National Law	2022	Defines by-products and end-of-waste status	Allows the reuse of fruit and vegetable residues in bioproducts

Regulation	Type (Law, Order, Regulation, Directive)	Year	Key Aspects	Impact on the Agri-Food Sector
Murcia Circular Economy Strategy	Regional Strategy	2021	Promotes the reuse of agri-food by-products	Supports projects such as Agro2Circular
Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste	European Directive	2008	Establishes the legal framework for waste management in the EU	Introduces by-product and end-of-waste concepts and defines conditions under which materials qualify
Murcia Regional Waste Plan 2016-2020	Regional Plan	2016	Promotes resource efficiency and transition to a circular economy	Paves the way for sustainable, competitive development and new business activities
Spanish Circular Economy Strategy 2030	National Strategy	2020	Reduces resource consumption and waste in all sectors, promoting reuse, recycling, and material recovery	Reduces food waste, promotes the use of agri-food by-products and sustainable fertilisers, fosters circular bioeconomy, and encourages water reuse and sustainable production and consumption
Order TED/646/2023 of 9 June	Ministerial Order	2023	Specifies which thermoplastic waste treated for final recovery ceases to be classified as	Admissible waste includes plastic waste, excluding packaging from agriculture, horticulture,

Regulation	Type (Law, Order, Regulation, Directive)	Year	Key Aspects	Impact on the Agri-Food Sector
			waste under the European Waste List	aquaculture, forestry, hunting, and fishing
Order TEC/852/2019 of 25 July	Ministerial Order	2019	Defines when polymeric material production waste used in the manufacture of silage film is considered a by-product	Facilitates decision-making on whether to classify such production waste as a by-product

8.7.2. 2. Regulation of By-products and End-of-Waste Status

Law 7/2022 establishes the regulatory framework distinguishing between waste and by-products in Spain. According to this regulation, a material is considered a **by-product** rather than waste if it meets four conditions:

1. It is generated as part of an intentional production process.
2. It can be used directly without further processing.
3. It complies with legal and environmental standards.
4. There is a guaranteed market for its use.

◆ **Example:** Fruit and vegetable residues that can be transformed into bioplastics or cosmetic ingredients.

A material ceases to be classified as waste and is recognised as a **useful product** under the **end-of-waste status** if it meets the following criteria:

- A specific and defined use.
- Existing market demand.
- Compliance with technical and environmental standards.
- No negative environmental impact.

◆ **Example:** Recovered multilayer plastics that, after processing, can be used for manufacturing new packaging.

8.7.3. 3. Secondary Raw Material Markets and Current Barriers

Access to secondary raw material markets in Spain remains challenging due to a **lack of regulatory harmonisation** and uncertainty regarding the legal status of certain materials.

Businesses face barriers such as:

- ✓ Lengthy bureaucratic processes and approval times for end-of-waste certification.
- ✓ High costs associated with the management and certification of by-products.
- ✓ Difficulties in ensuring **traceability and quality control** of recycled materials.
- ✓ **Lack of effective financial incentives** for the use of secondary materials.

8.7.4. 4. Regulation and Opportunities in Key Sectors

8.7.4.1. 🍷 Agri-Food Sector

- **Order TEC/852/2019** establishes criteria for considering certain silage film waste as by-products.
- **Murcia Circular Economy Strategy** promotes the use of agri-food by-products in the bioeconomy.
 - ◆ **Example:** Fruit skins and residues can be transformed into cosmetics or bio-based fertilisers.

8.7.4.2. 🗑️ Plastics and Packaging Sector

- **Order TED/646/2023** defines when certain processed thermoplastic wastes cease to be classified as waste.
- **Law 7/2022** mandates minimum recycled content in plastics.
 - ◆ **Example:** Recycled plastics from the food industry can be used for new sustainable packaging.

8.7.4.3. Industry and Construction

- The **EU Construction and Demolition Waste Directive** promotes material reuse in construction.
- **Regional plans** encourage the recovery of recycled aggregates and industrial by-products.
 - ◆ **Example:** Processed demolition waste can be used for new infrastructure materials.

8.7.5. Utilisation and Recovery of Residual Biomass in the Agri-Food Sector

The recovery of residual biomass in the agri-food sector is crucial for the circular bioeconomy, allowing waste to be transformed into bioproducts with applications in food, cosmetics, chemicals, and energy. With an annual production of **78 million tonnes of biomass** in Spain, leveraging these resources is key to **reducing environmental impact** and **enhancing industrial competitiveness**.

8.7.5.1. Regulatory Framework and Opportunities

The regulatory framework promotes waste recovery, with key policies including:

- **European Bioeconomy Strategy**
- **Law 7/2022 on Waste**
- **CAP 2023-2027**

EU projects such as **Agro2Circular**, **Up4Health**, and **NeoGIANT** demonstrate the feasibility of reusing residual biomass in the agri-food industry.

8.7.5.2. Standardisation in Residual Biomass Recovery

Standardisation plays a key role in establishing the **market for bioproducts** derived from residual biomass. UNE, as Spain's official standardisation body, works on setting criteria and methodologies through its participation in:

- **ISO/TC 323 Circular Economy**
- **CEN/TC 411 Bio-based Products**

1. Criteria for By-Product and End-of-Waste Status

- **Legislation:** Law 7/2022 establishes conditions for classifying materials as by-products rather than waste.
- **Ministerial Orders:** Regulations such as **Order TED/646/2023** define criteria for when certain thermoplastics cease to be classified as waste.
- **Standardisation:** Defining technical requirements to **convert waste into by-products** and facilitate their acceptance in the market.

2. Methods for Biomass Characterisation

- **CEN/TC 444 Environmental Characterisation of Solid Matrices** develops standards for identifying and characterising organic waste and biomass.
- **Standardised Methods Include:**
 - **UNE-EN 16168:2012** (Total nitrogen determination in treated biological waste).
 - **UNE-EN 16457:2014** (Framework for waste testing and analysis).
 - **CWA 18149:2024** (Guidelines for characterising extracts from agri-food waste).
- Methodologies are being developed to **ensure quality, traceability, and industrial compatibility** of transformed biomass.

3. Sustainability Requirements and Life Cycle Assessment for Bioproducts

- **ISO 59020** (Measuring and assessing circularity performance) establishes criteria for evaluating the environmental impact of bioproducts.
- **Other Standards in Development Include:**
 - **PNE-prEN 18027** (Guidelines for comparing the life cycle of bio-based and fossil-based products).
 - **UNE-EN 16751:2016** (Sustainability criteria for bio-based products).

8.7.6. Tools and Resources for Businesses

Resource	Entity	Access
By-Product Assessment	Ministry for Ecological Transition (MITECO)	View procedure

Resource	Entity	Access
Environmental Regulations	Official State Gazette (BOE)	Consult BOE
End-of-Waste Certification in Spain	Eurofins Environment Spain	Interpretation note
Regional Circular Economy Strategies	Regional Governments	[Check each regional government's website]

8.8. IB8: Data Integration System (DIS) tool

8.8.1. What is the DIS tool and how was it created?

The A2C Data Integration System (DIS) is an advanced digital tool designed to improve traceability, data integration, and decision-making in circular economy processes. Developed as part of the Agro2Circular (A2C) project, it provides a structured framework to track waste streams, optimise resource recovery, and ensure regulatory compliance in industries transitioning to sustainable practices. The DIS was developed through collaboration between leading technology and sustainability partners, integrating insights from real-world waste management challenges. By combining blockchain technology, artificial intelligence, and cloud computing, it offers a secure, transparent, and efficient way to manage waste and secondary raw materials across the entire value chain.

8.8.2. Key Functionalities – What does the DIS do?

The DIS tool is a powerful, easy-to-use digital platform that enables:

- ✔ **Real-time Waste Traceability:** Tracks materials from production to recycling, ensuring full visibility of waste flows.
- ✔ **Blockchain-Backed Security:** Guarantees tamper-proof traceability and prevents fraud or data manipulation.
- ✔ **AI-Driven Decision Support:** Uses predictive analytics to identify the best waste recovery strategies, helping businesses reduce costs and environmental impact.
- ✔ **Digital Product Passports (DPPs):** Provides detailed information on materials, helping manufacturers, recyclers, and consumers verify sustainability claims.
- ✔ **Regulatory Compliance Support:** Simplifies Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) and sustainability reporting, helping companies meet EU circular economy targets.
- ✔ **Industry-Wide Integration:** Aligns with international standards (EPCIS 2.0, GS1, JSON-LD) for seamless data exchange across different industries and value chains.

8.8.3. Who Should Use the DIS tool?

The DIS tool is designed for businesses, industries, and policymakers aiming to implement circular economy principles and improve sustainability practices. Key users include:

 Manufacturers & Producers: To track materials, optimise resource efficiency, and reduce waste costs.

 Recycling & Waste Management Companies: To improve sorting, enhance recycling efficiency, and ensure compliance with EU sustainability regulations.

 Sustainability & CSR Managers: To monitor, report, and verify sustainability performance across operations.

 Policymakers & Public Authorities: To assess regional circular economy progress, set targets, and enforce compliance.

 Entrepreneurs & Startups in Circular Economy: To develop innovative business models based on waste valorisation and sustainable packaging.

8.8.4. Why Should You Use the DIS tool?

◆ **Save Time & Reduce Costs:** Automates traceability, compliance, and reporting.

◆ **Enhance Transparency & Trust:** Ensures material traceability and prevents greenwashing.

◆ **Make Smarter Decisions:** AI-driven insights improve waste valorisation and recycling efficiency.

◆ **Comply with Regulations Easily:** Meets EU Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) requirements.

◆ **Adapt to Any Industry:** Suitable for plastics, agrifood, textiles, e-waste, construction, and more.

8.8.5. A2C Data Integration System (DIS) – User Instructions

Getting Started

The A2C Data Integration System (DIS) is a digital platform designed to improve waste traceability, decision-making, and resource efficiency within circular economy processes. It integrates real-time data tracking, blockchain security, and AI-driven analytics to enhance sustainability in industries such as agrifood, plastic recycling, and waste management.

To access the DIS platform, users need:

- ✓ An authorised account (for registered users).
- ✓ A compatible device (computer or mobile).
- ✓ A stable internet connection to interact with the cloud-based system.

1. Logging In

- Go to the DIS web platform.
- Click on "Login" at the top right corner.
- Enter your username and password (provided by the system administrator).
- Once logged in, you will be redirected to the Dashboard, where you can access various tools and data.

2. Navigating the Dashboard

The Dashboard provides a quick overview of waste streams, material traceability, and sustainability indicators. Key features include:

- ◆ Live updates on waste reception, processing, and recycling.
- ◆ Statistics & reports on material flows and resource recovery.
- ◆ User-specific access based on roles (waste producers, recyclers, manufacturers, etc.).

3. Key Functionalities

A) Traceability Tool (For waste producers, recyclers, and manufacturers)

How to Track Waste Movements:

- ✓ Scan the QR code assigned to each waste batch.
- ✓ View detailed information such as origin, material type, and processing status.
- ✓ Generate and download traceability reports for compliance and verification.

B) QR Identification App (For field operations)

 How to Use the QR App:

- Scan waste batch QR codes with a mobile device.
- Confirm waste acceptance, processing, or transfer in real-time.
- Ensure compliance by checking material specifications and regulatory status.

C) Decision Support Tool (DST) (For optimising waste valorisation)

 How to Use the DST:

- Analyse data trends in waste generation and processing.
- Compare different recycling or upcycling options using AI recommendations.
- Access predictive analytics to forecast waste availability and optimise logistics.

4. Who Can Use the DIS?

The DIS is designed for various industry stakeholders, including:

- ✓ Waste Producers & Managers → To track materials and ensure compliance.
- ✓ Recyclers & Manufacturers → To optimise resource recovery.
- ✓ Sustainability & CSR Managers → To improve environmental performance.
- ✓ Policymakers & Researchers → To develop and monitor circular economy strategies.

5. Need More Information?

For a complete guide and technical documentation, visit:

 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036838/results>

Search for these documents:

- A2C_D1.10 – Data Integration System (BETA Version)
- A2C_D6.2 – Data Integration System v1.0
- A2C_Deliverable_D1.13 – A2C Data Integration System (Public Summary)

8.9. IB9: Standardisation: guidelines for the agrifood industry

8.9.1. 1. Introduction and Objectives of the Guide

8.9.1.1. *Why Standardisation is Important in the Agri-Food Industry*

In the agri-food sector, standardisation plays a crucial role in ensuring product safety, quality, and sustainability. Standards provide a common framework for companies to operate efficiently, comply with regulatory requirements, and meet consumer expectations. By following recognised standards, businesses can enhance trust, transparency, and traceability across the entire food supply chain, from raw material sourcing to processing, packaging, and distribution.

Standardisation is particularly relevant for addressing emerging challenges in the agri-food industry, such as:

- Food safety concerns, including contamination risks and the presence of harmful substances.
- Sustainability issues, such as reducing waste, optimising resource use, and adopting circular economy principles.
- Global market access, as compliance with international standards is often a prerequisite for exporting products.
- Consumer demands, which increasingly focus on food quality, nutritional value, and environmental impact.

As the agri-food industry evolves, adopting standards helps companies stay competitive, innovate, and align with best practices in production, processing, and distribution.

8.9.1.2. *Benefits of Following Standards in the Agri-Food Sector*

Adhering to national, European, and international standards provides a range of benefits for businesses, regulators, and consumers alike.

8.9.1.3. *Food Safety and Consumer Protection*

- Compliance with food safety regulations (e.g., ISO 22000, HACCP) helps prevent contamination and foodborne illnesses.

- Traceability systems ensure rapid identification and recall of unsafe products.
- Standardised hygiene and processing practices reduce risks in food handling and production.

8.9.1.4. Sustainability and Circular Economy Integration

- Promotes efficient use of natural resources (water, energy, raw materials).
- Encourages the use of sustainable packaging solutions, such as biodegradable and recyclable materials.
- Reduces food waste through better inventory management and valorisation of by-products.

8.9.1.5. Operational Efficiency and Cost Reduction

- Optimises production processes, reducing errors and waste.
- Improves interoperability between different systems and supply chain partners.
- Enhances quality control, ensuring consistency and reducing product rejections.

8.9.1.6. Competitiveness and Market Access

- Facilitates exports by ensuring compliance with international standards.
- Supports certification schemes (e.g., organic, fair trade) that enhance brand reputation.
- Aligns with retailer and consumer expectations, increasing market opportunities.

8.9.1.7. Innovation and Technological Development

- Supports the introduction of new materials, processes, and digital solutions.
- Facilitates the adoption of smart farming, digital traceability, and blockchain technologies.
- Encourages investment in research and development for sustainable food production.

8.9.1.8. Standardisation and the Circular Economy: How It Helps the Sector

The transition to a circular economy is becoming a priority in the agri-food industry, and standardisation plays a key role in enabling this shift. Circular economy principles focus on reducing waste, reusing materials, and recycling resources, and standards help businesses implement these principles in a structured and effective way.

8.9.1.9. How Standards Contribute to a Circular Agri-Food System

- Sustainable sourcing: Guidelines for responsibly sourcing raw materials (e.g., CEN/TC 411 on bio-based products).
- Waste management: Standards on waste classification and valorisation (e.g., CEN/TC 444 on biowaste).
- Upcycling of by-products: Quality and safety requirements for using agricultural residues in food, cosmetics, and other industries.
- Sustainable packaging: Development of biodegradable and recyclable materials in line with EN 17033 and ISO 18604.
- Resource efficiency: Energy and water consumption standards to improve efficiency across production processes.

8.9.1.10. The Role of Standards in Circular Economy Innovation

- Creating consistent definitions and methodologies for measuring circularity (ISO 59020).
- Providing guidelines for eco-design and recyclability of products (ISO 14006).
- Supporting the integration of digital traceability (ISO/IEC 18004 on QR codes, ISO/TC 307 on blockchain applications).

8.9.2. Standardisation in the Agri-Food Industry

8.9.2.1. What is Standardisation?

Standardisation is the process of developing and applying technical documents that establish consistent requirements, guidelines, or characteristics for products, processes, or

services. In the agri-food industry, standardisation helps ensure food safety, quality, sustainability, and interoperability across the supply chain.

Standards are voluntary in principle, but they often align with regulatory requirements and are widely used to facilitate compliance. In some cases, certification schemes based on standards provide businesses with recognised proof of compliance, helping them access markets and build consumer trust.

Standardisation can take different forms:

- **Standards:** Documents that define best practices, methods, or requirements (e.g., ISO 22000 for food safety management).
- **Technical specifications:** More detailed technical requirements for a specific application.
- **Technical reports:** Informative documents that compile best practices or recommendations.
- **Regulations:** Binding legal requirements, often referencing standards for implementation.

8.9.2.2. Key Standardisation Bodies in the Agri-Food Sector

Several organisations develop and maintain standards relevant to the agri-food industry. These include international, European, and national bodies, as well as regulatory agencies that oversee food safety and public health.

International Organization for Standardization (ISO)

ISO is the world's leading organisation for developing voluntary international standards. Its work covers various aspects of the agri-food industry, including food safety (ISO 22000), environmental management (ISO 14001), and circular economy principles (ISO 59020). ISO standards provide a globally recognised framework for ensuring quality and compliance across international markets.

European Committee for Standardisation (CEN)

CEN is responsible for developing European standards (EN) that apply across EU member states. It works closely with ISO, adopting international standards where possible while addressing specific European regulatory and market needs. In the agri-food sector, CEN standards cover areas such as food packaging (CEN/TC 261), biowaste (CEN/TC 444), and sustainable agriculture.

Spanish Association for Standardisation (UNE)

UNE is Spain's national standardisation body, responsible for developing Spanish standards (UNE) and adopting European (EN) and international (ISO) standards. In the agri-food sector, UNE provides guidance on food quality, traceability, and sustainability, ensuring alignment with EU and global frameworks.

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

Although EFSA does not develop standards, it plays a key role in regulating food safety in the EU. EFSA conducts scientific risk assessments and provides guidance on contaminants, food additives, and novel foods. Many standards related to food safety are aligned with EFSA recommendations and European regulations.

8.9.2.3. Types of Standardisation Documents

Different types of documents exist within the standardisation system, each serving a specific purpose:

- **International Standards (ISO, IEC):** Developed by global standardisation bodies to ensure harmonised practices worldwide.
- **European Standards (EN):** Developed by CEN and adopted by all EU member states. These must be implemented at the national level, replacing conflicting national standards.
- **National Standards (UNE, BSI, DIN, AFNOR, etc.):** Developed by individual countries, often aligned with European or international standards.
- **Technical Specifications (TS):** More specific than general standards, often used in emerging technologies or sectors where full standardisation is still evolving.
- **Technical Reports (TR):** Informative documents that provide guidance but do not impose mandatory requirements.
- **Regulations and Directives:** Legal requirements set by governments or the EU, sometimes referring to standards for implementation.

Key Areas of Standardisation in the Agri-Food Industry

Standardisation in the agri-food industry covers a wide range of areas, helping businesses improve efficiency, ensure food safety, and adopt sustainable practices. This section outlines key standardisation areas with a focus on practical applications for businesses.

8.9.3. Circularity Standards in the Agri-Food Industry

The transition towards a circular economy is a priority for the agri-food sector. Standardisation plays a key role in supporting businesses to adopt circular practices by providing guidelines for product design, waste management, and bio-based materials.

8.9.3.1. Product and Process Design for Circularity

Applying circular economy principles in the agri-food sector involves designing products and production processes that minimise waste, optimise resource use, and enable recycling or upcycling. Standards such as **ISO 14006** provide guidelines for integrating eco-design into environmental management systems, ensuring that sustainability is embedded in product development from the start.

For example:

- **Packaging materials:** Using bio-based or compostable packaging to reduce plastic waste.
- **Food production:** Designing processes that allow the reuse of by-products, such as converting fruit peels into natural food additives or animal feed.

8.9.3.2. Agri-Food Waste and By-Product Management

The efficient management of agricultural and food industry waste is essential to reducing environmental impact and improving resource efficiency. Standardised approaches help businesses classify, process, and valorise their waste streams.

Key areas where standards are applied include:

- **Organic waste composting:** Following specific methodologies for biodegradability and compostability testing to ensure food and packaging waste can be safely returned to the environment.
- **Upcycling food waste:** Establishing clear criteria for the transformation of food processing by-products into new ingredients, such as using spent grain from breweries in baked goods.
- **Biowaste characterisation:** Standards such as **ISO 14044** (Life Cycle Assessment) help assess the environmental impact of different waste management options, supporting better decision-making.

8.9.3.3. Use of Bio-Based Products

Bio-based products are derived from renewable sources, reducing dependence on fossil fuels and promoting sustainable production models. The European standard **EN 16751** defines sustainability criteria for bio-based products, ensuring transparency and consistency in their production and labelling.

Examples include:

- **Bio-based plastics** for food packaging, which decompose more easily in natural environments.
- **Natural food additives and ingredients** extracted from agricultural by-products, such as plant-based proteins and fibres.
- **Biodegradable mulching films** used in farming to protect soil and improve crop yields while reducing plastic pollution.

8.9.4. Quality and Safety in Food Products

Ensuring food safety and quality is one of the main priorities of the agri-food industry. Standardisation provides a framework for businesses to comply with regulatory requirements, implement best practices, and build consumer trust. This section explores key standards for food quality management, manufacturing best practices, and traceability systems.

8.9.4.1. Food Quality and Testing Standards

Food quality assurance relies on rigorous testing and compliance with international and European standards. Several technical committees, such as **ISO/TC 34** (Food products) and **CEN/TC 275** (Food analysis – Horizontal methods), develop standards to regulate food composition, contaminants, allergens, and microbiological safety.

Key standards include:

- **ISO 22000** – A global standard for food safety management systems, integrating HACCP (Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points) principles to ensure food is safe at all stages of the supply chain.
- **ISO 17025** – Specifies the general requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories, ensuring food analysis results are reliable.

- **EN 13804** – Establishes methods for determining elements and chemical species in foodstuffs, essential for quality control in processed and fresh foods.

8.9.4.2. Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) in the Food Industry

Following GMP guidelines ensures that food and food-related products are consistently produced and controlled according to quality standards. These practices cover hygiene, equipment, personnel training, and process validation.

Important standards in this area include:

- **ISO 22000** – Provides a structured approach for implementing a food safety management system, helping companies control risks and comply with legal requirements.
- **ISO 22716** – A GMP guideline specifically for the cosmetics industry, ensuring safe and high-quality production of food-related cosmetic products such as edible oils used in skincare.

Practical applications for businesses:

- **Food processing facilities:** Adopting GMP-based procedures for equipment cleaning and sanitisation.
- **Ingredient suppliers:** Implementing quality control checks to verify compliance with safety standards before distribution.

8.9.4.3. Food Safety and Traceability in the Supply Chain

Traceability systems allow food businesses to track the journey of their products from farm to fork. This is essential for managing food recalls, preventing contamination, and ensuring regulatory compliance.

Key standards supporting traceability include:

- **ISO 22005** – Establishes general principles and basic requirements for designing and implementing traceability systems in the food and feed chain.
- **ISO/IEC 15459-4** – Standard for automatic identification and data capture techniques, ensuring consistent product labelling and tracking.
- **GS1 EPCIS 2.0** – A global standard enabling businesses to share real-time supply chain visibility data for better traceability and efficiency.

Examples of traceability applications:

- **Meat and dairy industries:** Using batch coding and blockchain technologies to track product origin and ensure food safety.
- **Retail and foodservice:** Implementing digital traceability platforms to monitor supply chain performance and detect risks early.

8.9.5. Use of Biomass and Valorisation of By-products

The agri-food industry generates a significant volume of organic waste and by-products, which, if properly managed, can contribute to sustainability and circular economy goals. Standardisation plays a key role in ensuring that bio-based products meet quality, safety, and performance criteria while facilitating their market uptake.

8.9.5.1. Bio-based Materials and Their Impact on the Agri-food Industry

Bio-based products are derived from biological sources and serve as alternatives to fossil-based materials in packaging, food additives, and biodegradable plastics. Standards ensure these materials meet sustainability criteria and provide transparency regarding their composition.

Key standards include:

- **ISO 16620** – A series of standards that define methods for determining the bio-based content of plastics, enabling accurate product labelling and environmental claims.
- **EN 16575** – Establishes a common vocabulary for bio-based products, ensuring clarity in regulations and certifications.
- **EN 16751** – Specifies sustainability criteria for bio-based products, supporting responsible sourcing and production.

Practical applications for businesses:

- **Food packaging manufacturers:** Using certified bio-based polymers to reduce reliance on conventional plastics.
- **Food processors:** Incorporating bio-based ingredients derived from agricultural by-products into functional food formulations.

8.9.5.2. Emerging Technologies for Waste Utilisation

Recent advancements in biotechnology and material sciences have enabled the conversion of agri-food residues into high-value products, promoting resource efficiency.

Examples of innovative approaches include:

- **Conversion of waste into bioplastics** – Agricultural residues such as fruit peels and starch-rich crops can be processed into biodegradable packaging materials.
- **Extraction of functional ingredients** – By-products from fruit, vegetable, and cereal processing can be transformed into antioxidants, dietary fibres, and proteins for food applications.
- **Anaerobic digestion for bioenergy** – Organic waste from food production can be used to generate biogas, reducing dependency on fossil fuels.

These technologies support sustainability objectives while providing businesses with cost-saving opportunities through waste valorisation.

8.9.6. Plastics and Packaging in the Agri-food Industry

Packaging plays a crucial role in preserving food quality and extending shelf life, but its environmental impact has led to increasing regulatory pressure and demand for sustainable alternatives. Standardisation ensures that packaging materials comply with food safety regulations while promoting circular economy principles.

8.9.6.1. Regulations on Food Contact Packaging

Materials intended for direct food contact must meet strict safety and hygiene standards to prevent contamination. European and international regulations define testing methods and migration limits for packaging components.

Key standards include:

- **CEN/TC 194** – Focuses on standardisation of utensils and packaging materials in contact with food, ensuring they meet safety requirements.
- **EN 1186 series** – Specifies methods for testing the overall migration of substances from plastic packaging into food.
- **ISO 22000** – Provides guidelines for food safety management, including requirements for safe packaging materials.

Practical applications for businesses:

- **Food manufacturers:** Ensuring that packaging materials comply with migration limits to prevent contamination.
- **Retailers:** Adopting certified food-safe packaging to build consumer trust and meet legal obligations.

8.9.6.2. Sustainable and Biodegradable Alternatives

In response to environmental concerns, there is a growing shift towards biodegradable, compostable, and recyclable packaging solutions. Standards help businesses adopt sustainable materials while ensuring their functionality and compliance.

Key standards include:

- **ISO 18604** – Defines requirements for packaging recyclability, promoting material recovery and waste reduction.
- **EN 17033** – Specifies requirements for biodegradable mulch films used in agriculture, supporting sustainable farming practices.
- **EN 13432** – Establishes criteria for compostable packaging, ensuring it breaks down safely in industrial composting conditions.

Examples of sustainable packaging applications:

- **Compostable food trays** made from plant-based polymers for takeaway meals.
- **Edible coatings** that extend the shelf life of fresh produce while reducing plastic use.
- **Recyclable paper-based alternatives** for single-use plastic wraps and containers.

Adopting these alternatives enables businesses to reduce their environmental footprint while complying with evolving regulatory frameworks.

8.9.7. Steps for Implementing Standards in Agri-food Businesses

The integration of standards into business operations can enhance product quality, ensure regulatory compliance, and improve sustainability. However, the process of adopting and certifying standards can be complex, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). This section provides a practical guide to help businesses navigate the implementation of standards in a structured and efficient manner.

8.9.7.1. How to Evaluate Which Standards to Apply?

Not all standards are applicable to every business. Companies should assess their specific needs, market demands, and regulatory obligations before selecting relevant standards.

8.9.7.2. Steps to identify relevant standards:

1. **Define business priorities** – Identify key areas such as food safety, environmental impact, circularity, or traceability.
2. **Analyse regulatory requirements** – Determine mandatory compliance obligations at national and European levels.
3. **Assess industry benchmarks** – Research competitors and industry best practices to understand which standards provide competitive advantages.
4. **Consult standardisation bodies** – Reach out to organisations such as **ISO, CEN, UNE, or EFSA** for guidance on sector-specific standards.
5. **Consider customer and market expectations** – Certifications such as **ISO 22000 (food safety)** or **EN 16751 (bio-based products)** may be required by suppliers, retailers, or export markets.

Example: A food packaging company aiming to transition to sustainable materials may need to comply with **ISO 18604 (recyclable packaging)** and **EN 13432 (compostable packaging)** to meet regulatory and market expectations.

8.9.7.3. How to Certify an Agri-food Process or Product?

Certification ensures that a company's processes, products, or services comply with recognised standards. It provides credibility, facilitates market access, and can serve as a differentiation factor.

General certification process:

1. **Gap analysis and internal audit** – Compare existing processes with the requirements of the chosen standard.
2. **Implementation of necessary changes** – Adapt procedures, documentation, and production practices to meet compliance criteria.
3. **Training and capacity building** – Ensure employees understand and can implement the standard's requirements.

4. **Engage an accredited certification body** – Contact organisations authorised to conduct audits and issue certifications. Examples include **AENOR (Spain), BSI (UK), and TÜV Rheinland (Germany)**.
5. **Undergo the certification audit** – An external audit will assess compliance with the standard. If successful, certification is granted.
6. **Continuous improvement and renewal** – Certifications are periodically reviewed, requiring businesses to maintain compliance through monitoring and updates.

Example: A food processing company seeking **ISO 22000 (food safety management)** certification would need to document its food safety procedures, implement hazard analysis controls, and pass an external audit.

8.9.7.4. Tools and Resources Available

Several tools and resources can assist businesses in adopting and certifying standards, reducing complexity and facilitating compliance.

1. Standardisation Organisations and Online Portals

- **ISO (International Organization for Standardization)** – Provides global standards across various industries (www.iso.org).
- **CEN (European Committee for Standardization)** – Develops European standards, including those on food safety and sustainability (www.cen.eu).
- **UNE (Asociación Española de Normalización)** – The Spanish standardisation body with specific guidelines for the agri-food sector (www.une.org).
- **EFSA (European Food Safety Authority)** – Provides scientific advice on food risks and safety regulations (www.efsa.europa.eu).

2. Certification Bodies

- **AENOR (Spain)** – Certifies compliance with ISO, EN, and UNE standards.
- **SGS, TÜV, and Bureau Veritas** – International certification bodies for food safety, environmental, and quality standards.
- **Local chambers of commerce and industry associations** – Often provide certification guidance and funding support.

3. Digital Tools and Training Resources

- **Online training courses** – Many certification bodies offer courses on specific standards.

- **Self-assessment tools** – Platforms such as the **ISO Certification Readiness Checklist** help companies evaluate their compliance gaps.
- **Industry guidelines** – Sector-specific associations provide best practices and implementation roadmaps.

8.10. IB10: Promoting awareness of circular economy at managerial level

8.10.1. The Circular Economy: A Strategic Imperative for Sustainable Business

- The circular economy moves beyond the traditional linear model (take-make-dispose) towards a **system that maximises resource efficiency**, minimises waste, and fosters sustainable innovation.
- At the **international level**, frameworks like the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Paris Agreement highlight circularity as a key pillar for economic and environmental resilience.
- In **Europe**, the EU Circular Economy Action Plan is driving regulatory changes, urging businesses to integrate circular practices into their operations.
- Circularity is not just about **compliance**, it provides a **competitive advantage**, reducing costs, encouraging innovation, and improving long-term sustainability.
- Companies leading this transition will be **better positioned** to navigate evolving regulations, meet growing consumer expectations, and future-proof their business in a resource-constrained world.

8.10.2. Advantages of Circular Economy for Agri-Food Businesses

- **Cost reduction and resource efficiency:** Implementing circular economy strategies allows companies to optimise resource use, reducing raw material consumption and minimising waste. This can lower production costs and improve overall operational efficiency.
- **Improved supply chain resilience:** Circular strategies, such as short supply chains and local sourcing, help reduce dependency on global markets and mitigate supply chain disruptions, making businesses more resilient to economic and environmental challenges.
- **Lower carbon footprint and environmental impact:** The application of circular approaches, including biodegradable and recyclable packaging, waste valorisation, and sustainable transportation, has been shown to significantly reduce greenhouse

gas emissions. In the Italian egg industry case study, these strategies led to a 22% reduction in CO₂-equivalent emissions.

- **Competitive advantage and market differentiation:** Companies adopting circular economy principles can enhance brand reputation by appealing to environmentally conscious consumers and meeting the growing demand for sustainable products.
- **Regulatory compliance and risk mitigation:** Circular practices help businesses stay ahead of environmental regulations, avoiding penalties and ensuring long-term sustainability in compliance with national and EU legislation.
- **New revenue streams through waste valorisation:** Many agri-food businesses can convert waste into valuable by-products, such as bio-based materials, animal feed, or renewable energy sources, turning waste management from a cost burden into a profitable opportunity.
- **Enhanced corporate social responsibility (CSR):** Circular economy initiatives contribute to broader sustainability goals, supporting the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by addressing food waste, responsible production, and climate action.

Reference

[38] S. Abbate, P. Centobelli, R. Cerchione, G. Giardino, and R. Passaro, "Coming out the egg: Assessing the benefits of circular economy strategies in the agri-food industry," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 385, Art. no. 135665, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.135665>

8.10.3. Circular Economy Incentives and Competitive Benefits for SMEs in the Agri-Food Sector

While circular economy practices have traditionally been viewed as environmental obligations, recent research highlights their **competitive advantages** for **small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)**. Circular operations can provide **strategic business benefits** at multiple levels, offering a compelling case for adoption beyond regulatory compliance.

1. Competitive benefits at the firm level

- **Cost savings and operational efficiency:** SMEs can reduce waste and raw material costs through resource optimisation, reuse, and recycling strategies.

- **Brand differentiation and customer loyalty:** Businesses that adopt circular principles can enhance their reputation, appealing to eco-conscious consumers and securing a competitive edge in the market.
- **Innovation and new business models:** Circular operations can drive product and service innovation, enabling businesses to explore alternative revenue streams, such as offering repair services, leasing models, or upcycled product lines.

2. Competitive benefits at the supply chain level

- **Stronger supplier and buyer relationships:** Implementing circular strategies fosters collaboration and trust between supply chain partners, leading to long-term partnerships and resilience.
- **Regulatory compliance and risk reduction:** SMEs can anticipate and comply with evolving environmental regulations, avoiding legal risks and financial penalties while maintaining supply chain continuity.
- **Supply security and reduced dependency on raw materials:** By valorising waste and promoting resource loops, businesses can buffer against supply shortages and price fluctuations in raw materials.

3. Competitive benefits at the societal level

- **Attracting investment and funding opportunities:** Many public and private funding schemes prioritise circular economy initiatives, allowing SMEs to access financial support for sustainable innovation.
- **Workforce engagement and talent attraction:** Employees, especially younger generations, value sustainability-focused companies, improving recruitment and retention of skilled professionals.
- **Contribution to local economic resilience:** SMEs that incorporate circularity contribute to regional sustainability efforts, enhancing their role in local economies and building community goodwill.

Reference

[39] N. McDougall, B. Wagner, and J. MacBryde, "Competitive benefits & incentivisation at internal, supply chain & societal level circular operations in UK agri-food SMEs," *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 144, pp. 1149–1162, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.02.060>

8.11. IB11: Good practice Directory for circular economy in the agrifood sector

8.11.1. Overview of the Directory

The Directory of Best Practices in Circular Economy for the Agri-Food Sector is an initiative under the Agro2Circular project (developed by AGROFOOD), designed to support businesses in the Region of Murcia in adopting more sustainable practices. Given the agri-food sector's reliance on natural resources and its environmental impact, transitioning to circular models is essential. This directory compiles a selection of success stories, providing practical insights into circular economy implementation. **The document is publicly available on the Agro2Circular [project website](#)** and serves as a guide for businesses looking to integrate circular economy principles.

8.11.2. Description of work

Each section of the proposed index has been carefully selected to provide a concise overview of the current state and future potential of valorising agri-food by-products and other waste.

Each section of the proposed index has been carefully selected to provide a concise overview of the current state and future potential of valorising agri-food by-products and other waste.

1. **Introduction** – This section familiarises the reader with the document by outlining the sources of information used to identify good practices.
2. **Best Circular Economy Principles (BPCE) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)** – A list of key circular economy principles, along with a visual representation of the SDGs, which are linked to each good practice presented in the document.
3. **Overview of the Circular Economy in the Agri-Food Sector** – A brief explanation of how the circular economy applies to the agri-food sector and its auxiliary plastic packaging industry. It also highlights the sector's regulatory requirements and consumer expectations, offering a global perspective.
4. **Policies and Support Mechanisms** – Since the Agro2Circular project has developed a Circular Economy Strategy for the Region of Murcia, this section provides an overview of relevant policies and support measures specific to the region.

5. **Methodology for Selecting Best Practices in Circular Economy. Classification and Evaluation criteria.** A methodology that includes the identification, classification and assessment of circular initiatives based on impact, replicability, innovation level and sustainability. Practices are classified by sector, scale, and type of circular strategy (including identified difficulties or challenges) and evaluated using quantitative indicators.
6. **Good Practices Database** – The core of the document consists of case studies of good practices identified through an initial search, followed by a review and validation process with stakeholders in the Region of Murcia. These internationally sourced success stories serve as practical examples for the agri-food sector. The practices are ranked based on their evaluation scores and categorised according to their primary area of impact—either within agri-food businesses generating by-products or in external industries adopting circular business models.
7. **Presentation of the Agro2Circular Project** – A brief description of the project’s key tasks within Work Packages 2, 3, and 6, along with the partners involved.
8. **Technologies for Valorisation** – A detailed overview of technologies available for the valorisation of agri-food by-products.
9. **Conclusion** – A final reflection encouraging the adoption of circular economy principles in the agri-food sector of the Region of Murcia.
10. **References** – A list of the most relevant bibliographical sources used in the document.

8.11.3. Content of the good practice sheets

The following information has been used to display the content of the Good Practice sheets:

- ✓ Name of the Good Practice. Responsible entity
- ✓ Representative image
- ✓ Location of the Good Practice
- ✓ Description and Objective of the Good Practice
- ✓ Key results of the Good Practice
- ✓ Advantages and disadvantages of implementing the Good Practice
- ✓ Connection with the Principles of Good Practices of the Circular Economy
- ✓ Connection with the SDG Objectives

- ✓ Web links for more information

8.11.4. Good practices selection

Throughout the implementation of the European Agro2Circular project, an international diagnosis was conducted to identify Good Practices in the Circular Economy within the agri-food sector and related auxiliary sectors with potential for circular development. Leveraging its involvement in working groups, councils, and similar platforms, the AGROFOOD MURCIA cluster accessed a wide network of contacts, enabling the identification of relevant actions and the assessment of their suitability for inclusion in the Guide. In certain cases, direct engagement with companies provided access to private initiatives that were subsequently reviewed and integrated into the material. To complement this network-based approach, a broader desk research effort was undertaken. This included a systematic search of databases related to R&D&I projects funded by entities such as regional governments, CDTI, AEI, and Horizon 2020. These projects—often carried out by research centres, universities, technology institutes, and businesses in collaboration—provided valuable examples. Once a potential success story was identified, further details were gathered through the respective organisations' websites and media coverage to enrich the corresponding case files.

The information collection was carried out in the period October 2022-September 2024. In total, 75 files have been made available for review and evaluation in the meetings held with the stakeholders (May 2023, December 2023, March 2024, October 2024).

The stakeholder panel was made up of representatives of the food industry in the Region of Murcia and external advisors with more than 30 years of experience. At the first meeting, the objective of the Agro2Circular project was reported and the assessment criteria were indicated, while at the following two meetings a debate was held on the incorporation or exclusion of Good Practices.

The initial list included Circular Economy actions from different entities that can be implemented by or for the agri-food sector. Once reviewed, a classification was made into 6 subcategories.

List of the 75 Good Practices detected for Circular Economy				
<i>Adidas</i>	<i>Cerveza ‘Sr. Mendrugo’</i>	<i>Fitplanet</i>	<i>Juver</i>	<i>Prosur</i>
<i>Agrain</i>	<i>Chanel</i>	<i>Florette</i>	<i>Kaura</i>	<i>Rebread</i>
<i>Agrosevilla</i>	<i>Circubica</i>	<i>Freshly Cosmetics</i>	<i>Kiko Milano</i>	<i>Riverbend</i>
<i>AgroSingularity S.L.</i>	<i>Circular Fiber</i>	<i>Gimme Sabor</i>	<i>La cámara</i>	<i>Rubymoon</i>
<i>Aliga Microalgae</i>	<i>Cynara</i>	<i>Girlfriend Collective</i>	<i>Laboratorios amerex</i>	<i>Sabater spices</i>
<i>Alver</i>	<i>Danone</i>	<i>GO AGROCIRCULAR INNOVA</i>	<i>Landratech</i>	<i>Sea threads</i>
<i>App ‘TOO GOOD TO GO’</i>	<i>Dcoop y Biopharma Research</i>	<i>GO CYCLEPLASTIC</i>	<i>Lush Cosmetics</i>	<i>Sigma Biotech</i>
<i>Arrocitoecoco</i>	<i>Dear Earth</i>	<i>Gravity wave</i>	<i>MaGie Creations</i>	<i>Siremwild</i>
<i>Basq Company</i>	<i>Done Properly</i>	<i>Green Spot Technologies</i>	<i>Mercadona - Reduce su huella de carbono</i>	<i>Supermercados Covirán</i>
<i>Betik</i>	<i>Ecoalf</i>	<i>Hero</i>	<i>Mr. Broko</i>	<i>The valorization community</i>
<i>Biodiverso</i>	<i>El Pozo</i>	<i>Incarlopsa</i>	<i>Nanollose</i>	<i>Uniqlo</i>
<i>Biogusto</i>	<i>Espigoladors</i>	<i>Indulleida</i>	<i>Nestlé</i>	<i>Väcka</i>
<i>Bioprocesia</i>	<i>Estrella de Levante</i>	<i>Ingredalia</i>	<i>NEWEX</i>	<i>Vicky foods</i>
<i>Blendhub</i>	<i>Everlane</i>	<i>Insectum</i>	<i>Nutripeople</i>	<i>Victoria</i>
<i>Catalina Food Solutions</i>	<i>Fabumin</i>	<i>Jongerius Ecoduna</i>	<i>Pescanova</i>	<i>Water2return</i>

Table 2 - 75 selected good practices for analysis

The selection of good practices was based on the following assessment criteria:

- **Key results** – Main achievements in environmental, economic, and social terms resulting from the implementation of the good practice (40%).

- **Challenges and difficulties** – Barriers or issues encountered during implementation (30%).
- **Scope of application** – Classification of the good practice within one of the following sectors:
 - i) Agri-food
 - ii) Nutraceutical
 - iii) Plastics/packaging
 - iv) Cosmetics
 - v) Other industries (20%).
- **Alignment with SDGs** – Degree of connection with Sustainable Development Goals (10%).

From the outset, a maximum number of good practices was considered to ensure a focused selection. The optimal range was set between 25 and 50 practices, prioritising those most relevant to the business landscape of the Region of Murcia. Only practices scoring above a weighted value of 5 were selected.

Ultimately, 30 good practices were compiled, with a significant proportion directly related to the agri-food sector and the implementation of the Agro2Circular project. These examples serve as practical models for businesses, though they are not limited to the fruit and vegetable subsector. Instead, the document encourages cross-sectoral replicability, including areas such as cereals, meat, and other agri-food industries.

In summary, 20 selected practices are directly linked to the agri-food sector, while 10 others are transversal or come from auxiliary sectors. The final selection was validated through individual meetings with stakeholders in October 2024, with the results presented below.

Figure 9 - final 30 selected good practices

Among the evaluated companies, **Indulleida** received the highest recognition for its long-standing expertise in processing a diverse range of fruits and vegetables throughout the year. The company offers an extensive product catalogue, making it a **notable example of Circular Economy implementation at the internal business level**. Currently, Indulleida is actively committed to sustainability, investing in energy efficiency improvements and CO₂ reduction strategies.

Cynara, a regional company, was highly rated for its innovative approach to **maximising the value of artichokes**, a raw material with a high percentage of by-products. By developing new marketable products such as artichoke chips, Cynara demonstrates a **scalable and low-investment good practice**, particularly suitable for smaller companies. Lastly, **Biodiverso Cosmetics**, a spin-off from **UPCT**, was recognised for its **circular business model**, which focuses on developing new products from raw materials supplied by third parties. The company primarily operates through **online sales**, showcasing an alternative approach to sustainable business development.

8.11.5. Difficulties encountered

- The vast amount of information retrieved from search engines using keywords such as *“extraction technologies and food industry”* resulted in lengthy screening sessions to identify relevant entities implementing Circular Economy solutions. Due to the

necessary filtering process, a significant amount of information was lost during summarisation.

- The initial evaluation criteria yielded **low scores** for some practices. To address this, a revised criterion has been proposed: “*Solutions to challenges faced by the entity responsible for implementing the Good Practice*” (30%). The new evaluation descriptor will focus on **difficulties or challenges identified** (30%).
- **Potential errors** were detected in assessing technologies implemented outside the Region of Murcia, as their current status could not always be verified. Within Murcia, the **Good Practices' scope and implementation could be confirmed** through stakeholder input. For instance, stakeholders identified several limitations in *Agrosingularity*, which ultimately ceased operations before the end of 2024 due to financial difficulties.

8.11.6. Conclusions

Recent trends in the food industry highlight an increasing focus on **Circular Economy principles**. A key strategy involves **valorising industrial waste**, such as by-products from fruit and vegetable processing, to extract valuable compounds (e.g., proteins, fibre, vitamins, and antioxidants) for use in new food formulations. Environmental impact is also minimised by adopting **sustainable technologies** such as green solvents, while energy efficiency remains a priority.

Numerous **regional, national, and international initiatives** are already in place, making updated **Circular Economy Good Practice Guides** a valuable resource for decision-makers in the sector. This document consolidates and evaluates companies that have successfully **adapted to new business models**, broadening their product portfolios.

Key takeaways:

- **Circular business models** that incorporate by-product valorisation within agri-food companies are becoming well-established and offer a **practical approach** to implementing Circular Economy strategies.
- Many **ingredient marketing companies** have developed new formulations using natural ingredients derived from agri-food by-products. This presents an opportunity for the **agri-food sector to benefit from the commercialisation of by-products**.

- In response to consumer demand, **new companies have emerged** that align with circular business models. While their long-term viability is uncertain, the growing presence of **digital platforms is increasing opportunities for SMEs** to market by-products and reduce waste.
- **Internationally**, several initiatives have successfully **differentiated themselves** by targeting sustainability-conscious consumers.
- During the evaluation, stakeholders highlighted the **importance of including Circular Economy Good Practices in the meat sector** to encourage **cross-sector replicability**.

This document provides **key insights** into the **current landscape and future potential** of valorising agri-food by-products and waste streams. The identified **Best Practices serve as reference models** for businesses looking to adopt Circular Economy principles.

8.11.7. Related website

 <https://looparm.es/casos-de-exito/>

Since October 2024, the **Dynamic Catalogue of Good Practices in Circular Economy**—promoted by the **Institute for the Promotion of the Region of Murcia**—has also been available. This tool complements the **Directory of Best Practices** by **allowing all companies in Murcia to showcase their circular business models**, as well as providing visibility to **organisations promoting Circular Economy initiatives** in the business community.

8.12. IB12: Industry Mentoring Programme

8.12.1. Introduction

The **Agro2Circular Industry Mentoring Programme** (implemented by PRIMA) was designed to support companies in the agri-food sector in adopting circular economy principles. Over the course of the programme, companies were mentored in generating innovation-oriented proposals, identifying best practices from past projects, receiving circular economy training, and implementing monitoring and evaluation activities to assess the impact of their initiatives.

Four key areas of collaboration were established:

1. **Development of innovation proposals** aligned with business challenges, with a focus on identifying new business opportunities and improving resource efficiency through circular strategies.
2. **Identification of existing circular practices** within participating companies, using past projects as a starting point to build on successful initiatives.
3. **Training in Circular Economy** tailored to the Agro2Circular project, covering fundamental concepts, best practices, and alignment with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
4. **Monitoring and Evaluation**, including **monthly group meetings** and **individual follow-ups** with programme coordinators over three months, culminating in this final report summarising the results and insights gained.

8.12.2. Selected Projects

The participating companies selected projects that aligned with their strategies and identified challenges. Their primary goals included:

- **Reducing resource losses** in production and operations.
- **Recovering and valorising waste** to create new value streams.
- **Digitisation of processes** to enhance traceability and efficiency.

8.12.3. Project Summaries

1. Industrias Anfra S.A.

- **Objectives:** Recovery of production waste and elimination of microplastic contamination.
- **KPIs:**
 - Annual production volume.
 - Waste recovery percentage (in weight and economic value).
 - Energy consumption and CO₂ emissions reduction.
 - Reduction of material spills per kg of processed material.

2. Reciplast

- **Objectives:** Circularisation of used packaging for receiving and processing recycled plastics.
- **KPIs:**
 - Number of suppliers and clients involved in the initiative.
 - Reduction in packaging placed on the market.
 - Impact on carbon footprint reduction.

3. Fundación Primafrío

- **Objectives:** Development of truck models using recycled plastics from their own facilities.
- **KPIs:**
 - Cost comparison with conventional production methods.
 - Volume of plastic reused.
 - Social impact through collaborations with social enterprises.

4. Mocitos

- **Objectives:** Circularisation of **multi-layer plastics**, evaluating their durability and integrity.
- **KPIs:**
 - Costs of logistics and production.
 - Durability of sustainable packaging alternatives.
 - Reduction of multi-layer plastic waste.

8.12.4. Programme Implementation and Progress

Over the three-month mentoring period, companies followed a structured plan, focusing on:

1. **Defining project requirements** (analysing existing processes and identifying weak points).
2. **Developing proof-of-concept solutions** for waste reduction and circularity.
3. **Implementing and tracking key performance indicators (KPIs)** to measure success.

Example Activities:

- **Industrias Anfra S.A.:** Conducted process flow analysis to identify waste hotspots and improve internal recycling.
- **Reciplast:** Implemented a **return system for reusable plastic containers**, reducing packaging waste.
- **Mocitos:** Explored **alternative uses for multi-layer plastic packaging** to extend product lifespan.
- **Fundación Primafrio:** Evaluated the feasibility of **producing scaled truck models** from recycled plastic.

8.12.5. Results from Follow-up Meetings

Key Findings from the 26 September 2024 Follow-Up Session:

- **Common Barriers for SMEs in Circular Economy Adoption:**
 - Resource constraints: Limited budget and personnel to implement circular strategies.
 - Technical challenges: Difficulty in finding viable recycling solutions for complex materials.
 - Dependence on external suppliers: Some projects required collaboration with third-party recyclers or technology providers.
- **Company-Specific Updates:**
 - Industrias Anfra: Progressed in circularisation of production waste but lacked detailed tracking of recovered materials.
 - Reciplast: Successfully engaged 10 clients in initial trials for reusable packaging, avoiding 7 Big-Bags in just one test cycle.
 - Mocitos: Encountered technical issues in reusing multi-layer plastics, requiring additional laboratory research.

- Fundación Primafrío: Project temporarily paused due to dependence on external feasibility assessments.

Planned Actions:

- Final meeting scheduled for March 2025 to consolidate results from all companies.
- Assessment of the Agro2Circular Digital Information System (DIS) to measure circularity impact and resource traceability.
- Extension of the project timeline until March 2025 to allow further development of ongoing initiatives.

8.12.6. Qualitative Feedback from Participants

The mentoring programme not only facilitated technical knowledge exchange but also transformed company perspectives on circular economy implementation. Below are key reflections from participating businesses:

- "We have set a goal to resume and reinforce these efforts, as outlined in our latest Management Review Report."
- "Although we have not been able to prioritise this project due to other urgent initiatives, we remain committed, and our management increasingly supports circular economy approaches."
- "For our company, achieving these objectives will be highly beneficial in the long term."
- "This experience has significantly changed my perspective on recycling and circular economy strategies."

These insights highlight the long-term value of circular economy principles, beyond immediate business operations, influencing **corporate decision-making and strategic priorities**.

8.12.7. Conclusions

The **Agro2Circular Industry Mentoring Programme** successfully supported SMEs in developing and implementing circular economy strategies tailored to their business models.

The main outcomes include:

1. Positive Results:

- Concrete advances in waste reduction and resource valorisation.

- Identification of new circular opportunities in supply chains.

2. Common Challenges:

- Limited financial and technical resources hinder full implementation.
- Dependence on third-party collaborations slows progress.

3. Future Impact:

- Companies plan to continue their circular initiatives and share best practices with industry peers.
- The extension of the project until March 2025 provides an opportunity to consolidate progress and refine strategies.

The programme has demonstrated that circular economy principles can be successfully integrated into industrial operations, even in SMEs facing structural challenges. Continued mentoring and cross-company knowledge sharing will be crucial for scaling these efforts further.

Finally, we extend our gratitude to all participating companies and partners, whose commitment and innovation have contributed to advancing sustainability in the agri-food sector.

Key lessons for the agri-food industry

The programme's experiences revealed critical insights for companies seeking to transition towards more circular business models. These lessons can guide other agri-food businesses, policymakers, and industry stakeholders in adopting sustainable practices.

Lesson 1: circular economy must be business-driven and integrated into strategy

- Companies that successfully implemented circular practices aligned them with their core business strategy rather than treating them as separate sustainability initiatives.
- Circular economy models should be profit-driven, focusing on both resource efficiency and cost reduction.
- Projects addressing supply chain inefficiencies, waste valorisation, and digitalisation had the highest potential for long-term adoption.

Example:

- Industrias Anfra S.A. achieved waste recovery and energy savings by integrating circularity into its production strategy.

Lesson 2: digitalisation is a key enabler of circularity

- The traceability of resources and waste streams is essential for achieving circularity in the agri-food industry.
- Digital tools, such as blockchain, ERP systems, and digital twin models, enhance the ability to track waste, optimise production processes, and identify circular opportunities.

Example:

- Reciplast developed a packaging return system, enabling clients to reuse packaging and track its lifecycle.

Lesson 3: collaboration across the value chain is essential

- Circular economy projects often require collaboration between multiple stakeholders, including suppliers, clients, recyclers, and technology providers.
- Many agri-food companies struggle with implementing circular solutions alone due to technological, financial, or logistical limitations.

Example:

- Fundación Primafrio faced challenges in sourcing recycled plastic materials and had to depend on external feasibility assessments.

Lesson 4: SMEs face common barriers that require structural support

- Lack of financial resources and technological expertise are the main barriers preventing SMEs from implementing circular strategies.
- Government incentives, industry collaborations, and mentoring programmes can help businesses overcome these barriers.

Example:

- Mocitos encountered technical difficulties in reusing multi-layer plastics and required external R&D support to develop viable solutions.

Lesson 5: circular economy provides tangible business benefits

- Companies that successfully implemented circular practices saw improvements in cost savings, efficiency, and sustainability metrics.
- These benefits included reduced waste disposal costs, enhanced regulatory compliance, and improved brand positioning.

Example:

- Reciplast's packaging reuse initiative reduced plastic waste and demonstrated measurable carbon footprint reductions.

Methodology for implementing circular economy initiatives in agri-food companies

To replicate and scale the successful initiatives from the Agro2Circular programme, businesses should follow a structured six-step methodology.

Step 1: circularity assessment (identifying opportunities and waste streams)

- Conduct a material flow analysis (MFA) to map raw material use, waste generation, and inefficiencies.
- Identify high-impact waste streams and untapped by-products.
- Use circular economy assessment tools (e.g., Ellen MacArthur Foundation's Circulytics, carbon footprint analysis).

Example:

- Industrias Anfra S.A. used process flow diagrams to identify and optimise critical waste points in production.

Step 2: define circular business objectives and strategy

- Align circular economy initiatives with business priorities (e.g., cost reduction, compliance, brand differentiation).
- Set clear KPIs to measure circularity performance, such as:
 - Waste recovery rate
 - Energy consumption reduction
 - Supply chain efficiency gains

Example:

- Reciplast set KPIs to measure packaging return rates and carbon footprint reduction.

Step 3: engage key stakeholders and build partnerships

- Involve suppliers, customers, recyclers, and industry associations to create a collaborative ecosystem.
- Identify potential technology partners (for digital traceability, recycling solutions, etc.).

- Secure financial support through grants, sustainability funds, or impact investment opportunities.

Example:

- Fundación Primafrío required partnerships with plastics recyclers and external feasibility assessors to advance its project.

Step 4: develop and test circular solutions

- Implement pilot projects to test circular strategies in a low-risk, controlled environment.
- Perform life cycle assessments (LCA) to evaluate the economic and environmental impact.
- Iterate based on feedback from operations, customers, and supply chain partners.

Example:

- Mocitos tested biodegradable and recycled plastics for packaging but required additional research due to material degradation issues.

Step 5: scale circular economy innovations

- Expand successful pilot projects into full-scale implementation.
- Integrate circular strategies into company-wide policies and production processes.
- Leverage digitalisation for continuous monitoring and performance tracking.

Example:

- Reциplast successfully expanded its reusable packaging initiative to include 10 clients, demonstrating scalability.

Step 6: monitor, evaluate, and improve

- Establish a long-term monitoring plan using KPIs and data analytics.
- Conduct periodic evaluations and adjust strategies based on new technological advancements and market conditions.
- Share best practices and lessons learned with industry networks and policymakers to drive sector-wide transformation.

Example:

- The Agro2Circular Digital Information System (DIS) is being evaluated to measure the traceability of circular materials and assess long-term impact.

3. Relevance for advancing the circular economy in the agri-food sector

This mentoring programme demonstrated the practical application of circular economy principles in the agri-food industry. The lessons and methodology outlined here provide a scalable framework that can be replicated by other companies to accelerate sustainability transitions.

Why is this approach valuable?

- Enhances resource efficiency by reducing waste and improving material recovery.
- Drives cost savings and operational efficiency through process optimisation.
- Improves sustainability compliance with EU policies and green regulations.
- Fosters innovation by identifying new revenue streams from by-products and waste.
- Strengthens supply chain resilience by diversifying resource sourcing and minimising waste dependencies.

9. ANNEX V - Training Plan for local actors: Public Sector

9.1. PS1: Circular Public Procurement: guidelines and best practices

Green public procurement (GPP) is a strategic tool that enables governments to acquire goods and services with a reduced environmental impact. In the agri-food sector, it plays a crucial role in promoting organic production, minimising food waste, and fostering sustainable supply chain practices. By leveraging public purchasing power, authorities can drive market transformation towards greater sustainability and resource efficiency.

- **The role of organic products in GPP**

Integrating organic products into GPP policies offers multiple benefits, making it a key mechanism for enhancing sustainability in public procurement.

- **Reducing pollution and protecting biodiversity**

Organic farming eliminates the use of synthetic pesticides and fertilisers, reducing soil and water contamination while supporting healthier ecosystems.

- **Enhancing food quality**

Research indicates that organic produce tends to contain higher levels of antioxidants and lower concentrations of heavy metals such as cadmium, contributing to better nutritional value.

- **Supporting local and sustainable economies**

GPP frameworks prioritising organic produce benefit small-scale farmers and reduce carbon emissions by shortening supply chains. Given that public procurement accounts for approximately 14% of the European Union's GDP, its influence is significant in steering the agri-food market towards sustainability.

9.1.1. Benefits of green public procurement in the agri-food sector

Implementing GPP in agri-food procurement generates multiple economic, social, and environmental advantages.

Economic value

- Reduces long-term costs by cutting food waste and improving resource efficiency.
- Encourages innovation in sustainable food production and processing.

Social value

- Provides access to healthier food options in public institutions such as schools, hospitals, and care facilities.
- Strengthens local economies by connecting producers with public sector buyers.
- Raises awareness about sustainability, ethical food production, and responsible consumption.

Sustainable agricultural practices

- Encourages environmentally responsible farming methods free from synthetic chemicals.
- Incentivises regenerative agriculture and agroecological principles that improve soil health and biodiversity.

Fostering green communities

- Strengthens community ties by prioritising local suppliers, reinforcing engagement and social cohesion.
- Supports initiatives that promote regional food networks and food sovereignty.

Regulatory compliance

- Ensures alignment with EU legislative frameworks and sustainability targets in public procurement.
- Helps public institutions meet obligations under environmental policies and circular economy strategies.

Building consumer trust

- Enhances the public perception of institutions by demonstrating commitment to sustainability.
- Influences consumer behaviour, encouraging greater support for sustainable initiatives.

Environmental impact

- Lowers pollution and greenhouse gas emissions associated with conventional food production.
- Improves resource management by reducing waste and optimising the circular use of materials.

9.1.2. Steps for implementing circular criteria in Public Procurement for the agri-food sector

9.1.2.1. Defining sustainable procurement criteria

A robust framework for circular public procurement begins with clear and measurable sustainability criteria. These should be aligned with EU regulations and best practices to promote resource efficiency and environmental responsibility.

9.1.2.2. Set minimum organic product requirements

- Establish a mandatory percentage of organic products in procurement contracts (e.g., at least 30% of purchased food products must be certified organic).
- Prioritise seasonal and locally produced organic goods to reduce the carbon footprint associated with transportation.

Require eco-certifications and compliance with EU standards

- Suppliers must provide valid organic certifications in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2018/848 on organic production and labelling of organic products.
- Encourage compliance with additional standards, such as GlobalG.A.P., EU Ecolabel, and ISO 14001 for environmental management systems.
- Include sustainability metrics such as carbon footprint reduction targets, water use efficiency, and waste minimisation.

Promote packaging circularity

- Mandate minimal or recyclable packaging, avoiding single-use plastics.
- Encourage innovative solutions such as compostable or reusable packaging made from agrifood waste.

Encourage sustainable farming and animal welfare

- Preference should be given to producers adopting regenerative agriculture practices, agroecology, and biodiversity conservation.
- Consider higher welfare standards for animal products by prioritising suppliers certified under EU animal welfare legislation.

9.1.2.3. Integrating circular criteria into tendering processes

Once sustainability criteria have been established, they must be incorporated into procurement tenders to ensure their enforcement.

Modify tender specifications to include circularity requirements

- Require bidders to submit proof of environmental certifications, traceability records, and sustainability reports.
- Award points for suppliers offering additional waste reduction initiatives, food surplus redistribution programmes, or innovative circular economy solutions.

Apply weighted scoring for environmental impact

- Develop a procurement scoring system that assigns a significant percentage of evaluation points to sustainability criteria (e.g., 30–40% of the total score).
- Use life-cycle costing (LCC) approaches to assess environmental impact across the product's lifespan, from production to disposal.

Favour short supply chains and local suppliers

- Specify a preference for regional producers to strengthen local economies and reduce emissions linked to long-distance transportation.
- Encourage direct procurement from farmers' cooperatives and social enterprises engaged in sustainable food systems.

9.1.2.4. Monitoring and verifying compliance

To ensure that suppliers meet sustainability commitments, robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms must be put in place.

Implement supplier audits and inspections

- Conduct periodic site visits to verify sustainable production practices and ethical sourcing.
- Require suppliers to undergo independent third-party audits for compliance with environmental and food safety standards.

Establish digital traceability systems

- Use blockchain-based platforms or digital product passports (DPPs) to track food products from farm to fork.

- Require suppliers to provide transparent data on production methods, emissions, and waste generation.

Mandate sustainability reporting

- Contracted suppliers should submit annual sustainability performance reports detailing their impact on waste reduction, carbon emissions, and ethical sourcing.
- Implement corrective measures if non-compliance is detected, including contract termination for repeated violations.

9.1.2.5. Educating and raising awareness

Capacity-building efforts are essential to ensure that procurement officers, suppliers, and stakeholders understand the importance of circular procurement principles.

Training for public procurement officers

- Organise workshops and e-learning sessions on circular economy practices, environmental regulations, and sustainable food procurement.
- Develop guidelines and toolkits tailored to municipalities, public institutions, and procurement professionals.

Engagement with suppliers and producers

- Offer training programmes for food suppliers on how to align their business models with circular procurement requirements.
- Create incentives for SMEs to adopt sustainable practices by providing funding, certification support, or reduced administrative burdens.

Public awareness campaigns

- Run information campaigns in schools, hospitals, and public canteens to highlight the benefits of organic and sustainably sourced food.
- Engage citizens in sustainable food initiatives, such as farm-to-table programmes or zero-waste school meal projects.

9.1.3. Ensuring compliance with organic procurement criteria

For public administrations to successfully implement organic procurement criteria, robust monitoring and verification mechanisms are essential. Compliance with EU regulations, transparency in supply chains, and the use of digital tools can ensure that organic food procurement aligns with sustainability objectives.

9.1.3.1. Official certifications and regulatory compliance

To be classified as organic within public procurement, food products must meet strict EU regulations, ensuring sustainable agricultural practices and responsible sourcing.

EU organic certification – Regulation (EU) 2018/848

- This regulation defines the principles of organic production in the European Union, covering environmental sustainability, biodiversity conservation, and chemical-free farming.
- All organic food suppliers must comply with this standard to be eligible for public contracts.

Mandatory labelling for transparency

- Organic products must display the EU organic logo, verifying that they adhere to rigorous environmental and food safety standards.
- Labels should provide clear traceability details, including certification numbers and origin information, ensuring public buyers can identify authentic organic products.

9.1.3.2. Audits and supplier controls

Public procurement bodies must establish verification mechanisms to ensure that suppliers maintain compliance throughout the contract period.

Regular supplier audits

- Conduct scheduled and random inspections to verify that suppliers meet organic certification requirements.
- Require third-party certification bodies to validate supplier claims.

Traceability and documentation checks

- Suppliers should submit detailed documentation on product origin, farming practices, and distribution routes.
- Public institutions can request periodic reports on sustainability indicators, including carbon footprint and pesticide-free production.

9.1.3.3. Digital verification platforms

Technology plays a key role in enhancing transparency and efficiency in organic procurement.

Electronic monitoring systems

- Implement digital procurement platforms to track organic food purchases and verify compliance in real-time.
- Require suppliers to use blockchain-based or cloud-based traceability systems that allow authorities to cross-check certification data.

Best practice example: Denmark's digital organic procurement system

- The Danish government has developed a digital system that monitors the percentage of organic food in public procurement.
- Institutions can use this data to adjust procurement policies and increase the share of organic products over time.

9.1.4. Circular criteria in green public procurement (GPP)

Incorporating circular economy principles into green public procurement (GPP) strengthens environmental sustainability while ensuring resource efficiency in public purchasing.

1. Environmental performance

Public procurement should prioritise low-impact products and services that contribute to environmental sustainability.

- Reduce carbon, water, and material footprints associated with food production and supply chains.
- Optimise energy efficiency in production, storage, and distribution, favouring suppliers who use renewable energy sources.
- Implement life-cycle assessments (LCA) to evaluate and compare environmental impacts across different procurement options.

2. Use of recycled and recyclable materials

A core principle of circular public procurement is ensuring that materials remain in circulation for as long as possible.

- Establish a minimum percentage of recycled content in packaging and food service materials.
- Prioritise products designed for recyclability, including compostable or biodegradable food packaging alternatives.
- Require suppliers to demonstrate commitments to circular material use through certifications such as Cradle to Cradle, EU Ecolabel, or ISO 14021.

3. Durability and extended product life cycle

Public procurement should discourage planned obsolescence by prioritising durable products with long-term usability.

- Require extended warranties and repairability guarantees for kitchen equipment and food service infrastructure.
- Set procurement standards that mandate modular or interchangeable components, making products easier to repair, upgrade, or repurpose.
- Encourage suppliers to offer maintenance and repair services as part of their contracts to prolong product life cycles.

4. Waste reduction strategies

Green public procurement must integrate waste prevention and resource-efficient consumption strategies.

- Minimise unnecessary packaging by favouring bulk purchasing and refillable containers.
- Require suppliers to use biodegradable or reusable food packaging materials, reducing single-use plastics.
- Encourage the procurement of refurbished or second-hand goods, including kitchen appliances and storage equipment, to reduce material waste.

9.1.5. Incentives for implementing green public procurement (GPP) in the circular economy

Transitioning to circular economy models through green public procurement (GPP) requires strong incentives to support businesses, public institutions, and supply chains. A combination of financial, regulatory, and market-based mechanisms can accelerate the adoption of circular principles while ensuring economic feasibility.

9.1.5.1.1. Financial incentives

Economic incentives help offset the initial costs of transitioning to circular business models, ensuring that companies can comply with green public procurement criteria without financial strain.

Subsidies for circular innovation

- Public funding programmes should support companies developing circular products, such as biodegradable packaging, recycled-content materials, or zero-waste supply chains.
- Start-ups and SMEs focusing on circular solutions in the agri-food sector should receive targeted support to scale their innovations.

VAT reductions and tax exemptions

- Reduced VAT rates on goods with high recycled content, promoting the purchase of sustainable materials.
- Tax exemptions for reused, refurbished, and repaired products, making circular alternatives more competitive.

Fiscal benefits for sustainable enterprises

- Companies that meet environmental and circular economy criteria in public tenders should benefit from tax deductions and financial rewards.
- Governments can provide preferential financing options, such as green loans or sustainability-linked bonds, for businesses investing in circular infrastructure.

9.1.5.2.2. Regulatory incentives

Mandatory legal frameworks ensure that circular economy principles become a standard in public procurement.

Recycled content requirements

- Public tenders should enforce minimum thresholds for recycled materials in procurement, such as a mandatory percentage of recycled plastic in food packaging or 100% recycled paper in office supplies.
- These requirements should progressively increase over time to push market adaptation.

Bans on unsustainable products

- Public procurement policies should phase out non-sustainable products, including single-use plastics and high-emission packaging materials.
- Governments should implement progressive bans, giving businesses time to transition.

Mandatory environmental labelling

- Products acquired through public procurement should display environmental impact labels, allowing purchasing authorities to compare sustainability credentials transparently.
- Labels should cover carbon footprint, recyclability, and chemical use to promote low-impact alternatives.

9.1.5.3. Market-based incentives

Public procurement can stimulate emerging markets for circular products by creating demand-driven incentives.

Public tenders supporting circular market growth

- Governments should design procurement contracts that reward companies integrating circular economy principles, ensuring long-term demand for sustainable solutions.

Financial bonuses for sustainable suppliers

- Procurement contracts can offer financial bonuses for companies exceeding minimum sustainability thresholds, encouraging continuous improvement.

Public–private partnerships for circular innovation

- Collaborative agreements between public institutions and private companies can drive research and development in circular economy innovations.
- Initiatives should support technological advancements in waste reduction, bio-based packaging, and closed-loop supply chains.

9.1.6. Strategies to promote organic food consumption

Ensuring organic procurement is not just about compliance—it also requires active promotion and engagement to stimulate demand and create a long-term cultural shift towards sustainable food consumption.

Integrating organic products in public institutions

- Schools, hospitals, and public canteens should include organic products in their menus to promote healthier and more sustainable diets.
- Public institutions can set minimum organic food targets (e.g., 50% organic meals in schools by 2030).

Financial incentives for organic suppliers

- Tax reductions or subsidies can encourage small and medium-sized organic producers to participate in public tenders.
- Lowering the financial barrier for organic food suppliers can increase competition and availability.

Food education in schools and healthcare centres

- Raising awareness about the benefits of organic food among children and patients can influence long-term consumption habits.
- Educational programmes should highlight organic farming's role in environmental protection, biodiversity, and climate change mitigation.

Reducing food waste in public procurement

Food waste is a major issue in public sector catering. Circular public procurement should integrate waste prevention strategies to maximise resource efficiency.

1. Efficient meal planning to avoid surpluses

- Demand-driven procurement should ensure that food orders are aligned with actual consumption levels.
- Public institutions can use predictive analytics tools to adjust order quantities and reduce over-purchasing.

2. Redistribution of surplus food

- Excess food should be donated to food banks, community kitchens, or charities, rather than being discarded.
- Public procurement contracts should include food donation clauses to formalise these redistribution efforts.

3. Leveraging technology for waste reduction

- Smart food management systems can measure waste levels and adjust procurement volumes accordingly.

Best practice example: Finland's smart canteen system (see references)

- In Finland, public canteens use sensors and AI-driven software to track food waste in real-time.
- The data helps adjust future orders, preventing unnecessary food losses.

4. Sustainable and biodegradable packaging

- Public procurement should ban single-use plastics and prioritise biodegradable or compostable packaging.

- Alternatives include bio-based materials made from agrifood waste, aligning with circular economy principles.

9.1.7. Best practices in organic food public procurement

Public procurement policies that prioritise organic and sustainable food have been successfully implemented across several European countries. These initiatives demonstrate how governments can leverage procurement power to support sustainable agriculture, reduce food waste, and promote healthier public meals.

1. Sweden: Leading the way in organic public procurement (see references)

Sweden has set a global benchmark for sustainable food procurement, particularly in schools and healthcare institutions.

- Over 50% of food served in public sector canteens is organic, making Sweden one of the most advanced countries in integrating organic food into public procurement.
- A 20% reduction in food waste has been achieved through real-time monitoring systems that allow adjustments in meal preparation quantities.
- The Swedish government encourages short food supply chains, ensuring that a significant portion of organic food comes from local and regional producers.

2. France: Energy transition law and organic food in public procurement (see references)

France has taken significant legislative steps to integrate organic and locally sourced food into public procurement frameworks.

- Since 2022, 50% of food in public institutions must be either organic or sourced from sustainable local production.
- The government has introduced financial incentives and bonus schemes for suppliers that meet high environmental standards.
- Municipalities have implemented sustainable food action plans, aligning public food procurement with broader climate and biodiversity strategies.

3. Italy: The “Green Catering” certification in public procurement (see references)

Italy has developed a national certification system for sustainable catering in public procurement, setting a strong example for integrating circular economy principles.

- Public contracts require at least 40% of food purchased to be organic, with a preference for local and seasonal products.

- Italy has launched a digital tracking platform that enables public institutions to monitor and report the percentage of sustainable food purchases.
- The certification system also promotes reduced food waste, sustainable packaging, and ethical supply chains.

9.1.8. Successful examples of GPP in the circular economy

Several European cities and countries have successfully implemented GPP strategies with significant environmental and economic benefits.

1. Vienna (Austria) – EcoBuy programme (see references)

- Reduction of 100,000 tonnes of CO₂ emissions and €44.4 million in savings between 2004 and 2007.
- Prioritised circular products and services in public tenders, integrating waste reduction and energy efficiency into procurement contracts.

2. The Netherlands – Sustainable public procurement framework

If all authorities applied circular procurement criteria, the Netherlands could achieve:

- A reduction of 3 million tonnes of CO₂ emissions.
- A 10% decrease in public sector energy consumption.
- The government mandates life-cycle analysis (LCA) in procurement, ensuring long-term sustainability benefits.

3. Copenhagen and Sweden – Sustainable technology procurement

- GPP strategies in Copenhagen and Sweden have led to a reduction of 30 TWh in energy consumption.
- This savings is equivalent to the annual energy production of four nuclear reactors, demonstrating the high-impact potential of green procurement policies.

9.1.8.1. Case studies in Spain: Circular procurement in agrifood systems

Spain has implemented GPP models in regional contexts, with a focus on supporting local food production and circular economy principles.

1. Case study: Urduña (Basque Country)

Sustainable food procurement in a localised agricultural economy

Agricultural context:

- Urduña is characterised by small-scale, non-specialised farms, focusing on local livestock and crop production.
- Traditional extensive livestock farming supports regional biodiversity and local food networks.

Sustainability approach:

- The procurement strategy prioritises local food supply chains, ensuring higher profit margins for farmers.
- Short supply chains enhance economic resilience while reducing transport-related emissions.

Performance indicators:

- The initiative successfully diversified food sources, promoting sustainable farming practices.
- The case study highlights the effectiveness of local food procurement in enhancing rural economic sustainability.

2. Case study: El Vallès (Catalonia)**Green public procurement in a medium-sized agricultural region****Agricultural context:**

- The region is characterised by medium to small-sized municipalities, with a focus on Mediterranean crops such as cereals, legumes, and some intensive pig farming.

GPP model:

- Public food procurement is outsourced to a catering company that manages food supply and preparation for schools.
- The contract integrates ecological criteria, promoting organic and local produce.

Challenges and opportunities:

- While the procurement model supports sustainability, it faces challenges in food sovereignty.
- A significant portion of organic food is sourced from outside Catalonia, limiting local agricultural participation.
- Quality control depends on catering services, reducing direct engagement with local farmers.

9.1.9. References

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9.2. PS2: Guidelines for fostering public engagement in circular economy

9.2.1. 1. Introduction

These guidelines aim to identify effective ways to foster public engagement for each of the four key stakeholder groups involved in circular economy projects. Whenever relevant, a particular focus will be placed on the agrifood sector. To ensure a structured approach to stakeholder engagement, we recommend referring to the **CCRI Methodology**, which offers specific guidance on **involving stakeholders in the development of Circular Systemic Solutions (CSSs)**. A CSS is a project designed to achieve overall sustainability in a local context by applying innovative circular economy models. CSSs facilitate the transition towards a circular economy by addressing factors beyond resource management and waste recovery, considering all aspects that enable or hinder circularity at the local/regional level. **The CCRI Methodology** presents a comprehensive framework to support project promoters, policymakers, and decision-makers in advancing CSSs and broader circular economy initiatives at local and regional scales. Given that the methodology is extensive, we do not reproduce it in full here, but we highlight its key phases as they complement these guidelines:

- **MAP:** This initial phase focuses on analysing the local context and identifying key stakeholders. It involves stakeholder mapping, regulatory framework assessment, and resource and challenge evaluation, ensuring a robust knowledge base for decision-making.
- **DESIGN:** This phase determines priority intervention areas for circularity and develops specific CSS cases. Stakeholders collaborate to co-create solutions that address local needs, define objectives and monitoring indicators, and refine the project through iterative feedback.
- **IMPLEMENT:** This final phase ensures financial resource availability and activates the circular system. It involves preparing for financing, monitoring project performance, adapting systems in real time, and maintaining transparent communication to secure ongoing stakeholder support.

Further details on the CCRI Methodology can be accessed at this [link](#).

The following sections outline key strategies for fostering public engagement in the circular economy, with a specific focus on the agri-food value chain. Drawing on existing research and project-backed activities, it presents policy recommendations and stakeholder roles, highlighting both regulatory and community-driven approaches to advancing circular practices.

9.2.2. What is Public Engagement: introduction and value

Public engagement refers to the process of involving individuals and communities in activities that influence collective decision-making and societal change. Emerging in the 1990s, public engagement became a key element in democratic governance and civic participation, involving citizens in governmental, scientific, and business activities. Public engagement has been essential in tackling environmental issues, particularly climate change and increasingly the circular economy (CE). In the context of the circular economy, public engagement plays a crucial role in shifting behaviours and encouraging participation in sustainable practices. As society moves from a linear economy—based on "take, make, waste"—towards circular models, engaging the public as active stakeholders in adopting and promoting these new systems is essential. This shift demands not just technological innovations but also changes in public attitudes and practices.

Kumpu (2022) draws on existing research to outline two key dimensions of public engagement: **1) Personal engagement:** Personal engagement refers to the cognitive, emotional, and behavioural connection an individual has with an issue. In terms of the circular economy, this involves understanding and embracing circular practices, such as reducing waste or choosing durable products. For example, adopting sustainable consumer habits—like repairing items rather than replacing them or selecting products made from recycled materials—demonstrates personal engagement with circular economy principles. **2) Civic engagement:** Civic engagement focuses on collective actions, such as participating in decision-making and problem-solving. This form of engagement encourages public involvement in shaping policies and creating systems that support circular models. Research highlights that public consultations, citizen juries, and participatory design processes are vital for fostering this type of engagement. Civic engagement in the circular

economy context may include collaboration with local governments, businesses, and NGOs to develop sustainable waste management systems or promote circular business practices.

Both personal and civic engagement are seen as pathways to societal change in the fight against climate change and in fostering a circular economy. The key objective is to encourage a societal shift where public engagement becomes a driver for sustainability. However, this requires more than just raising awareness—it also demands public involvement in decision-making and policy formation. Engagement leads to broader societal transformation when individuals and communities take ownership of sustainability issues and collaborate on solutions. In particular, civic engagement emphasizes collective problem-solving and democratic participation, ensuring that public policies and initiatives reflect the diverse perspectives of the population.

9.2.2.1. Stakeholder collaboration as a driver for CE implementation

- Stakeholder collaboration is critical for the successful implementation of circular economy initiatives, aligning with sustainability concepts and stakeholder theory (Hörisch et al., 2020).
- Active involvement of stakeholders throughout the supply chain fosters shared responsibility for sustainability goals and enhances circular system performance.
- Collaboration between firms, particularly in complex sectors such as healthcare waste management, is often necessary for establishing CE practices (Mishra et al., 2021; Kleine Jäger C Piscicelli, 2021).
- Supply chain collaboration has a positive correlation with environmental sustainability performance (Hussain C Malik, 2020).
- Collaboration not only improves environmental performance but also creates opportunities for economic and social benefits, involving local businesses and communities working together (Ibn-Mohammed et al., 2021).
- Long-term organizational engagement with sustainability concepts increases the likelihood of adopting a circular economy system (Barreiro-Gen C Lozano, 2020).

9.2.3. Stakeholders: who is to be engaged?

In the transition towards a Circular Economy, it is essential to involve a wide range of stakeholders from the beginning of the decision-making process, ensuring collaborative action to achieve shared goals. Stakeholders refer to people and organisations with a direct or indirect interest in circular economy initiatives and who participate in activities that facilitate their implementation. The **Quintuple Helix Model** is a comprehensive framework used to understand the interactions between different stakeholders involved in the transition to a sustainable Circular Economy (CE). This model extends the traditional Triple Helix Model, which focused on the collaboration between government, industry, and academia, by adding two additional critical dimensions: civil society and the natural ecosystem. Together, these five helices represent key stakeholders that drive innovation, eco-innovation, and sustainable practices through their interconnected roles and influences.

The five main stakeholders in the **Quintuple Helix** are:

- **Government:** Public administrations and local authorities that play a key role in governance and oversight of the circular economy.
- **Industry:** Businesses and firms across various sectors that are essential to driving economic activity and innovation.
- **Academia:** Universities and research institutions that contribute through the generation of knowledge and education.
- **Civil society:** Consumers, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and community groups that represent societal interests and advocate for sustainable practices.
- **Ecosystem:** The natural environment, which serves as the foundation for all human and economic activities by providing essential resources and environmental services (van Bueren, 2023).

9.2.3.1. Roles of Key Stakeholders in the Circular Economy

In the transition to a Circular Economy, different stakeholders play essential roles in enabling and sustaining circular practices. The **Quintuple Helix Model** provides a useful framework to understand these roles, highlighting the contributions of government, industry, academia, civil society, and the natural ecosystem.

Figure 10 - Quintuple Helix of Stakeholders representation. From van Bueren (2023)

Public Administration and Local Entities

Public administrations shape the regulatory environment and provide the necessary infrastructure and incentives for circular economy initiatives. Their key roles include:

- **Regulation and enforcement:** Introducing and enforcing policies such as waste separation, extended producer responsibility, and minimum recycled content requirements.
- **Financial support:** Creating funding schemes and subsidies for circular initiatives, fostering investment in circular business models.
- **Public procurement and awareness:** Promoting circular public procurement and running campaigns to increase consumer acceptance of circular products.
- **Business facilitation:** Reducing bureaucratic obstacles and fostering public-private partnerships (PPPs) to scale circular economy solutions.

Industry and Business

Businesses and industries drive circularity through innovation, resource efficiency, and new business models. Their key roles include:

- **Circular business models:** Shifting towards reuse, refurbishment, remanufacturing, and recycling to minimise waste and extend product lifecycles.
- **Supply chain transformation:** Incorporating circular principles into production, logistics, and sourcing practices.
- **Industrial symbiosis:** Collaborating with other industries to optimise resource use and reduce waste.

Civil Society

Consumers, NGOs, and community groups play a fundamental role in shaping demand for circular products and advocating for sustainable policies. Their key roles include:

- **Sustainable consumption:** Adopting reuse, repair, and sharing economy practices to extend product lifecycles.
- **Advocacy and awareness:** NGOs and community groups promote circular economy policies and engage in capacity-building initiatives.
- **Behavioural shifts:** Societal influences, including media and culture, help normalise circular behaviours and drive systemic change.

Academia and Technological Organisations

Universities and research institutions contribute to the Circular Economy by generating knowledge, developing innovations, and providing education. Their key roles include:

- **Research and innovation:** Advancing circular economy solutions, such as biodegradable materials and sustainable production techniques.
- **Education and capacity-building:** Training professionals and raising awareness of circular principles in society and industry.
- **Knowledge transfer:** Collaborating with businesses and governments to scale up circular innovations.

Ecosystem

The natural environment serves as the foundation for human and economic activities, providing essential resources and absorbing waste. Its key roles include:

- **Resource regeneration:** Maintaining the natural cycles of water, air, and materials necessary for sustainability.

- **Carbon sequestration:** Acting as a natural carbon sink through forests, peatlands, and wetlands.
- **Biodiversity support:** Ensuring ecological balance by preserving ecosystems that sustain circular resource flows.

9.2.4. Public Sector: guidelines for fostering circular economy projects in agrifood

Below is a set of guidelines for fostering public engagement (understood as both personal and civic engagement) in the circular economy, adapted to the agrifood value chain. Based on the evidence presented in the study by Alonso-Almeida et al. (2020), public sector efforts to promote CE can be classified into **soft** and **hard** initiatives, each influencing circular consumption and market competitiveness differently.

- **Soft initiatives** focus on **raising awareness and providing information** to consumers. These include campaigns that highlight CE benefits, labels that enhance product credibility, and educational programmes to reduce consumer uncertainty. These measures have been found to positively influence circular consumption and market competitiveness by increasing consumer trust and demand for circular products.
- **Hard initiatives** involve **regulatory and financial incentives that directly shape market behaviour**. These include differentiated taxation levels for resource-efficient products, extended producer responsibility schemes, and green public procurement (GPP) to stimulate industry engagement. Research suggests that while hard initiatives significantly drive circular consumption, they do not always translate into improved market competitiveness.

A key finding from Alonso-Almeida et al. (2020) is that stakeholder responses to these initiatives vary. While businesses and professional associations value soft initiatives for their impact on competitiveness, consumers respond more positively to financial incentives and extended guarantees, which underscores the need for tailored policy approaches that align with stakeholder priorities.

1. Examples of soft initiatives

- **Awareness campaigns:** Large-scale communication efforts to inform the public about CE principles, benefits, and practical applications. These should highlight success stories and make CE engagement more tangible for citizens.
- **Consumer education:** Integrating CE concepts into formal education and public workshops to increase understanding and acceptance of circular consumption practices.
- **Transparency and labelling:** Ensuring clear, credible, and standardised information about CE products, such as product lifespan, recyclability, and environmental impact.
- **Incentivising voluntary participation:** Encouraging public involvement through recognition schemes, certifications, or small-scale financial rewards for pro-circular behaviours (e.g., waste sorting, product returns).

2. Examples of hard initiatives

- **Regulatory frameworks:** Implementing extended producer responsibility (EPR) schemes, minimum recyclability requirements, and tax incentives for circular business models.
- **Green public procurement (GPP):** Setting sustainability criteria in public tenders to increase demand for circular products, indirectly influencing private sector adoption.
- **Financial incentives:** Implementing tax reductions or subsidies for consumers who purchase circular products or services, making sustainable choices economically attractive.
- **Infrastructure investments:** Developing CE-friendly urban infrastructure, such as collection points for food waste, repair and refurbishment centres, and local bio-waste processing facilities.

9.2.4.1. Recommendations to foster public engagement in the Circular Economy:

1. Enhance Consumer Awareness and Information Accessibility

- Implement large-scale awareness campaigns to educate consumers on the benefits of CE.

- Develop and enforce clear labelling systems that indicate product sustainability, durability, and reparability.
- Promote digital platforms where consumers can access information on CE principles and available circular products.

2. Introduce Economic Incentives for Circular Consumption

- Reduce VAT or offer tax incentives for circular products, such as refurbished electronics and sustainable packaging.
- Establish deposit-return schemes for packaging and other recyclables.
- Encourage businesses to offer extended warranties and leasing options to reduce planned obsolescence.

3. Strengthen Green Public Procurement (GPP) Policies

- Require that all public sector purchases prioritise products with high recyclability and resource efficiency.
- Implement procurement criteria that favour businesses adopting circular business models.
- Facilitate knowledge exchange between policymakers and businesses to streamline GPP implementation.

4. Support Industrial and Agricultural Circular Initiatives

- Provide grants and funding opportunities for businesses innovating in CE practices.
- Foster industrial symbiosis by creating regional clusters where waste from one sector serves as raw material for another.
- Encourage the agro-food sector to integrate waste valorisation processes, such as bio-based packaging and nutrient recovery from organic residues.

5. Develop Circular Economy Education and Community Engagement

- Integrate CE principles into school curricula and vocational training programmes.
- Support citizen-led initiatives, such as repair cafes and community composting projects.
- Promote behavioural change campaigns that encourage sustainable consumption habits.

6. Improve Waste Management Infrastructure and Traceability

- Invest in smart waste management technologies, such as blockchain-based traceability systems for recyclable materials.
- Expand separate collection systems for different waste streams, ensuring higher-quality recycling outputs.
- Partner with the private sector to develop take-back schemes and reverse logistics systems.

9.2.4.2. Sector-Specific Recommendations for the Agri-Food Value Chain

1. Incentivise Sustainable Agricultural Practices

- Offer subsidies for precision farming techniques that minimise waste and resource use.
- Promote regenerative agricultural methods that restore soil health and enhance biodiversity.

2. Encourage Food Waste Prevention and Valorisation

- Implement policies that require supermarkets and food producers to donate surplus food.
- Support the development of bio-based materials derived from agricultural residues, such as biodegradable packaging and biofertilisers.
- Facilitate the industrial-scale adoption of innovative waste valorisation processes, such as enzyme-assisted extraction of bioactive compounds.

3. Promote Circular Supply Chains in the Food Industry

- Encourage local sourcing and closed-loop supply chains to reduce transport emissions and waste.
- Develop certification schemes for circular food production, ensuring transparency and consumer trust.
- Foster collaboration between farmers, food processors, and waste management companies to optimise resource efficiency.

9.2.4.3. Fostering public engagement beyond market-driven approaches

The study by Ortega Alvarado, Pettersen, and Berker (2022) highlights the need to reframe the circular economy (CE) beyond mere technological solutions and market-driven approaches. The authors argue that CE must integrate social and cultural dimensions,

particularly by addressing consumerism as an institutional logic that shapes material consumption. Their research, based on case studies in Norway, reveals several shortcomings in existing CE policies and identifies alternative logics that public administrations can leverage to foster public engagement in circular practices.

Promoting institutional frameworks that support alternative consumption practices

Evidence from the study: The authors demonstrate that current CE policies often reinforce market-based and technocratic solutions, such as corporate-led recycling or waste-to-energy strategies, rather than supporting citizen-led initiatives that extend product life cycles (e.g., repair, reuse, and upcycling). Their findings indicate that alternative practices (e.g., repair clubs, communal tool-sharing, and waste recovery networks) are often marginalised or exist in tension with dominant economic logics.

Policy implication: Public administrations should develop institutional mechanisms that legitimise and integrate these grassroots initiatives into formal CE strategies. This could include:

- Recognising community repair initiatives as official CE actors rather than informal or marginal activities.
- Providing public funding and resources for community-led CE projects.
- Facilitating partnerships between local authorities, civil society, and informal CE practitioners.

Considering the agrifood value chain

Policy implication: Public administrations should develop institutional mechanisms to integrate and legitimise alternative food consumption practices in CE strategies. This could include:

- Recognising food-sharing initiatives, urban gleaning groups, and community-supported agriculture (CSA) schemes as key actors in CE, ensuring they are eligible for policy support.
- Providing funding for local food networks, including farmers' markets, cooperative grocery stores, and short food supply chains.
- Facilitating partnerships between food producers, social enterprises, local authorities, and consumers to encourage food redistribution and waste prevention at the community level.

Supporting community initiatives that reinforce use-value over market-value

Evidence from the study: The authors find that many grassroots initiatives focus on extending the lifespan of products through social interactions, rather than treating CE as a business opportunity. For instance, repair clubs and communal spaces in Trondheim function as sites of skill-sharing and community-building, rather than profit-making. This aligns with their argument that CE should be a practice-driven institutional transformation, rather than just an economic model.

Policy implication: Public administrations should:

- Fund public repair spaces in community centres or libraries, similar to how public services support education or digital literacy.
- Develop repair and reuse networks that encourage citizens to share skills and tools, rather than relying solely on commercial repair services.
- Reframe CE policies to highlight the social and cultural benefits of repair and reuse, rather than just their economic or environmental efficiency.

Considering the agrifood value chain

Policy implication: Public administrations should:

- Fund community food hubs, seed-saving initiatives, and cooperative farms, ensuring they have stable financial support.
- Promote agroecology and local food networks as alternatives to industrialised food production, including through public procurement in schools and hospitals.
- Reframe CE policies to highlight the social and cultural benefits of alternative food systems, rather than just focusing on waste valorisation.

Reforming regulations that penalise reuse and waste recovery

Evidence from the study: The research shows that legal barriers often obstruct citizen-led waste recovery. For example, one interviewee engaged in electronic repair and recovery was forced to leave his job because Norwegian law treats discarded electronics as company-owned waste, making informal recovery illegal. Similarly, dumpster diving is only legally viable when waste is not locked away, creating unnecessary institutional obstacles for waste reduction efforts.

Policy implication: Local and national governments should:

- Amend regulations to allow certain types of informal or small-scale waste recovery (e.g., enabling individuals or repair shops to salvage and reuse discarded electronics legally).
- Encourage take-back schemes that prioritise repair and redistribution rather than destruction and disposal.
- Create secondary markets for recovered goods, reducing unnecessary barriers to resale or donation.

Considering the agrifood value chain

Policy implication: Governments should:

- Revise food safety laws to facilitate safe food redistribution while maintaining public health standards.
- Encourage take-back schemes that enable farmers and food retailers to redistribute surplus food rather than discarding it.
- Support secondary markets for recovered food by reducing barriers to selling ‘imperfect’ produce, surplus grains, or food close to expiration dates.

Strengthening education and knowledge-sharing

Evidence from the study: The research highlights that practical knowledge of repair and reuse is often passed down informally (e.g., through families, local repair groups, and online communities). However, these skills are not widely accessible, and many citizens remain dependent on disposable consumption patterns due to a lack of repair competencies. The study identifies community learning spaces—such as bike repair clubs and clothing repair groups—as crucial for expanding repair knowledge but notes that these initiatives struggle with visibility and institutional support.

Policy implication: Public administrations should:

- Integrate repair and reuse education into formal school curricula, vocational training, and lifelong learning programmes.
- Support local repair groups with training grants and public awareness campaigns to normalise repair practices.
- Develop digital platforms where citizens can access repair tutorials, exchange second-hand goods, and find local repair services.

Considering the agrifood value chain

Policy implication: Public administrations should:

- Integrate sustainable food practices into school curricula, vocational training, and public awareness campaigns. This could include food preservation, composting, regenerative farming, and plant-based cooking skills.
- Support knowledge-sharing networks that connect farmers, chefs, and consumers in sustainable food initiatives.
- Develop digital platforms for food-sharing, community-supported agriculture, and waste prevention, making CE food practices more accessible.

Implementing fiscal and economic incentives for circular practices

Evidence from the study: The authors highlight that repair services in Norway are often prohibitively expensive, making it cheaper for consumers to buy new products instead. This is largely due to labour costs and taxation structures that favour new product sales over repair services. Their findings align with broader critiques of CE policies that prioritise market-driven solutions over sufficiency-based models.

Policy implication: Governments should:

- Reduce taxes on repair services, making them more affordable compared to new product purchases.
- Provide subsidies or tax deductions for businesses and community initiatives that extend product life cycles.
- Introduce producer responsibility policies that require companies to offer longer product warranties, repair services, and spare parts availability.

Considering the agrifood value chain

Policy implication: Governments should:

- Reduce VAT on organic, local, and circular food products, making them more competitive with industrial food.
- Provide subsidies for small-scale regenerative agriculture and local processing initiatives, reducing reliance on long supply chains and food imports.
- Introduce financial incentives for surplus food redistribution, such as tax deductions for businesses that donate unsold food.

Rethinking circular economy policies from a socio-cultural perspective

Evidence from the study: Ortega et al. (2022) argue that the dominant technocentric approach to CE fails to question consumerism as a structural issue. Instead, mainstream CE discourse often promotes business-led strategies that reinforce market growth, rather than tackling the underlying overconsumption problem. Their findings show that alternative CE models—such as community sharing, cooperative ownership, and non-market exchanges—challenge this paradigm but receive little institutional support.

Policy implication: Public administrations should:

- Shift from growth-based CE models towards sufficiency-driven policies that prioritise waste prevention, reuse, and social inclusion.
- Support non-market circular practices (e.g., tool libraries, skill-sharing platforms, and community resource banks).
- Recognise CE as a cultural and institutional transformation, not just an economic opportunity.

Considering the agrifood value chain

Policy implication: Public administrations should:

- Shift from waste valorisation strategies to sufficiency-driven policies, prioritising food waste prevention, short food supply chains, and regenerative farming.
- Support non-market circular food practices, such as gleaning networks, cooperative food hubs, and direct farm-to-consumer models.
- Recognise circular food systems as a cultural and institutional transformation, not just an economic opportunity.

9.2.4.4. Social media for fostering public engagement

The increasing use of social media for stakeholder engagement presents opportunities for public institutions to enhance participation in circular economy initiatives. Evidence from the agri-food sector indicates that digital platforms can serve as effective tools to promote awareness, foster dialogue, and encourage collective action towards sustainability. Based on findings from an analysis of Twitter discussions on circular economy and agri-food

(Esposito, B., et. al, 2023), the following recommendations outline how the public sector can strengthen its engagement strategies.

Recommendations

1. **Integrate social media into public engagement strategies:** Public authorities should incorporate social media channels into their broader communication frameworks for circular economy initiatives. Engagement strategies should move beyond traditional one-way information dissemination and prioritize interactive content that facilitates dialogue and participation.
2. **Promote a balanced approach to circular economy communication:** Public discourse on circular economy in the agri-food sector is heavily focused on recycling, with less attention given to reduction and redesign strategies. Public institutions should ensure that all pillars of the circular economy are equally addressed, emphasizing waste prevention, resource efficiency, and systemic innovation alongside recycling efforts.
3. **Encourage two-way communication with stakeholders:** Posts that invite interaction generate higher levels of engagement. Public institutions should design digital campaigns that encourage responses, discussions, and user-generated content. Mechanisms such as moderated Q&A sessions, citizen consultations, and participatory decision-making forums can increase public involvement.
4. **Facilitate cross-sectoral collaboration through digital platforms:** Governments and municipal authorities should use social media to connect businesses, researchers, and civil society organizations working on circular economy initiatives. Publicly accessible digital platforms can help disseminate best practices, showcase local projects, and foster multi-stakeholder cooperation.
5. **Develop sector-specific guidelines for effective digital engagement:** Public authorities should provide tailored guidelines on how businesses, municipalities, and organizations can communicate their circular economy efforts effectively. These guidelines should include recommendations on tone, content structure, and best practices for engaging diverse audiences, including consumers and industry stakeholders.
6. **Monitor and evaluate public engagement efforts:** Tracking engagement metrics, such as interaction rates, public sentiment, and participation levels, is essential for

refining outreach strategies. Public institutions should establish mechanisms to assess the effectiveness of their digital engagement initiatives and adapt their approaches based on public response and emerging trends.

9.2.5. The Role of Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) in fostering public engagement in the Circular Economy

Civil society organisations (CSOs) play a crucial role in fostering public engagement in the circular economy (CE) by acting as intermediaries, knowledge disseminators, and advocates for systemic change. Drawing inspiration from the interplay between CSOs and businesses in CE transitions, we outline three key approaches through which CSOs can enhance public engagement in circular economy initiatives:

1. Awareness and campaign-based engagement

CSOs can mobilise communities through targeted awareness campaigns that highlight the urgency of transitioning to a circular economy. Public engagement strategies such as educational workshops, community clean-up events, and digital advocacy campaigns can help citizens understand CE principles and their relevance to everyday life. These initiatives often rely on social pressure and media amplification to promote sustainable behaviours. However, while awareness campaigns increase visibility, their long-term impact depends on sustained efforts and follow-up actions that translate knowledge into tangible behavioural change.

2. Resource efficiency and behavioural change initiatives

Beyond raising awareness, CSOs can facilitate public engagement by promoting practical interventions that encourage waste reduction, reuse, and repair. Initiatives such as repair cafés, tool-sharing schemes, and zero-waste consumption challenges provide opportunities for citizens to directly participate in circular practices. CSOs can collaborate with local businesses and policymakers to co-design incentive schemes, such as deposit-return systems or tax benefits for sustainable consumer choices. The key challenge in this approach is maintaining engagement beyond initial enthusiasm, which requires integrating CE-friendly practices into local economies and social norms.

3. Collaborative circular design and policy co-creation

For deeper engagement, CSOs can position themselves as co-creators of circular economy policies and initiatives, involving citizens in participatory decision-making processes. This

approach aligns with the concept of ‘boundary work,’ where CSOs mediate between policymakers, businesses, and communities to develop CE solutions that reflect local needs. Examples include citizen assemblies on waste management, co-design of circular urban planning strategies, and participatory budgeting for CE projects. This model fosters long-term commitment and system-level change, but it requires strong institutional partnerships and resource allocation to support sustained involvement.

9.2.5.1. Recommendations for CSOs’ relationships with business/industry

1. Adopt a multi-strategy approach to engagement

- CSOs should recognize that engagement with businesses can take multiple forms, including collaboration and contestation. Based on Ho et al. (2022), CSOs can engage in three types of CE boundary work:
 - **Campaign-based approach:** Using public campaigns and advocacy to exert pressure on businesses to address end-of-life product issues.
 - **Resource efficiency-based approach:** Partnering with businesses to improve efficiency in resource use, with a focus on incremental and pragmatic CE transitions.
 - **Circular design-based approach:** Deep collaborations where CSOs work directly with firms to redesign products and services to eliminate waste and embed circularity.

2. Use boundary work strategies to enhance collaboration

- CSOs should engage in boundary work to create, maintain, or disrupt existing practices and norms in businesses. This includes:
 - **Competitive boundary work:** Differentiating their CE agenda and advocating for sustainable alternatives.
 - **Collaborative boundary work:** Aligning with businesses on shared CE goals and developing joint initiatives.
 - **Configurational boundary work:** Bridging diverse actor perspectives to facilitate systemic change.

3. Leverage campaign-based activism for initial engagement

- As demonstrated by the Beach Guardian campaign against PepsiCo, public pressure can be effective in forcing businesses to take responsibility for their

waste streams. However, CSOs should aim to transition from confrontation to collaboration when opportunities arise.

4. **Facilitate resource efficiency initiatives**

- CSOs can provide businesses with tools, knowledge, and practical strategies to improve resource efficiency, such as reducing packaging waste or implementing refill schemes. The Plastic Free Communities initiative by Surfers Against Sewage illustrates how grassroots mobilization can successfully engage local businesses in waste reduction.

5. **Engage in circular design collaborations**

- CSOs should seek partnerships with firms that go beyond incremental changes and instead aim for systemic CE innovation. The collaboration between A Grain of Sand and The Wave highlights how deep integration of sustainability expertise within a company can result in fundamental changes to business models and production processes.

6. **Act as knowledge brokers and intermediaries**

- CSOs should position themselves as intermediaries in CE transitions, translating technical knowledge and sustainability principles into actionable strategies for businesses. This role is critical in aligning different stakeholders and facilitating cross-sectoral collaboration.

7. **Combine contestation with cooperation**

- Rather than seeing collaboration and contestation as mutually exclusive, CSOs should strategically navigate both approaches depending on context. Campaign-based activism can open the door for dialogue, while direct collaboration can lead to long-term CE integration within businesses.

9.2.6. **The role of business/industry in fostering public engagement**

Strengthening CSR as a catalyst for the circular economy

Companies in the agrifood sector should integrate CSR principles into their business strategies to support circular economy (CE) initiatives, as CSR-driven actions enhance resource efficiency, waste reduction, and sustainable production practices.

The study highlights that firms that actively incorporate CSR models tend to be more oriented towards circularity, demonstrating a higher commitment to sustainability goals.

Encouraging stakeholder engagement

Businesses should actively engage with stakeholders, including consumers, suppliers, policymakers, and local communities, to foster collaboration on circular economy practices. According to the study, transparency in sustainability efforts strengthens consumer trust and encourages broader participation in CE initiatives, ensuring long-term engagement from various actors.

Investing in innovation and sustainable practices

Companies should allocate resources to R&D for the development of innovative, eco-friendly packaging, sustainable sourcing, and waste valorisation, as these elements have been identified as key drivers in the transition towards a circular economy.

The research findings suggest that circular business models, such as product-as-a-service and closed-loop supply chains, contribute significantly to the reduction of environmental impact and resource conservation.

Leveraging policy support and incentives

Businesses should align their CSR and CE strategies with existing policies and regulatory frameworks to maximise impact, as regulatory alignment facilitates smoother implementation of circular economy principles.

The study underscores the role of government incentives, such as tax reductions or funding mechanisms, in encouraging businesses to transition towards more sustainable operations and long-term adherence to CE practices.

Measuring and communicating impact

Companies should adopt clear metrics and key performance indicators (KPIs) to assess the impact of CSR and circular economy initiatives, as the research highlights that effective impact measurement can enhance corporate accountability.

Transparent reporting and regular communication of sustainability progress not only reinforce corporate commitment but also serve as a model for industry-wide adoption, leading to greater overall sustainability in the agrifood sector.

9.2.7. 7. Successful cases in stakeholder engagement

9.2.7.1. Stakeholder engagement in a centrally coordinated circular economy (CE) ecosystem: Case A – publicly organised regional endeavour in Tampere, Finland

Steps for achieving stakeholder engagement

Step 1: Identifying, prioritizing, and selecting CE ecosystem stakeholders

In the context of Tampere, the city has adopted a broad and inclusive approach to stakeholder identification. By organizing open seminars, the city attracts diverse potential stakeholders without limiting selection by strict criteria. The focus is on engaging companies, research institutions, and public organizations that share an interest in solving the environmental issue posed by the by-product. This strategy emphasizes transparency and inclusivity, ensuring a wide net is cast for potential collaborations.

Step 2: Reaching out to stakeholders and securing their interests

The city, in collaboration with local research organizations, works to secure stakeholder interest by sharing state-of-the-art knowledge and openly marketing the problem and potential solutions. Open seminars and events provide a platform for engaging stakeholders, while research organizations actively interview potential participants to gauge their interest and expertise. Information is shared through local media and personal contacts at relevant conferences, ensuring widespread dissemination of the CE goal.

Step 3: Interacting, building relationships, and encouraging learning

Once stakeholders are engaged, the city encourages continued collaboration by fostering an environment of mutual learning and relationship building. Pilot projects serve as an experimental space for companies and organizations to test CE solutions and explore partnerships. The city supports these pilots by providing resources and commissioning research studies, ensuring all stakeholders have access to the necessary data and technical support. This phase strengthens trust and solidifies partnerships, as participants work toward shared goals.

Step 4: Evaluating stakeholder engagement outcomes and processes

Evaluation is a critical component of the CE ecosystem in Tampere. The city assesses the feasibility of proposed solutions using its public procurement criteria, ensuring that projects are both sustainable and cost-effective. This step is essential for refining the solutions developed during the pilot phase and determining their potential for long-term

implementation. The continuous evaluation process also serves as a feedback mechanism to improve future stakeholder engagement efforts.

9.2.7.2. Stakeholder engagement in a centrally coordinated circular economy (CE) ecosystem: Case B – national beverage packaging recycling in Finland

Case B highlights the development of a deposit-based recycling ecosystem for beverage packaging in Finland, led by a non-profit organization, Suomen Palautuspakkaus Ltd. (Palpa), along with other key stakeholders from the brewery and retail industries, consumers, and material utilizers. The system-level goal of the CE ecosystem is to build a sustainable and efficient recycling system. Although beverage packaging recycling is legislated, the initiative was first introduced in the 1950s by the proactive efforts of the brewery industry. Over time, this CE ecosystem has evolved into a widely recognized national institution that many stakeholders naturally seek to join. The boundaries of the ecosystem are primarily national and industry-based, centred around the brewery and retail industries.

Key stakeholders, including the brewery industry, retail industry, recycling operators, and logistics providers, collaborate through a centralized hub. The hub, owned by major national companies from these industries, supervises and manages the recycling system while balancing competing interests, ensuring that the system remains efficient and consumer-friendly:

"Palpa's role is to oversee the operational side of the return system and to balance the interests of retail and brewery industries to maintain efficiency and consumer-friendliness."

(Manager, brewery industry).

As the ecosystem grows, stakeholders not originally covered by legislation, such as juice producers, now seek to join and promote the circular economy.

Steps for achieving stakeholder engagement

Step 1: Identifying, prioritizing, and selecting CE ecosystem stakeholders

In this national CE ecosystem, stakeholders often self-identify the potential benefits of membership and actively approach the hub to apply for inclusion in the system. The hub has established clear criteria to select stakeholders who meet the requirements of the ecosystem, ensuring alignment with the recycling and sustainability goals of the initiative. Since the system is embedded in national institutions and culture, it has become self-evident

and highly visible to potential stakeholders, making identification and selection more straightforward.

Step 2: Reaching out to stakeholders and securing their interests

The hub effectively communicates the benefits of joining the ecosystem through a wide range of marketing and educational materials available on its website and in the media. The long-standing presence of the ecosystem, embedded in national culture and institutional frameworks, naturally attracts stakeholders from various sectors, including consumers, beverage producers, retailers, and material recyclers. The hub's reputation as a trusted and efficient entity ensures that stakeholders recognize the value of collaboration within this well-established CE system.

Step 3: Interacting, building relationships, and encouraging learning

The hub plays a critical role in balancing the sometimes-competing interests of its stakeholders, such as the brewery and retail industries. Regular meetings are organized to discuss common goals and ensure smooth cooperation. Stakeholders actively participate in co-developing the CE ecosystem by sharing trade secrets, legal aspects, and other sensitive information with the mutually trusted hub. This openness fosters strong relationships and encourages a collaborative learning environment. The hub also establishes common guidelines for stakeholders, building trust and ensuring the continued success of the ecosystem.

Step 4: Evaluating stakeholder engagement outcomes and processes

The hub collects operational data and shares it with relevant authorities, such as regional bodies, to ensure compliance and enable further support for stakeholders. Based on the hub's reports, regional authorities can approve and facilitate the fulfilment of stakeholders' interests, including economic benefits like tax exemptions. This evaluative process allows the hub to track the performance of the CE ecosystem and ensure that it continues to meet the needs of its stakeholders while remaining aligned with broader sustainability goals.

9.2.7.3. Stakeholder engagement in a centrally coordinated circular economy (CE) ecosystem: Case C – global sustainable fast-food business

Steps for achieving stakeholder engagement

Step 1: Identifying, prioritizing, and selecting CE ecosystem stakeholders

In this global CE ecosystem, Hesburger identifies stakeholders based on their potential contribution to the fast-food industry's value chains. The hub prioritizes those that align with its sustainability requirements, values, and long-term relationship potential, ensuring a focus on stakeholders who can support its global sustainability objectives. By selecting stakeholders such as packaging suppliers, research partners, and regulators, Hesburger ensures that the ecosystem remains aligned with both environmental and economic goals.

Step 2: Reaching out to stakeholders and securing their interests

To attract and engage key stakeholders, the hub utilizes joint research projects, industry associations, and broad marketing campaigns that highlight its commitment to sustainability. The company promotes its CE goals by sparking general discussion and raising awareness about food sustainability within society. By publicly aligning its operations with sustainable practices, Hesburger not only secures the interest of environmentally conscious stakeholders but also encourages traditional business partners to adapt to new CE goals.

Step 3: Interacting, building relationships, and encouraging learning

Hesburger fosters long-term relationships with its stakeholders by promoting mutual learning and collaboration through joint circular economy projects. The hub provides platforms for stakeholders to share ideas, including a digital platform where individual representatives can contribute their perspectives on CE solutions. Moreover, the company actively works to engage stakeholders with divergent interests by educating them on the benefits of CE practices. This proactive dissemination of information ensures that all stakeholders remain informed and involved, even if their initial priorities are not fully aligned with the sustainability goals.

Step 4: Evaluating stakeholder engagement outcomes and processes

To assess the success of the ecosystem, Hesburger evaluates stakeholder engagement outcomes based on both sustainability and economic criteria. By focusing on these dual measures of success, the company ensures that the CE initiatives are both environmentally beneficial and profitable, promoting the long-term viability of the ecosystem. This continuous evaluation process allows Hesburger to refine its engagement strategies and optimize the value of its stakeholder relationships.

9.2.7.4. Stakeholder engagement in a self-organised circular economy (CE) ecosystem: Case D – regional public–private collaboration for shared good

Case D highlights a self-organised regional circular economy (CE) ecosystem that emerged through public–private collaboration in Forssa, Finland. Local companies, public organizations, and research institutions worked together with the shared goal of enhancing local prosperity and promoting public welfare through industrial symbiosis. The Envi Grow Park, located in a new landfill area of the city, became the focal point for this ecosystem, with stakeholders contributing various material flows, such as wood, glass, and biowaste. Initially formed organically, the ecosystem was later promoted and supported by public organizations, which provided facilitation in the form of funding, marketing, and consulting services.

Stakeholder interests varied; companies saw business opportunities in exchanging materials, while public organizations viewed the ecosystem as a way to promote sustainable local development and societal welfare. This collaboration has broadened the ecosystem's boundaries and diversified the stakeholder base, with engaged parties now considering the inclusion of stakeholders from other areas within the city's region. The senior manager of a local waste management company remarked on the organic nature of the collaboration:

"I know very well the environmental-oriented companies in Finland, so I personally have had a lot of negotiations during the years that we have an excellent area in Forssa, [saying,] 'Please come and build your company here,' though it was not my job, rather a hobby."

Steps for achieving stakeholder engagement

Step 1: Identifying, prioritizing, and selecting CE ecosystem stakeholders

In this self-organised CE ecosystem, local companies played a crucial role in identifying stakeholders with compatible resource flows through their personal contacts and industry knowledge. Public organizations, on the other hand, identified potential stakeholders based on the needs of the regional ecosystem. This dual approach ensured that stakeholders with a shared vision of promoting local prosperity and sustainable material exchanges were prioritised and selected.

Step 2: Reaching out to stakeholders and securing their interests

Public organizations took the lead in marketing the CE ecosystem's brand, reaching out to regional and national stakeholders to generate interest. Engaged companies, in turn, spread knowledge about the benefits of participating in the ecosystem through informal networks

and word-of-mouth. This organic method of outreach helped build trust and credibility, encouraging additional stakeholders to join the initiative.

Step 3: Interacting, building relationships, and encouraging learning

Once stakeholders were engaged, collaboration deepened through personal contacts, shared histories, and mutual trust. Companies and public organizations worked closely to address any issues, with public institutions regularly meeting with companies to identify problems and provide resources, such as legal support and funding. This interactive, trust-based approach fostered long-term relationships and allowed for continuous learning and adaptation within the ecosystem.

Step 4: Evaluating stakeholder engagement outcomes and processes

Evaluation in this self-organised CE ecosystem is largely individualized. Stakeholders assess the success of their engagement based on their specific interests and goals. For companies, the evaluation focuses on the business opportunities and material exchanges achieved through the collaboration, while public organizations evaluate the impact on local welfare and sustainability. This flexible, stakeholder-driven evaluation process ensures that the ecosystem remains responsive to the varying needs of its participants.

9.2.8. References

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